

Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences

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UY-JOY KOMMUNAL XIZMAT KO'RSATISH TIZIMIDA SUV TA'MINOTI VA SUV RESURSLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH

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***Kalit so'zlar:** Kommunal, uy-joy, xo'jalik, infratuzilma, mahalliy, kapital, texnologiya, modernizatsiya, kanalizatsiya, investitsiya.*

Suv ta'minoti — suv iste'molchilariga yer usti yoki yer osti suvlarini kerakli miqdorda va suv obyektlaridagi suv sifatining maqsadli ko'rsatkichlariga muvofiq yetkazib berish.

Suv turli xil iste'molchilar tomonidan turli xil ehtiyojlar uchun iste'mol qilinadi. Biroq, ushbu xarajatlarning katta qismini asosiy toifalarga ajratish mumkin:

maishiy va ichimlik ehtiyojlari uchun xarajatlar (ichish, pishirish, yuvish, uylarni toza saqlash va boshqalar);

ishlab chiqarish ehtiyojlari uchun xarajatlar (sanoat, transport, energetika, qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarini tomonidan iste'mol va boshqalar).

Markazlashtirilgan va markazlashtirilmagan suv ta'minoti mavjud. Markazlashtirilgan suv ta'minoti suv ta'minotini tashkil etish orqali bir nechta suv olish punktlarini suv bilan ta'minlaydi, bu muhandislik inshootlari majmuasi bo'lib, uning yordamida suv ta'minoti manbasidan suv olinadi, uning sifatini suv iste'molchisining talablariga yetkazish uchun zarur bo'lgan ishlov berish, iste'mol joyiga suv yetkazib berish va iste'molchilar o'rtasida taqsimlash. Ichimlik suvining sifati GOST tomonidan tartibga solinadi. Markazlashtirilgan maishiy va ichimlik suvi ta'minoti yer usti yoki yer osti suv manbalarida tashkil etiladi.

Suv ta'minoti tizimi-bu ma'lum bir (berilgan) iste'molchilar guruhini (ushbu ob'ektni) kerakli miqdorda va kerakli sifatda suv bilan ta'minlash uchun tuzilmalar majmui. Bundan tashqari, suv ta'minoti tizimi ma'lum darajada ishonchlilikka ega bo'lishi kerak, ya'ni iste'molchilarga yetkazib beriladigan suv miqdori yoki sifatiga nisbatan belgilangan ish ko'rsatkichlarining qabul qilinishi mumkin bo'lmagan pasayishsiz suv yetkazib berishni ta'minlashi kerak (uzilishlar yoki suv ta'minotining pasayishi yoki uning sifatining qabul qilinishi mumkin bo'lmagan chegaralarda yomonlashishi).

Suv ta'minoti tizimi (aholi punkti yoki sanoat korxonasi) tabiiy manbalardan suv olishni, iste'molchilarning talablari tufayli uni tozalashni va iste'mol joylariga yetkazib berishni ta'minlashi kerak. Ushbu vazifalarni bajarish uchun odatda suv ta'minoti tizimining bir qismi bo'lgan quyidagi tuzilmalar ishlatiladi:

tabiiy manbalardan suv olinadigan suv olish inshootlari;

suvni ko'tarish inshootlari, ya'ni suvni tozalash, saqlash yoki iste'mol qilish joylariga yetkazib beradigan nasos stantsiyalari;

suvni tozalash inshootlari;

suvni iste'mol qilish joylariga tashish va yetkazib berish uchun xizmat qiladigan suv quvurlari va suv ta'minoti tarmoqlari;

suv ta'minoti tizimida tartibga soluvchi va zaxira idishlar rolini o'ynaydigan minoralar va tanklar.

Mahalliy tabiiy sharoitlarga va suv iste'molining xususiyatiga, shuningdek iqtisodiy jihatlarga qarab, suv ta'minoti sxemasi va uning tarkibiy elementlari juda ko'p o'zgarishi mumkin. Qabul qilingan suv

ta'minoti manbai suv ta'minoti sxemasiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi: uning tabiati, kuchi, undagi suv sifati, undan suv bilan ta'minlangan ob'ektgacha bo'lgan masofa va boshqalar.

Suv ta'minoti tizimlari bir qator asosiy xususiyatlarga ko'ra tasniflanishi mumkin.

Maqsadga muvofiq:

aholi punktlarining (shaharlar, posyolkalarning) suv ta'minoti tizimlari;

ishlab chiqarish suv ta'minoti tizimlari;

qishloq xo'jaligi suv ta'minoti tizimlari;

yong'inga qarshi suv ta'minoti tizimlari;

birlashtirilgan suv ta'minoti tizimlari (iqtisodiy va ishlab chiqarish, iqtisodiy va yong'inga qarshi va boshqalar).

Suv ta'minoti usuli bo'yicha:

tortishish kuchi (tortishish kuchi);

mexaniklashtirilgan suv ta'minoti bilan (nasoslar yordamida);

zonalar (tortishish kuchi bilan ba'zi joylarda, boshqa nasoslarda).

Amaldagi tabiiy manbalarning tabiati bo'yicha :

yer usti manbalaridan suv olish (daryo, ko'l va boshqalar);

yer osti manbalaridan suv olish (buloq, artezian va boshqalar),

aralash turdagi.

Suvdan foydalanish usuli bo'yicha:

to'g'ridan-to'g'ri oqim suv ta'minoti tizimlari (suvdan bir marta foydalanish bilan);

aylanma suv ta'minoti tizimlari;

suvni qayta ishlatadigan tizimlar.

Ichimlik suvi ta'minoti-aholini ichimlik suvi bilan ta'minlash bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar majmui. Ichimlik suvi ta'minoti mumkin bo'lgan suv ta'minoti manbalarini tanlash va baholashni o'z ichiga oladi (yer osti suvlari uchun – ularning zaxiralarini baholash), yotqizish joyini tanlash va suv olish inshootlarini qurish, suvni sanitariya baholash va ularni ifloslanishdan himoya qilish choralari. Aholi punktlarini ichimlik suvi bilan ta'minlashning zamonaviy tizimlari markazlashtirilgan: ularning har biri iste'molchilarning katta guruhini suv bilan ta'minlaydi.

Suv ta'minoti manbasini tanlashda, birinchi navbatda, ichimlik suviga bo'lgan talab va hududda yer usti yoki toza yer osti suvlari mavjudligi hisobga olinadi. Suv sifati va ifloslanishdan himoya qilish nuqtai nazaridan yer osti suvlariga ustunlik beriladi. Yer usti suv ta'minoti manbasini tanlashda gidrologiyalar, sharoitlar, minimal va o'rtacha suv sarfi, ularning mo'ljallangan suv olish mosligi, havzaning sanitariya xususiyatlari, sanoatning rivojlanishi, kelajakdagi suv olish hududida maishiy, sanoat va qishloq xo'jaligi ifloslanishi manbalarining mavjudligi va paydo bo'lishi ehtimoli baholanadi. Agar yer usti suv ta'minoti manbai ichimlik suvining tarkibi va xususiyatlari talablariga javob bermasa, sanitariya-epidemiologiya xizmati organlari bilan kelishilgan holda, suvni to'g'ri sifatini ta'minlaydigan (filtrlash, koagulyatsiya, dezinfektsiya va boshqalar) qo'shimcha, suvni qayta ishlash choralari rejalashtirish mumkin. Ichimlik suvi ta'minoti uchun yer osti suvlaridan foydalanganda: mintaqaviy geologik-gidrogeologik va geofizik ishlar asosida amalga oshiriladigan konlarni (uchastkalarni) va ularning tarkibidagi suv qatlamlarini qidirish; oldindan. hisoblangan gidrogeologik parametrlarni olish, oqilona suv olish sxemasini tanlash, o'rganilgan maydonda yer osti suvlarining ekspluatatsion zaxiralarini oldindan baholash, baholashni o'z ichiga olgan razvedka; suv olishni loyihalash va qurish uchun kapital qo'yilmalar ajratilishini ta'minlaydigan toifalar bo'yicha ishlab chiqilgan sxema va suv olish dizayniga nisbatan yer osti suvlarining ekspluatatsion zaxiralarini baholash bilan yakunlanadigan batafsil razvedka.

Kommunal-maishiy suv ta'minoti aholining suvni to'g'ridan-to'g'ri iste'mol qilishi (ichimlik uchun, oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarining bir qismi sifatida), suvdan maishiy maqsadlarda foydalanish (yuvish, tozalash, yuvish va boshqalar), kommunal-maishiy ehtiyojlar (kir yuvish, sartaroshxonalar va boshqalar), shahar transporti, qurilish tashkilotlari. Kommunal va maishiy suv ta'minoti nisbatan past qaytarib bo'lmaydigan iste'mol bilan tavsiflanadi. Shu sababli, kanalizatsiya tizimini kengroq joriy etish sug'orish yoki sanoat uchun qayta ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan (tegishli tozalashdan keyin) chiqindi suv miqdorini oshiradi. Bu uning iste'molchilari foydalanadigan suvni tejashga imkon beradi.

Qishloq aholi punktlarini suv bilan ta'minlashning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari (shaharlardagi kommunal-maishiy suv ta'minoti bilan taqqoslaganda) quyidagicha: katta soatlik notekislik, qaytarib bo'lmaydigan suv iste'molining katta hajmi (kanalizatsiya tizimidan kamroq foydalanish tufayli), o'ziga xos suv iste'moli kamroq. Kelajakda qishloq aholi punktlarini obodonlashtirish o'sishi bilan bu farqlar kamayadi.

Sanoat suv ta'minoti. Suv resurslarining mavjudligi va ulardan foydalanish imkoniyati sanoatni rivojlantirish va joylashtirishda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi.

Suv iste'moli hajmi sanoat korxonalarining tuzilishiga, texnologiya darajasiga, suvni tejash bo'yicha amalga oshiriladigan tadbirlarga bog'liq. Issiqlik energetikasi, qora va rangli metallurgiya, mashinasozlik, neft-kimyo va yog'ochni qayta ishlash sanoati eng ko'p suv talab qiladigan sohalardir. Sanoatning suv omborining o'zi - elektr energetikasi - toza suv iste'molining 68 foizini va qayta ishlangan suvning 51 foizini tashkil qiladi.

Uy-joy kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish tizimida suv ta'minoti va suv resurslaridan samarali foydalanish bugungi uy-joyga talab yuqori bo'lgan vaqtda e'tibor berilishi zarur bo'lgan omillardan biri hisoblanadi.

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SOCIO-PREVENTIVE SYSTEM OF ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

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Relevance of the topic. It gives a positive result if, through the study of the methodology of educational work, they are taught to independently, creatively solve the general issues of youth education on their own, are closely connected with the pedagogical practice of students' work activities and motivate them to self-education professionally. As a result, the study of this course is aimed at educating students: pedagogical treatment, culture of speech, pedagogical interaction, independent regulation of the mental state of the educator, drama and recessure of pedagogical influence, activation of independent educational activities of the Youth Union, Education of students in labor, vocational guidance, educational activities carried out outside the classroom, educational power of the family and - in the conditions of combining enthusiasm, general education schools, vocational schools, academic lyceums, there is no doubt that the curriculum will help students to educate themselves professionally.

Educational process educators-teachers in educational institutions of a specific profession, armed with the idea of national independence, must have the skills to bring it to the consciousness of every citizen. Only then will the Educator be able to educate.

The maturation of the human personality is very complex, and it is formed through a continuous long process. His upbringing is directly influenced by his parents, school, Neighborhood, Friends, public organizations, the environment, the media, art, literature, nature, etc. Therefore, upbringing is an indispensable attribute for All Society, for the formation of the future generation, every day, every time upbringing. In this regard, our President Sh.M.In Mirziyoyev's address to the Deputies of the Oliy Majlis, the fundamental turns taking place in the life of our people, the designation of 2020 as the year of "science enlightenment and development of the digital economy", determines the main content of the work to be done. Especially attention to science and enlightenment and education, education of spiritual thinking of students and young people is one of the important tasks facing our state, and this topic is one of the pressing problems in the state and is of great importance in the development of society. Our President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, having reorganized the organization "Youth Union" of the Republic of Uzbekistan and paying special attention to the establishment of Youth Education, said that "youth is our future". Through morality, education is taught to establish only a good attitude, to behave well in a perfect person, while forming spiritual thinking and high consciousness. Gradually, this condition becomes a habit (reflex) in it.

Conclusion. Therefore, it is necessary to educate our current youth spiritually perfect human qualities and form them in themselves. After all, as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "the upbringing of the younger generation has become extremely important and relevant in all times." In this regard, the education of high rules of etiquette explains the need to create conditions for the identification, development and stimulation of gifted children with spiritual thinking and consciousness.

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The History of Skobelov City or New Margilan

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Annation. *This article tells about the city of Skobelov, which was founded in the Ferghana Valley during the Soviet period. After some time, the city founded by a Russian general began to be called New Margilon, and in 1924 the current name became known as Fergana.*

Key words: *Russian Margelan, Skobelov, New Margelan, 1876 years, Fergana 1924 years, versts, Central Asia, Russia.*

Skobelov¹ or the Russian Margelan is called New Margelan, in contrast to the Old Kokand Margelan, which is as much as 12, if not 15 versts from here. If all the native cities of Central Asia resemble each other like two drops of water, then the Russian Central Asian cities, in turn, resemble one another to the point of indistinguishability. The city of Margelan is also among the bare steppe. From afar, it is a huge green forest, shaded by distant white pyramids of snowy mountains. There are no numbers of poplars here. There are whole regiments, whole armies of giant poplars, and one is slimmer, one is taller than the other. Our Central Asian military administration planted pyramidal poplar everywhere with special diligence. Askhabad, Samarkand, Tashkent, Kokan, Margelan are, first of all, endless dense alleys of huge poplars.

This tree of the south is really very comfortable. It does not obscure dwellings as much and does not take up as much space as spreading trees; it is neat and beautiful like no other; it grows so quickly and so unpretentiously as no other, and then it immediately makes the landscape of the area a southern landscape. But it seems to me that the military heart, accustomed to the alignment of the formation, to the construction in columns and ranks, also feels an involuntary predilection for this, so to speak, disciplined, compressed and selected tree, which is so easily amenable to a soldier's rank, almost ready to march along straight lines. long streets with their motionless elongated, like an army on review, green rows.

Margelan and other cities of the Ferghana region owe these plantations to the former talented governor of the region, General Abramov, who, together with Governor-General Kaufman, was animated by a special zeal for tree plantations of all kinds. The current governor, Korolkov, is also famous as a lover and expert in tree planting and, as I heard, he was even summoned to the Transcaspian region, to the Bairam-Ali sovereign estate, for meetings on the issue of planting gardens and forests, which he knew well; he proved his readiness for this matter while still being an assistant to the governor in Samarkand, where he so successfully made almost all of his many plantings.

In order to kill in the eyes of the natives the former dominant significance of Kokan and deprive him of dangerous historical prestige, the supremacy of the conquered khanate was transferred to the newly created Margelan, just as during the conquest of the Crimea by Catherine the old Bakhchisarai, the residence of the Gireys, was demoted to a provincial city and had to give its former superiority to the insignificant Ak-Mosque, granted to the provincial city and renamed Simferopol. For the same reason, the very name of the Kokand Khanate was destroyed, which was given its ancient Arabic name - Fergana, Fergana region.

But in addition to endless rows of poplars, in Margelan there are also endless rows of barracks, camps, and batteries. There are two artillery batteries here, of which one mountain, equestrian, especially

¹ <https://rus-turk.livejournal.com/tag/newmargilan>

needed in such areas, three line battalions of 4 companies each, one Cossack regiment - a whole impressive detachment capable of holding in reverence and fear the not quite resigned spirit of various wild-stone Kirghiz, the Kipchaks and other warlike tribes of Kokan, who so recently still fought with us with weapons in their hands. It is no wonder that now everything here is quiet and calm. And withdraw the army tomorrow, and everything will turn upside down. However, the local Sarts reach us even in a peaceful position. Looking more closely after the first fear that Skobelev's defeat inspired in them, they became convinced that the Russian government, not only in words, but in deeds, applies the same measure of law to all Russian subjects, that the Russian court is equally accessible, equally impartial to the Sart and the Kirghiz, as well as to Russian. And so they braved to the point of impudence, comprehended vividly any judicial slander, all sorts of clever geshefts with bills, contracts, pledges, began to take contracts and supplies for the army, learned to understand and speak in Russian everything that they need to say and understand, and, like the Jews in Byelorussia, clinging to each other in an inseparable kahal, they gradually took over all the trade and industry of the region, decisively recaptured all profitable business from the Russians. In Russian Margelan - most of their houses, shops, warehouses - theirs.

New Margelan differs from Tashkent and Samarkand only in greater abundance and greater density of greenery. Positively, this is one poplar garden. The boundless vistas of colossus trees open up in all directions, intersecting with each other. These solid green walls of infinite length, enormous height, are extremely original and beautiful. The merry unceasing murmur of ditches, flowing at their roots, even more transfers the imagination to the sphere of gardens and rural nature.

Governor Street is the main artery of the city. All the local institutions are there; there, by the way, is an excellent two-storey military assembly house with luxurious balconies and terraces in an oriental style, surrounded by flower beds and a garden. Inside there are many tastefully decorated rooms, a huge ballroom with elegant parquet, an elevated platform for concerts and performances, drawing rooms and dressing rooms full of fashionable furniture, reading rooms with all kinds of newspapers and magazines. It is hard to believe that you are in the recent kingdom of Khudoyar Khan, in the country of the Kipchaks and Kirghiz.

The new house of the regional governor is being built on the same street and is almost ready. The current residence of the governor, both in its modest appearance and in its position, is more like a summer house. It is entered through the alleys of Gubernatorskaya Street.

At the other end of this street is a city garden, very shady and cozy. Several wide rammed alleys, lined with tall trees, run along the street, others converge in rays in the central platform. There is a small wooden church, temporarily replacing a new cathedral under construction nearby.

There are two schools in Margelan, one for women, the other for four classes in the city with a six-year course. Both have their own spacious and comfortable houses.

There is also an Asian bazaar, in which there is absolutely nothing interesting and in which all trade, with the exception of some 2-3 Russian shops, is in the hands of local Sarts.

There are decent shops in the city, Zakho, Filatov, and others, but in general, trade here is quiet, although Margelan is the official capital of the Fergana region, the residence of its governor and the highest military authorities of the region.

In order to kill in the eyes of the natives the former dominant significance of Kokan and deprive him of dangerous historical prestige, the supremacy of the conquered khanate was transferred to the newly created Margelan, just as during the conquest of the Crimea by Catherine the old Bakhchisarai, the residence

of the Gireys, was demoted to a provincial city and had to give its former superiority to the insignificant Ak-Mosque, granted to the provincial city and renamed Simferopol. For the same reason, the very name of the Kokand Khanate was destroyed, which was given its ancient Arabic name - Fergana, Fergana region.

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EXTRA INFORMATIONS

The monument of Skobelov 1876-1910

Military unit building at New Margilan

№ 33 г. Скобелевъ. Почтово-телеграфная контора.

Post office of New Margilan(Skobelov)

A City Between Two Rivers

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70220301 - history (according to areas and types of activity)

Abstract. *This scientific article provides detailed information about the history of the village of Choja, Narinsky district of Namangan region, scientific observations from historical sources, changes in the village today.*

Key words: *Narin, Chooja, Karadarya, Kurban Buva, Istekhom, Khakkulabad, Great Silk Road.*

It is impossible to develop without studying history. For a long time we did not study history objectively. Whereas world science uses more than 100 methods to illuminate history. These include civilized, mental, logical, deductive, written and other methods.

History is a very responsible profession. Any attempt to subordinate history to the requirements of certain social and political interests contradicts the requirement of objectivity in relation to this science. Because the past is an objectivity that is not subject to the historian, but must be correctly understood and explained. At this point, the historian is like a tourist walking at the end of a caravan of past events. Events at the head of the caravan, in the middle, for him beyond the possibility of vision and completely objective reality. Revealing the conditions for the occurrence of events, their causes, the processes of their passage, consequences, influence on subsequent events, the laws that bind this system, requires the historian to have deep and detailed knowledge and skills in working with sources.

The historian, especially the source historian, is responsible for truthful description, analysis and interpretation of the distant and recent past on the basis of material, written and oral sources. At the same time, the historian must correctly assess the relation of the source he uses to reality. Because the conflict of interest is a natural phenomenon in the sources of different eras. To prevent such conflicts from arising, we have an urgent task to study history objectively and leave scientifically based ideas to future generations. With such a noble goal, we got acquainted with the history of the village of Chooja, Narin district of Namangan region. Namangan region, Narin is rich in villages with a unique history, Chooja is one of the largest and oldest villages in the district.

The village of Chooja is located in the western part of the Narin district. The water of the Narin River, which flows through the region, is distinguished by its transparency and healing properties from the waters of other rivers.

Chooja Village, like other regions, has an ancient and rich history. We can learn this information from books written by historians who studied the history of the village, information told by the elderly nobles of the village, the Kurbanata Jome mosque in the village and the hill of the same name located here.

The efforts of Salijon Norgoziev, who taught history at school for many years, deserve special attention in covering the history of the village. His book "The Winged Dargokhs in Oorikzor" contains valuable information about the history of the village. This book says: "There are 3 villages in the Ferghana Valley called Chooja. One of them belongs to the Uchtepa of the Narin district and is one of the oldest settlements. First of all, it is distinguished by a unique natural and geographical position. "Thanks to Narin and Karadarya, you can feel the pure mountain air here both in winter and in summer."

Village luminaries give some information about the foundation of the village and the settlement of the population here. According to their information, people from the Chinabad and Balykchee regions

moved to the village from the 18th century. At first they built small huts on the banks of the Black River and were engaged in agriculture, cattle breeding and fishing. Later, the name "Chooja" came from the same word "Choza".

Karadarya and Narindarya merge at the end of the village and form the Syrdarya. There is 1 hill in the village. The Shah and the poet Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur in their "Baburnoma" wrote about the lands between two rivers (Narin and Karadarya) (mainly Narin, Uchkurgan, Izboskan districts of the Andijan region, mountainous regions of Kyrgyzstan), called "between two waters". .

According to most information, the meaning of the word Chooja means "stretched village". The length of the village is about 14-15 km. is

There are 2 schools and 1 college in the village. The village has factories for the production of reinforced concrete, building materials, crushed stone (from the Narin River), etc. Farms grow cotton, grain, fruits and vegetables, and livestock products. The villagers also have extensive experience in the productive use of household plots.

In terms of geography, this place can be called a "peninsula". "Fortress" on the peninsula. To the northeast of the village called "Istekhkom" on the peninsula, near which the river Narin once flowed, is Kurban-Tepa. On the plain to the west of the hill there is also a cemetery named after grandmother Kurban. They say that the grandmother of the deceased was a saint, her grave is here. In ancient times, the name of the hill could be different or none at all. His age is also not clear. The length of this hill is 100 meters from east to west, 130-150 meters from north to south. The river washed away about 50 meters of soil. The height is about 25 meters. Later the river changed its course. At the foot of the hill, where the river once flowed, people are now engaged in agriculture.

People have lived by the water since ancient times. Because water is the source of life. The hill is well preserved, except for the northern part, washed out by the river. He is round. There is no doubt that the hill, which withstood natural factors (snow, rain, wind, earthquake, etc.), was larger than before. The hill was surveyed under the guidance of Kakhramon Askarov, associate professor of the socio-economic faculty of NamSU. Earth from there. cf. Found household items made of ceramics, copper and iron, fragments of tools dating back to the 4th-4th centuries AD. There are also finds from the Middle Ages (XII-XIII centuries).

The museum of the 44th school of the village contains a pear-shaped ceramic vessel (from which doctors poured liquid medicine) and copper coins found during excavations of a cemetery near the hill. Academician A. Askarov believes that the age of the hill is about 2500 years. Some scientists (Sattoralı Khaydarov) gave him 3,000 years, said the grateful teacher Salijon Norgoziev. Two and a half thousand years is a considerable date for the history of the country, of course. History has many unsolved mysteries. It can be said that this hill, which is called a fortress, was of great military and strategic importance, since it is located between two rivers.

When teacher Salijon taught at the school, he took his students to this hill in the subject of "Historical Geography" and taught a lesson in the style of an excursion. There is also a cave with an open mouth on the hill. There is another cave in the northeast of the hill, as a result of natural factors, the soil was washed away and the mouth of this cave was blocked. In the past, there were doors at the entrance to the caves through which one could get into the underground passages. The hill and its slopes are covered with yantok, wormwood and similar herbs. If the hill is old, then we can say that our holy religion belonged to the Zoroastrians even before Islam. On such hills the Zoroastrians worshiped the sun and fire. An example of this is the "Mug Castle", located in the upper reaches of the Narin River. Such abodes of fire worshipers can also be found in other regions (for example, in Chust). After our ancestors adopted the sacred religion of Islam, the Zoroastrian temples on the hills were demolished. Later they were used for defense and

communications purposes. The guards on the hill were the first to notice the enemy army and lit a torch (fire) to inform the population.

It is known from history that under the leadership of Genghis Khan, the Mongols invaded the territory of our country. The Mongols with great difficulty managed to conquer the city of Khojent, located in the upper reaches of the Syr Darya. This was facilitated by the natural and geographical position of the city and the courage of the mayor Temur Malik. In the chapter "Sergak Tepalar" of the novel "Temur Malik" by the famous writer Mirmukhsin, it is said that the general examined the guardhouse in Chordar. In the book we read the following lines: "... this artificial hill, towering five hundred gas (1 gas - 71 cm) above the roadway of Garovulkhan, as some say, was built in the time of Afrosiab. Ahraman (the god of evil in the Zoroastrian religion) stood like a giant at a distance of every ten yogs (1 yyog is equal to 6 km.) Temur Malik dismounted from his horse and with two or three servants approached the guardhouse..." It is close to the truth that Kurban-Buva Hill was also a guardhouse.

Grandpa Oormon, a blacksmith from Chooja, made 10 swords from the original steel. The villagers placed their swords on the belts of the 10 horsemen and followed them to the battlefield. These young men, even in distant lands, preserved the purity of the Uzbek name as their faith. Turgun moylov Makhmudov, the head of Chodzhi, the old men - Ismail buva Yoldashev, Mullahodzhamberdi Adashev, Kurbankhodzha Mansurkhodzhaev, Sabir kori Madumarov, Begmat buva Karabaev took 12 hectares of land from the collective farm for farming and grew cotton. The area where they worked is still called "Land of the Old Men".

Previously, when a boy was born in a family in Naryn, he was wrapped in a blanket or a dagger was placed next to the bed. This event was not in vain, of course. Raising your sons healthy, brave and worthy of serving the Motherland is the dream of all parents in our country. Marufjon Madaminov of Chooja graduated from the military academy. He was a military doctor, an expert in his field. Rank - Colonel. For many years he worked as the chief sanitary doctor in the Ministry of Defense. Author of several scientific and methodological books. He worked as the head of the 2nd department of the Ministry of Health.

The national liberation uprisings that took place in the Narin region during the time of the Russian Empire also deserve attention. In the village of Chooja of this region, a crowd led by Y. Masodikov, Kh. Khodzhiyev, Sh. Koraboev and Kh. Makhmudboev attacked the house of the eldest son of Kerimboy and elder T. Normatboev, armed with sticks, hoes and scythes. , those who did. However, the elder and the centurion managed to escape earlier. A military detachment fired at a group of people who had gathered and killed two people.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the village of Chooja, located on the territory of the Narin district, is distinguished by its ancient history, rich culture, various toponyms, brave, hardworking and simple people. This article also shows the natural and geographical position and ethnographic features of the village. In addition, comments on current changes in the village are shown.

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Металлографическое Исследование Порошковых Материалов

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***Аннотация.** Исследуемые пары трения работают при не достаточном поступление смазочного материала. Для решения этого недостатка при подборе нового материала был использован материал порошковой металлургии. Нами были выполнены исследовательские работы по подбору материала для подшипников скольжения, работающих при переменном нагрузке и недостаточном поступления смазочного масла. Для подбора рационального состава материала были изготовлены образцы. Исследуемые пары трения работают при не достаточном поступление смазочного материала. Для решения этого недостатка при подборе нового материала был использован материал порошковой металлургии. По результатам исследование для подшипников скольжения выбрана материал Ж Гр2 Мж2 S0,5, что по механическим и другим показателям соответствуют требованиям для подшипников скольжения работающих при переменных нагруждениях и недостаточном поступление смазки.*

***Ключевые слова:** трение, изделие, порошковый металл, образцы, подшипники скольжения, смазка, нагрузка, само-смазывания, твердость, микрошлиф, пористость.*

1. Введение:

При выполнении исследовательских работ по подбору материала для подшипников скольжения, работающих при переменном нагрузке и недостаточном поступления смазочного масла. Были изготовлены образцы для подбора рационального состава материала. Как уже ранее отмечалось, исследуемые пары трения работают при не достаточном поступление смазочного материала. Для решения этого недостатка при подборе нового материала было решено использовать материал из порошковой металлургии.

В материалах, изготовленных методом порошковой металлургии образуется поры, что обеспечивает эффект само-смазывания. В порах таких материалов во время работы скапливается масла, благодаря которому узел трения может работать без дополнительной смазки.

2. Целью данной работы - является повышение качественных показателей, повышение износостойкость, производительность. трущихся деталей и снизить себестоимость изготовления деталей машин.

3. Задача данной работы - исследовать взаимодействие рабочих органов сельхозмашин с почвой, изыскания путей снижения тягового сопротивления рабочих органов. В контакте деталей с массой движущихся твердых частиц происходит интенсивное разрушение поверхностного слоя, вследствие чего сроки службы нередко исчисляются десятками часов. К деталям, изнашивающимся при трении в массе твердых частиц, относятся многочисленная группа деталей рабочих органов и инструментов сельскохозяйственных, горных, строительных, дорожных, а также элементов оборудования различных машин.

4. Объектом научной работы – повышения показателей износостойких порошкового материала на основе железа.

5. Методика научного изыскания: Для исследования данной научной работы были применены методы металлографического анализа, гидростатическое взвешивание и методика сравнение-измерение всех полученных данных.

Порошковый материал – это совокупность частиц металла, сплава или металлоподобного соединения с размерами до 1 мм, находящихся во взаимном контакте и не связанных между собой. Порошковая металлургия - это изготовление металлических порошков и разных изделий из них. Применение исходного сырья в виде порошков является особенностью порошковой металлургии, как промышленного метода изготовления различного рода материалов, которые затем формуются в изделия нужных размеров и подвергаются спеканию, проводимой при температурах ниже температуры плавления основного компонента шихты.

6. Научная значимость работы: Порошковая металлургия применяется при массовом производстве как экономически выгодная замена механической обработки деталей. Технология позволяет получить высокоточные изделия и для достижения особых свойств и заданных характеристик, которые невозможно получить другим методом. Метод порошковой металлургии позволяет варьировать химическим составом материала в зависимости от назначения изделия. Для повышения износостойкости и обрабатываемости при резании и прочности были выбраны следующие легирующие элементы.

Создаваемый материал можно использовать в подшипниках скольжения работающих при переменном нагружении при недостаточном поступлении смазки.

Рисунок 1. Микроструктура образца из материала Ж Гр2 Д2 Мж2:

а – х 200; б – х 200 (травление 4% HNO_3); в – х500 (травление HNO_3).

Твердость спеченного материала определяли на приборе Бринелля (ТШ-2) при нагрузке 7 500 Н и диаметре шарика 5 мм. Пористость исследовали на нетравленных шлифах под бинокулярным микроскопом МБС—2. Размеры пор устанавливали на окулярной сетке при увеличении $\times 16$ на микроскопе МБС -2, $\times 100$ на микроскопе МБИ - 6. Шлифы подготавливали на шлифовально-полировальном станке. Готовые шлифы высушивали струей горячего воздуха на люминесцентном дефектоскопе ЛД - 4. Шлифы травили 4% - ным раствором азотной кислоты в этиловом спирте. Для исследования структуры использовали горизонтальный металлографический микроскоп МИМ-8М. Фотографирование микроструктуры производили на фотопластинке, а замер микро-твёрдости отдельных составляющих структуры - на микро-твёрдометре ПМГ– 3 при нагрузке 50 и

100 г (в зависимости от величины твердости). Минимум из десяти замеров выбирали среднеарифметическое значение твердости.

Состав композиции (Ж Гр₂ Д₂ Мж₂-) после спекания включал:

С - 1,02%, Мп - 0,35%, Р - 0,51%, Си - 2,0%, т.е. потери компонентов в процессе спекания незначительны. Ее твердость по Бринелю составляет - НВ 750 - 820 МПа, прочность на изгиб - 470 - 480 МПа, прочность на растяжение 11,5 - 11,7 МПа, коэффициент линейного расширения $10,0 - 10,2 \cdot 10^{-6} 1/^\circ\text{C}$.

Общий объем пористости, определенный методом гидростатического взвешивания, составлял 22–24%. Поры равномерно распределены по объему материала с некоторой тенденцией концентрации по границам зерен металлической матрицы (рис.1а). Размеры пор изменяются в пределах от 5 до 40 мкм, преимущественно 10-30 мкм (рис.1 б, в).

Микроструктура металлической основы представляет собой сочетание перлитных колоний с отдельными ферритными зёрнами и мелких изолированных белых включений, по-видимому, фосфидов марганца и железа (рис.1 б, в).

Промер микро-твердости на ПМТ - 3 отдельных составляющих структуры показал, что перлит имеет твердость - 3,0 - 3,4 ГПа, феррит - 1,6 - 1,9 ГПа, фосфиды - 4,2 - 4,6 ГПа.

Пористые спеченные материалы, содержащие в своем составе 1 - 3% препарата "мажеф", графита и серы. Анализируя результаты исследований состава, строения, и свойств выбранной композиции и составляя их с аналогичными данными композиции Ж Гр₂ Мж₂ S_{0,5} можно сказать, что введение 2% меди в состав композиции благотворно сказалось на комплексе структурных и механических характеристик: наблюдается диспергирование цементита в составе перлитной составляющей, повышение общей твердости на 100-200 МПа, прочности на изгиб (на 10-15%) и некоторое повышение прочности на растяжение (на 5-10%). Все это подтверждает результаты лабораторных испытаний на изнашивание и позволяет предположить повышение износостойкости и долговечности изделия при эксплуатации из предлагаемого материала.

Результаты. В зависимости от мест концентрации износа потеря культиватора работоспособности происходит по тем или иным причинам. При этом не исключено возможность, что при сравнительно медленном изнашивании культиватор может дойти до предельного состояния, например вследствие образования недопустимо большой затылочной фаски, быстрее, чем в условиях большой скорости изнашивания, но благоприятным распределением износа по поверхности культиватора. В результате эксплуатации, происходит износ рабочего слоя. Причем значение износа рабочих деталей работавших в засушливых регионах Узбекистана сравнительно остальными регионами значительно осуществима, так как почва Узбекистана имеет соледержащий, абразивный состав.

В связи с отмеченными целесообразно, сохранив понятие абразивной способности (абразивности) материалов, пользоваться при необходимости понятием об изнашивающей способности почв. При этом абразивность материалов (в том числе почвы) определяются по износостойкости материалов, а изнашивающая способность – по конструкционной износостойкости.

Заключение. Для исследования абразивности почвенная масса и износостойкости землеобрабатывающего инструмента – культиватора, испытания проводилось непосредственно в полевых условиях. В результате определена, что износ культиватора зависит в основном фракционного состава почвы, причем фракция частиц 0,1...0,25 мм (преимущественно кварц) оказывает наибольшее изнашивающее действие. Плотность почвы мало сказывается на величине износа культиватора.

Выводы. По результату исследования для подшипников скольжения выбран материал Ж Гр₂ Мж₂ S_{0,5}, что по механическим и другим показателям соответствует требованиям для подшипников скольжения работающих при переменном нагружении и недостаточном поступлении смазки.

Проведенные металлографические исследования показали, что легирование порошкового материала фосфидами марганца и железа создает условия увеличению почти 1,5...2,0 раза. За счет пористости пористо спеченных материалов создает условия эффекта само смазывания. Особенно при недостаточном поступлении смазки на поверхности трения. В порах накапливается оставшийся смазка и за счет температуры в результате трения из пор выступает смазка и создает смазочную пленку между трущимися поверхностями.

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Maqsud Shayxzodaning Hayoti Va Ijodi

Mamurova Feruza Islomovna, Abduvobov Akbarxon Abduvob o'g'li

Annotasiya. Maqsud Shayxzodaning o'zbek adabiyotiga, madaniyati ravnaqiga qo'shgan hissasi mustaqil O'zbekiston va uning hukumati tomonidan munosib e'zozlandi. Maqsud Shayxzoda Ozerbayjon va O'zbek xalq adabiyotining eng zabardast shoir va adiblaridan biri hisoblangan. U juda ham kuchli idrokli, zehni baland va harqanday yaxshi va yomon vaziyatlardan o'znotiqligi bilan chiqib keta olgan hozirjavob inson bo'lgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Atoqli shoir, mutafakkir, she'riyat, ijod, ilg'or, jurnallar, til, adabiyot, umr.

Atoqli shoir va mutafakkir Maqsud Shayxzoda 1908-yil Ozarbayjonning Ganja viloyatidagi Agdash (Oqtosh) shahrida tug'ildi. U yoshligidan she'riyatga erta qiziqdi. Ijod na'munalari ona vatanida ko'z ochdi, lekin ilg'or fikrlari tufayli otashin shoir mustabid tuzumning jabr-zulmidan chetda qolmadi. U birinchi bor 1928-yil qamoqqa olingan va sovetlarga qarshi tashviqotda ayblanib, 3-yilga O'zbekistonga surgun qilinadi. Shundan boshlab umrining oxirigacha O'zbekiston unga ikkinchi vatan bo'lib qoldi. Shoir Toshkentga ko'chib, turli gazeta va jurnallar tahriryatlarida ishlaydi. 1935-1938 yillarda Fanlar qo'mitasi qoshidagi til va adabiyot institutida dars beradi. Shu qatori 1938-yildan to umrining so'ngigacha qadar Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU da ilmiy faoliyat olib bordi. Uning ko'pdan ko'p tadqiqotlari o'zbek adabiyotshunosligi rivojiga katta hissa qo'shdi, ammo shoir mustabit tuzum zulmidan ikkinchi bor ham chetda qolmadi va O'zbekiston yozuvchilar uyushmasidan o'chirildi hamda 1952-yili 22-sentyabrda qamoqqa olindi va 25-yilga ozodlikdan mahrum qilindi. Broq shoir oradan ko'p o'tmay Stalin vafodidan so'ng ozodlikka chiqadi va ijodga qaytdi. Shayxzodaning Alisher Navoiy poetik mahoratini tadbiq etgan ishlari ilmiy chuqurligi, go'zalligi bilan ajralib turadi. Buyuk bobomiz Alisher Navoiyni "G'azal mulkining sultoni" deb ilk bor qo'llagan shoir bu Maqsud SHayxzodadir.

Maqsud Shayxzodaning o'zbek adabiyotiga, madaniyati ravnaqiga qo'shgan hissasi mustaqil O'zbekiston va uning hukumati tomonidan munosib e'zozlandi. Qator maktab va ko'chalarga uning nomi berildi. Maqsud Shayxzoda bundan tashqari 2001-yilda «Buyuk xizmatlari uchun» ordeni bilan taqdirlandi. XX asr o'zbek she'riyati rivojida Shayxzodaning o'rni katta. Rang barang shakl va mazmun, ko'tarinki ruh, bilan sug'orilgan she'rlaridagi quyma obrazlar, ramziylik, so'zlardagi jarangdorlik, musiqiy salobat shoir asarlariga ajib badiiy yaxlitlik baxsh etadi, o'quvchi qalbida shularga monand hissiyotlar to'lqinini uyg'otadi. Shoir hech qachon, kitobiy, sun'iy muammolarni izlamadi. Shoir uyg'otgan yog'dular kitobxon qalbi, shuuriga ham ko'chib o'tadi. Uning she'rlarida chiroyli badiiy obrazlar mo'ldir. Shayxzoda she'rlari «Chorak asr davomida», «Dunyo boqiy», «Xiyobon» singari o'nlab to'plamlarda bosilib chiqdi. Bu she'rlar yuksak insoniy orzular bilan yashayotgan zamondosh xayollari, muhabbati, dardlari, umidlari bilan kuylandi. To'g'ri, qirq yil davom etgan ijodida Shayxzoda Lenin, Kreml, sho'rolar, irqa va irqaviylarni ham kuyladi. Lekin bu zamon va tuzumning shoir taqdiri va ijodidagi muhridir. Shayxzoda shoirning asosiy vazifasi «inson ruhini tarbiyalash, odamda yaxshilik unsurlarini ko'paytirish, xalqqa go'zallik va nafosat tuyg'usini yanada baland darajada ko'tarishda» deb bilgan edi. Uning «Toshkentnoma» nomli lirik falsafiy dostoniga munosabatda ham shu nuqtayi nazardan kelib chiqish to'g'ri bo'ladi. Shoining bu fikrlari o'zining aksar she'rlari uchun ham ochqich bo'la oladi. Maqsud Shayxzoda fikricha va iqroriga, hayotdagi buyuk ne'matlardan biri she'riyat, tengsiz go'zalliklardan biri she'rdir. Shayxzoda «She'r chin go'zallik singlisi ekan» nomli she'rida butun ijodi bo'ylab porlagan – she'riyatning insonga cheksiz go'zalliklar, ruhiy tovlanish va evrilishlar in'om etguvchi mohiyatini kuylaydi, uning yangi-yangi qirralarini ochishga intiladi deb hisoblagan edi. Hamda Maqsud Shayxzoda shoirlik bilan bir qatorda o'zbek adabiyotini «Jaloliddin Manguberdi», «Mirzo Ulug'bek» nomli tarixiy dramalari bilan boyitadi. "Jaloliddin Manguberdi" darmmasida Shayxzoda Vatan erki, mustaqilligi uchun fidoyilarcha kurash olib brogan mana shu jasur sarkarda qiyofasini bdiiy

gavdalantirdi. “Mirzo Ulug’bek” tragediyasida esa buyuk o’zbek astronomi va ma’rifatparvar podshosi obrazini o’zbek adiblaridan birinchi bo’lib yaratdi. Yozuvchining bunday serqirra va sermahsul ijodlari bilan birqatorda judoliklarni ham boshdan kechirdi. 1966-yilda yaqin do’sti, buyuk shoir G’afur G’ulom va munosabatlari yaqinbo’lgan davlat arbobi Usmon Yusupov vafot etdi. Bu yo’qotishlar shoir yuragida kuchli aks sado berdi: “G’afurga xat” va “Ayriliq” (Usmon Yusupov xotirasiga) nomli she’rlar yozdi. Insonni qadrlash, har bir qalbning istag nafsiga xolis munosabat muammolarni badiiy yoritish Shayxzoda she’riyatining yetakchi yo’nalishi bo’lgan edi.

Shayxzoda adabiy bilim doirasining kengayishi, ijodining mumtoz jahon yozuvchilari badiiy tajribasi bilan boyishida tarjima muxim rol o’ynadi. U Sh. Rustavelining „Yo’lbars terisini yopingan paxlavon“ (hamkorlikda) eposi, U. Shekspirning sonetlari, A. S. Pushkinning she’rlari, „Mis chavandoz“ dostoni, „Motsart va Salyeri“ tragediyasi, M. Yu. Lermontovning she’rlari va „Kavkaz asiri“ dostonini, shuningdek, Nizomiy, Fuzuliy, Mirza Fatali Oxundov, Ezop, Esxil, Gyote, Bayron, Mayakovskiy, Nozim Hikmat va boshqa yozuvchilarning ayrim asarlarini o’zbek tiliga katta mahorat bilan tarjima qildi.

Maqsud Shayxzoda Ozerbayjon va O’zbek xalq adabiyotining eng zabardast shoir va adiblaridan biri hisoblangan. U juda ham kuchli idrokli, zehni baland va harqanday yaxshi va yomon vaziyatlardan o’znotiqligi bilan chiqib keta olgan hozirjavob inson bo’lgan. Shoirni hayot yo’li oson davrga to’gri kelmaganligiga qaramasdan hech ham ijodda izlanishdan to’xtamadi. Hattoki o’zi tug’ulib o’sgan diyoridan mustabit tuzimning noxaq ayblovlariga ko’ra bashqabir yurtga surgun qilinishiga qaramay, u o’z tanlagan yo’lida davim etdi. Uning ijodi shuqadar qiziqki u faqat bir yo’nalishda emas balki turli xil yo’nalishlarda juda ham qiziq faoliyat olib borgan va o’z ortidan o’chmas iz qoldirgan.

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Facilities and Devices of the Yale Farm

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Annation. *Is main function is to evenly distribute the force from the sleepers to the main platform of the Earth's polotnos, to ensure the resistance of the sleepers to the effects of vertical and horizontal forces, to ensure the elasticity of the underground floor, as well as to adjust the rail-sleeper grid in profile and avoid overhead waters from it.*

Key words: *railway, element, soil, artificial structure, plot, train, speed, safe, movement, supply.*

All elements of the railway (soil lifting, high structures and artificial structures) in terms of strength, stability and condition should ensure safe and even movement of trains on this site at the specified speed. Plan and profile of the road. The rail must correspond to the radius of the curves, the correct and curved circuit, the approved road plan and profile in relation to the slope ties.

The station, Jack and crossing points should usually be located on a horizontal platform: in some cases, they are allowed to be located on slopes that do not exceed 0.0015, in difficult conditions, usually on slopes that do not exceed 0.0025. In order to prevent spontaneous departure of wagons to other tracks in the required cases, systems of the protection berk road, the protection Arrow, The lowering heads or the arrow devices should be envisaged. Stations, jacks, crossing points, as well as some parks and towing paths should be located on the right lots. Under difficult conditions, their location in a radius curve of not less than 1500 m is allowed. Under extremely difficult conditions, it is allowed to reduce the radius of curvature up to 600 m, in Mountain conditions up to 500 m.

The plan and profile of the main and Station roads, as well as the roads belonging to the railway, must undergo periodic equipment inspection.

The longitudinal profiles of the sorting Hills, pull-out track and hill side tracks at the sorting, site and freight stations are checked at least once every three years, and the profile at the rest of the station tracks at least once every 10 years. The longitudinal profile of the main roads is checked during the period of the Indigenous and middle repair of the roads.

Soil lift (ground floor), high road structure and artificial structures

Soil hoist (ground floor)

The ground floor is a complex of grunt spill structures resulting from the processing of the upper part of the Earth, designed to put the rail'1 superstructure, to ensure the strength of the road, to protect it from the effects of the atmosphere and groundwater.

The upper width of the soil riser should correspond to the upper structure of the path on the right plots. The width of the soil riser before their reconstruction on existing lines should not be less than 5.5 m on one – way lines, 9.6 m on two – way lines; and on Rocky and sizot – water land, on one-way lines-no less than 5.0 m, on two-way lines-no less than 9.1 m. The minimum width of the soil lifting edge should be 0.4 m on each side of the road.

In curved plots with a radius of less than 2000 m, the soil lift is expanded according to the established norms.

High road structure. To the upper structures of the road, the ballast part of the road, sleepers, rails, pads, pads, rails are introduced.

Ballast layer: its main function is to evenly distribute the force from the sleepers to the main platform of the Earth's polotnos, to ensure the resistance of the sleepers to the effects of vertical and horizontal forces, to ensure the elasticity of the track floor, as well as to adjust the rail-sleeper grid in profile and avoid overhead waters from it.

Sleepers

The sleepers serve as a base under the rail, receiving tension from the rail and transferring it to the ballast layer, installing rails on the sleepers and ensuring the regular width of the track. In addition to sleepers, the underground base of Rcls also includes sleeper-bruses of bridges and arrow conductors, in the form of a half-sleeper, a monolithic slab and a frame. Sleepers should be strong, elastic, inexpensive and have sufficient resistance to electric currents. Wood, reinforced concrete and metal are used as the Traverse material.

The length of wooden sleepers is 2.75 m and the weight will be on average 70-80 kg, the service life is 15-18 years. Reinforced concrete sleepers are 2.70 m long and weigh an average of 265 kg, the BF-70 type has an average service life of 320 kg, an average of 50-years.

Epyura sleeper

The order of longitudinal placement of sleepers under the rail is called its "ePure". In reinforced concrete sleepers, sleepers can be laid in 3 epures and 1,600, 1,840 and 2,000 sleepers can be laid in a length of 1 km. In the BF-70 type, 1,680 and 1,720 sleepers can be laid in a length of 1 km

Rails

The rail is designed to direct the wheels of the action structure, taking the load from it and giving it to the sleepers. In addition, in autobiographical plots, rails are used as conductors of signal spills, and in electric traction, as conductors of return spills.

The dimensions of the approximation of buildings have the following designations:

C — for structures and devices placed near public railway tracks with speeds up to 200 km/h inclusive. and external access roads of general and non-public use from the junction station to the territories of enterprises.

Jv — for structures and devices placed near non-public railway tracks located on and between the territories of factories, workshops, depots, river and sea ports, mines, freight yards, bases, warehouses, quarries, forest and peat developments, power plants and other industrial and transport enterprises, as well as for industrial railway stations, loading and unloading and other special tracks at public railway stations.

The dimension of the rolling stock is the maximum transverse outline perpendicular to the axis of the track, in which, without going outside, the railway rolling stock should be placed on a straight horizontal track both empty and loaded. The size of the rolling stock differs in different countries and may differ on different lines within the same country.

T is a static dimension for rolling stock allowed to be put into circulation on public and non-public railway tracks with a gauge of 1520 mm on electrified railways and other sections, structures and devices on which meet the requirements of the dimensions of the approach of buildings C and Sp;

Tc is a static dimension for tanks, dump trucks and other rolling stock allowed for circulation on public and non-public railway tracks, structures and devices on which are brought to the requirements of the control outline;

1-T is a static dimension for railway rolling stock allowed for circulation on all public and non-public railway tracks, external and internal tracks of industrial and transport enterprises of railways.

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Boshlang'ich Sinf Ona Tili Va O'qish Savodxonligi Darslari Samaradorligini Ta'minlovchi Integratsion Yondashuv Metodikasi

Adizova Nodira Baxtiyorovna

BUXDUPI dotsenti

Anotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada 2020-2021-o'quv yilida joriy etilgan ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi darsligi tahlili va fanlararo integratsiya qilish haqida yoritilgan. Ona tili darslari orqali bir necha fanlarni integratsiyalash orqali o'quvchilarni kasbga yo'naltirish metod va usullari haqida ma'lumot keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: milliy o'quv dasturi, ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi, integratsiya, inkorporatsion yondashuv, kasbga yo'naltirish, siperalsimon darsliklar.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining «Ta'lim-tarbiya tizimini yanada takomillashtirishga oid qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida» 2020 yil 6 noyabrdagi PQ-4884-son qarori ijrosini ta'minlash, shuningdek, umumiy o'rta ta'lim tizimida fanlarni o'qitish metodikalari, uzluksiz metodik xizmat ko'rsatish tartibi va o'qituvchilarning kasbiy mahoratini oshirish, ta'lim jarayoniga zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalarini joriy etish maqsadida, umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida ona-tili fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy inter faol metodlardan foydalangan holda o'quv jarayonlarini salohiyatini oshirish hamda boshqa fanlararo integratsiyalashuvini ta'minlagan holda o'quvchi yoshlarni bilim salohiyatini yanada oshishiga muxim zamin yaratadi.

2021-2022-o'quv yilida yangi milliy o'quv dasturi asosida yaratilgan birinchi va ikkinchi sinf ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi darsligi yaratildi. Bu darslik jahon ta'lim tizimi talablariga mos ravishda tuzildi. Milliy o'quv dasturi asosida yaratilgan darsliklar siperalsimon tuzilgan bo'lib, o'quvchi bilimni yanada oshiradi va mustahkamlaydi. Bu darsliklar mualliflari Iroda Azimova, Klaraxon Mavlonova, Sa'dullo Quronov, Shokir Tursun.Xalqaro ekspert Lannuzzi Susan. Bu darsliklar ikki qismdan iborat. Darslik o'quvchi yoshiga mos ravishda chiroyli rasmlar, audiomatnlar bilan boyitilgan. Bu darsliklar orqali o'quvchilarning nutqiy kompetensiyalari ya'ni og'zaki nutq, yozma nutq, anglash(o'qish va tushinish, tinglab tushinish) va lingvistik kanpetensiyalari shakllantiriladi. O'quvchini xalqaro baholash – o'qish savodxonligini baholovchi PIRLS hamda PISA dasturlariga tayyorlash maqsadida o'qib tushinish malakalarini shakllantirishga qaratilgan mashq va topshiriqlar darslik mazmuniga singdirilgan.

Darslikda o'quvchining mantiqiy, tanqidiy, ijodiy fikrlashi, o'qib tushinish va tinglab tushinishga yo'naltirilgan juda ko'p topshiriqlar berilgan. O'qish savodxonligi mukammal bo'lgan o'quvchi boshqa fanlarda o'rganayotgan

matnlarni o'qish orqali mantiqiy, tanqidiy, ijodiy fikrlaydi, olgan bilimlarini hayotda qo'llay olish iqtidori rivojlantiriladi. Shuningdek, o'quvchining mantiqiy fikrlashini va amaliy ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga yo'naltirilgan xalqaro baholash dasturi (PISA, PIRLS) talablariga mos keladigan matnlar bilan ishlashga mo'ljallangan amaliy topshiriqlarni matnlarning mazmuniga moslashtirish o'qituvchi oldidagi asosiy vazifalardan biri. Bunda matnni tushinish, tahliliy, tanqidiy fikrlash va munosabat bildirish malakalarini shakllantirish ko'zda tutiladi.

Ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi darsligi ijtimoiy va aniq fanlar bilan integratsiyalashgan holda o'qitiladi. O'quvchilar matndan tashqari jadval, diagrammalardagi topshiriqlarga mantiqiy va ijodiy yondashadi. Ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi matematika, astranomiya. Tarix, biologiya, texnologiya, rasm, tabiiy fanlar va geografiya fanlari bilan integratsiyalashgan. Ona tili va o'qish savodxonligini musiqa va tasviriy

san'at darslarini o'zaro bog'lab tashkil etish bolalarda san'at asarlarini to'g'ri tushunish va qadrlash qobiliyatlarini o'stiradi, o'quvchining ma'naviy dunyoqarashini o'stirishga xizmat qiladi.

O'qituvchilar integratsiyadan ko'pincha butun dars bosqichlarida emas, balki uning biron bosqichida foydalanishadi. Ya'ni darsning muayyan qismigina integratsiyalashadi. Shu usul bilan tabiatshunoslik xususiyatiga ega axborotlar lug'at boyligi bilan keng ishlashda imkon yaratadi. U yoki bu so'zni tilshunos nuqtayi nazari bilan ham, tabiatshunos nuqtayi nazari bilan ham talqin etish mumkin. Bu ona tili va tabiatshunoslik fanlari integratsiyasiga zamin yaratadi.

Tabiiy fanlar va geografiya fani bilan integratsiyalashganligini 2-sinf ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi darsligining 1-qismida yaqqol ko'rishimiz mumkin.3-bo'lim "Tabiat ne'matlari" bo'limidagi qishda uxlaydigan hayvonlar, yer ostida nima bor?, sayohatchi qushlar mavzulari aynan tabiiy fanlar va geografiya bilan bog'liq. Yer ostidagi qazilma boyliklari haqidagi matn tushintiriladi. ,matn tarkibidagi narsa nomlarini bildiruvchi so'zlarni ularga so'roq berish orqali aniqlanadi. Matnni ifodali va ravon o'qish malakasini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan topshiriqlar bajariladi. Tabiiy boyliklardan oqilona foydalanish va ularni tejash haqida tushintiriladi.

Bu mavzular orqali o'quvchilar geografik bilimlarini oshiradilar. "Yer ostida nima bor" mavzusini tushintirayotganda o'qituvchi yer osti boyliklarini qazuvchi kishilar ya'ni geologlar haqida ham ma'lumot beradi. Geologlar yer osti boyliklarini qidirib topuvchi kasb egalaridir. Geolog kasbi juda mashaqqatli shu bilan birga juda sharaflidir. O'quvchilarni bu mavzu orqali geolog kasbiga qiziqish uyg'otamiz.Bu mavzudan so'ng "Geolog" so'zi she'ri keltirilgan. Bu she'r orqali geolog kasbi haqidagi bilimlari mustahkamlanadi. Bir vaqtning o'zida bir mavzu orqali bir necha fanlarni integratsiyalash orqali o'quvchilarni kasbga yo'naltiramiz. Bu ona tili darslarida inkorporatsion yondashuv deb ataladi. O'quvchilar olgan bilimlarini haqiqiy hayotda qo'llay oladilar. Bu darsliklar aynan shunga yo'naltirilgan.

Ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi darsligini yana biologiya fani bilan integratsiyalashgan. 2-sinf darsligining 1-qismi 4-bo'lim "Sog' tanda sog'lom aql " bo'limi aynan biologiya fani bilan integratsiyalashgan. Bu bo'limda bakteriya va mikroblar, foydali nonushta, tanamizni o'rganamiz mavzulari o'rin olgan. Bu bo'limga 28 soat ajratilgan. O'quvchilar 28 soat davomida ona tiliga doir bilimlar bilan birgalikda biologiyaga doir bilimlarni egallashadi. Aynan tana a'zolari haqidagi mavzular 2-sinf Tabiiy fanlarda ham bor. Ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi va tabiiy fanlardagi bu mavzular o'quvchilarga bir vaqtda siperalsimon tarzda o'rgatiladi. Darsliklarning bunday tuzilganligi o'quvchilarning bilimini yanada mustahkamlaydi. Bakteriya va mikroblar mavzusini o'tish jarayonida matn bilan tanishtiriladi, undagi ayrim so'zlar talafuziga e'tibor qaratiladi. So'zlar tarkibidagi A-O va O-O' unlisi ishtirok etgan so'zlar talafuzi va imlosiga e'tibor qaratiladi,Ushbu harflar qatnashgan so'zlarni bo'g'inlarga ko'chirich mashqlari o'tkaziladi. Matn tarkibida kelgan ilmiy atamalar ma'nosi tushintiriladi, lug'at bilan ishlash ham o'rgatiladi.Bu ona tiliga doir o'rganishi kerak bo'lgan bilimlardir.Biologiyaga doir bilimlar ham shu darslar davomida o'quvchilarga o'rgatib boriladi. Bakteriya va mikroblar mavzusi ilmiy mant hisoblanadi. Bakteriyalar tana qismlarining turli qismlarida joylashishi, ular foydali va zararli bo'lishi, biotin, K vitamini haqidagi biologiyaga oid bilimlar ham o'rgatiladi.

Sog'lom turmush tarzi, o'zlarining tana tuzilishlari haqidagi bilimlarga ega bo'ladilar. Darslar davomida egallagan bilimlarini o'zlarining hayotlarida o'sha vaqtning o'zidayoq qo'llay boshlaydilar. Chunki bu darslik olgan bilimlarini hayotda qo'llay olishlariga yo'naltirilgan. Bu darslarni o'tish jarayonida albatta ko'rgazmali vositalardan va AKT vositalaridan foydalanish juda muhim. Bu dars samaradorligini yanada oshiradi.

Milliy o'quv dasturi asosida yaratilgan barcha darsliklar o'quvchini hayotga tayyorlash va olgan bilimlarini o'z kundalik hayotlarida qo'llay olishlari bilan ajralib turadi.

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Interdisciplinary Integration as a Factor of Complete Worldwide

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Annation. *In this article, from the philosophical point of view of the integration of sciences, the integrative issues of things and phenomena in nature are covered. In particular, it helps to have the correct understanding due to integrative ideas about man and nature, the structure of the Coyote, the Earth and the Sun, the moon and the stars.*

Key words: *integration and differentiation of sciences, integration of natural sciences, natural-scientific outlook, integration of chemistry and biology.*

Intelligent man (Homo sapiens) has been through many trades since his emergence as a biological species. Due to his weakness in the face of the forces and phenomena of nature, man tried to describe it differently and to the extent of his own mind. Explaining the structure of the universe in the dimensions of the Earth, Sun, Moon and stars itself has led to the creation of many erroneous thoughts, ideas, opinions, hypotheses and theories.

The dialectics of life and death, health and disease, the organism and its surrounding environment, the relative extents and prospects of the products of the natural and artificial and synthetic material worlds, and the interrelationship of biomaterial and bioenergetic boundaries have also generated much debate. .

Many global geological, tectonic, meteorological and other phenomena in the atmosphere, lithosphere and hydrosphere caused different interpretations of past processes on the planet Earth. Even the very nature and causes of such phenomena as reproduction, sex, and the birth of a boy or a girl were interpreted differently and unnaturally. The complexities of the biosphere, where living units exist, have presented new puzzles to humanity.

The sciences that have already appeared and managed to "find" the objects and subjects of their research, that is, concrete and worldly knowledge, shed light on many controversial issues. Socio-humanities revealed the laws of nature and society relations. Advances in technique and technology, industry and economy have led to the creation of certain and specific views of the world.

The integration of natural sciences such as physics, chemistry, biology, geography, geology effectively serves to create a general scientific picture of the world. However, separate fields of knowledge - natural, technical, social and humanitarian sciences - cannot form a complete picture of nature, society and man, their socio-natural phenomenon, standing apart from each other.

Philosophical outlook is clarified with the help of natural-scientific view of the world. For this, the most important achievements of the natural sciences should be integrated. Just one example: Benjamin Franklin (United States of America) invented the lightning rod and saved mankind from the scourge of the "tongue monster".

If we consider that 15,000 lightning strikes the Earth's surface every second and how many people die prematurely because of it, the value of this invention increases even more. Another unique American talent, Thomas Alva Edison, surprised the intellectuals of the world by making 4093 inventions and discoveries during his lifetime.

Since it is the highest form of science, it means that objective reality is eternally elevated to the level of ideality. It is known that sciences have already been divided into large groups that study living nature, inanimate nature, and social spheres according to their study objects and research subjects. However, it is a natural process for various sciences that study the material and spiritual world to interact.

At the same time, due to the narrowing of the scope of research, fine specialization in each of these disciplines inevitably occurs. Two objective trends in the development of sciences - differentiation (branching) and integration (combination) - as a result, have an incomparable place in the creation of a holistic, general scientific picture of the universe.

Many things and phenomena, such as the close relationship between the organism and the environment, the relationship of celestial bodies, the way life on Earth depends on cosmic factors, the connection of changes in the life of human society to geological and astrophysical phenomena, the connection of historical events on Earth with the activity of the Sun, are known due to the successful participation of the development of science in learning about the universe. it happened.

Such global scientific-creative, social-educational and anthro-noospheric processes continue unabated. Using philosophy and natural sciences involved in solving the most important and general issues and problems in the "world-man" relationship with its worldview, methodological, axiological, epistemological, ontological, praxeological, humanistic, educational, communicative, critical, integrative, prognostic and sociological functions. will be able to comment accurately and fully, objectively and in the mirror of reality

For example, chemical information should be widely reflected in the content of biology education. The chemical composition of the earth, the biogeochemical significance of soil and air, and the chemical relationships between living and non-living nature have become clear to mankind thanks to the integration of these two sciences. Now there is a need to cover these issues in the content of school subjects. However, there are some obstacles to solving this pedagogical problem: 1. Shallowness, dispersion and unsystematic nature of chemical materials in the content of biological educational literature. 2. Inadequate chemical literacy of biology teachers. 3. Inadequate organization of scientific and methodical support. 4. The establishment of intersubject communication has not been studied as a separate research object and subject. 5. Non-organization of integrative courses, etc.

At the same time when old and secular sciences such as biology and chemistry are intensively intermingled, there was a need to eliminate such defects in the education system. In this, it is necessary to call for help the information of such sciences as chemistry, physics, biology, geology, geochemistry, geodesy, geometry, biogeochemistry, cosmochemistry, biogeography, anthropology, ecology.

It's no secret that Uzbekistan, a country of great opportunities, has great chemistry. It is a didactic requirement that the achievements of the chemical and processing industry become a structural component of the biology course. In fulfilling such a task, it is appropriate to use President I.A. Karimov's work "Uzbekistan-towards a great future" as a guide.

The correct answer to such questions as the chemical composition of organisms, the continuous exchange of matter and energy with the organism and its surrounding environment, growth and development, and reproduction can only be found due to the cooperation of biology and chemistry.

Due to the didactic cooperation of the subjects of chemistry and biology, students' knowledge of these subjects will be strengthened, and their attitude to material and spiritual values will certainly change in a positive direction. In addition, the principles of patriotic education of chemistry and biology education are also fulfilled.

Issues such as lack of knowledge about the material and social world, the correctness and completeness of the general scientific picture of the world, and the finding of scientific and educational answers to the existing problems will be positively resolved through the strengthening of interdisciplinary communication, of course.

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Как Создать Управляемый Бизнес После Пандемии: Проблемы, Решения

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Аннотация. Как управлять экономикой малого бизнеса и предпринимательства в условиях пандемии, что предпринимается экономистами разных стран, какие имеются пути, что необходимо предпринять для решения насущных задач по выходу из состоявшейся ситуации и не впасть в кризис. Есть ли пути выхода из сложившейся ситуации. Что бы минимизировать риски в этих условиях автор предлагает применение цифровой экономики, моделировать производственный процесс как экономическую модель.

Ключевые слова: Пандемии, стран.

Производственные технопарки – новые формы создания производственных площадей для малого бизнеса при использовании пустующих производственных площадей, имеющих действующую производственную инфраструктуру;

Система экспертной оценки – система информационных обеспечений при оценке показателей производственных проектов;

Цифровизация экономики – широкое использование IT технологий при разработке бизнес-плана;

Экономическая модель – табличное описание экономических процессов в целях анализа производства;

Актуальность исследуемой темы

Пандемия, начавшаяся в 2020 году, сделала экономику всех стран весьма своеобразной. В том числе и сделала определенные коррективы и в экономику Узбекистан. В основном пострадали предприниматели малого и среднего бизнеса. В этих условиях быстро поправили свои дела те предприятия, которые быстро сумели приспособиться к противодействию внешних факторов. Какие проблемы возникли в этих условиях, как их решить?

Одним из направлений, как в теоретическом, так и в практическом плане является применение экономика математических методов.

Успешное применение математики в экономике стимулировало математизацию и других общественных и естественных наук. Разработку первого баланса народного хозяйства СССР за 1923-1924 гг., на основе которого была построена широко известная ныне модель В. В. Леонтьева. Л. В. Канторовичем впервые был применен метод линейного программирования экономических систем. Его теория широко нашла применение в решении транспортных задач. Методы математического моделирования социально-экономических процессов применяются преимущественно в научных разработках, а рекомендации ученых зачастую в практике игнорируются.

Примечательно то, что вопросам цифровизации малого бизнеса и предпринимательства внимания никто не уделяет. Мы решили восполнить этот пробел, что и явилось создание ПО «Экономическая модель разработки бизнес-плана для стартапов».

В настоящее время в Узбекистане цифровизация экономики является общегосударственной проблемой. В этой связи разработка нашей ПО «Экономическая модель разработки бизнес-плана для стартапов» является своевременным ответом для реализации Постановлений Президента РУз.[3,4]

Представители малого бизнеса и предпринимательства затрудняются самостоятельно выжить в условиях пандемии и сплошного хаоса. Чтобы организовать непрерывное производство, работать эффективно, и приспособливаться к форс-мажорным ситуациям и выйти из таких ситуаций без участия государственных органов было бы не просто. Роль государственных органов Узбекистана послужила во многом в решении сложных вопросов в период пандемии.

В период пандемии 2020 года, в первую очередь, больше всего пострадали представители малого бизнеса и предпринимательства. Но, несмотря на снижение выпуска продукции в период карантинных мероприятий, с выходом из карантина, почти все предприниматели, восстановили свои позиции. Об этом свидетельствуют статданные Узбекистана, из которого видно, что в 2020 году по сравнению с 2019 годом, годом до пандемии рост производства вырос на 23,6%, а в 2021 году, рост к предыдущему составил 118,15%. Это говорит о том, что руководством республики в Узбекистане большое внимание уделяет развитию предпринимательства и малого бизнеса.

Во всех городских районах крупных городов республики Узбекистан, на базе бездействующих площадей крупных предприятий были созданы **производственные технопарки**. На их территориях представителям малого бизнеса предоставляли производственные площадки со всей производственной инфраструктурой. На этих площадках предприниматели начали размещать свое оборудование, чтобы наладить собственное производство. При этом малому бизнесу предоставили все условия для их развития. Так же, специальным постановлением Правительства¹, стимулируется повышение производства экспортной продукции малыми предприятиями и предпринимателями. Согласно указанного постановления созданы все условия производства экспортной продукции, ее оформление и отправка по логистической системе, со своими службами, для беспрепятственного экспортирования внешним потребителям.

Динамика изменения доли ВВП малого производства и предпринимательства в экономике Узбекистана представлена в следующей таблице:

Доля малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства (МБЧП)

Показатели	2000	2005	2010	2015	2016	2017	2019	2020	2021
ВВП	31,0	38,2	60,8	64,6	66,8	65,3	56,0	55,7	54,9
Промышленность	12,9	10,0	26,6	40,6	45,3	41,2	25,8	27,9	27,0
Строительство	38,4	50,9	52,5	66,7	66,9	64,8	75,8	72,5	72,4
Занятость	49,7	64,8	74,3	77,9	78,2	78,0	76,2	74,5	-
Экспорт	10,2	6,0	13,7	27,0	26,0	22,0	27,0	20,5	22,3 ²
Импорт	22,8	33,7	35,8	44,5	46,8	53,6	61,6	51,7	48,7

Данные за 2000-2002 гг. малый и средний бизнес. Данные за 2010-2019 гг. приведены с учетом уточненных (пересмотренных) данных. 2021 год предварительные данные.

¹ «О мерах по организации деятельности агентства по развитию малого бизнеса и предпринимательства при Мин-ве экономики и промышленности Р Уз».

² <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/small-business-and-entrepreneurship-2>

Рис 1. ДИАГРАММА ДОЛИ МБЧП

Пути решения проблемы

Для решения многих экономических задач с точки зрения ее развития мы видим в проблеме глубокого экономического анализа производства и выявления резервов роста для **управления малым бизнесом и предпринимательством**. И в этом вопросе, как на правильным является **моделирование экономических процессов производства**, или организация производства на основе разработки бизнес-плана. Конечно на первый взгляд это покажется абсурдным, но мы предлагаем метод разработки программного - продукта разработки бизнес-плана, или цифровизации экономического процесса. Создание такой программы позволит упростить работу расчета экономического анализа производства, внедрения новых проектов в процесс малого производства, или нового так называемого стартапа и создать целостную систему экспертной оценки бизнес проектов.

Что это нам даст:

- Экономическая модель целостной системы экспертной оценки бизнес проектов позволит создать единую методику расчета «бизнес-плана», для системы целевого финансирования новых производств;
- Оперативно работать инвесторам с каждым клиентом по инвестиционному проекту индивидуально;
- Получать на регулярной основе оперативную информации по инвестиционным проектам;
- Повышать общий уровень оценки проектов благодаря внедрению единой методики и возможности оперативного контроля;
- Возможность перераспределения ресурсов благодаря наличию цифрового плана финансирования каждого проекта;
- Создание системы мониторинга исполнения работы по проекту инвестирования ведет к повышению уровня возврата инвестиционных ресурсов, и ускорению оборачиваемости инвестиционных ресурсов.

Что получит инвестор от внедрения «целостной системы экспертной оценки бизнес проектов»

- ✓ бизнес план будет рассчитывать программа, куда сотрудник отдела инвестиций будет вводить исходную информацию;
- ✓ на основе ввода информации будет получен результат при внедрении стартапа по периодам (месяц, квартал, год);
- ✓ имея результат по периодам расчета начиная с начального отсчета, можно определить сумму вложения на данный стартап по периодам и определить необходимое количество вложений;

- ✓ вложения можно производить по нескольким источникам: кредитным, собственным, долевым участием;
- ✓ соответственно определить соразмерность вложений, для дальнейшего распределения полученной прибыли по участникам вложений;
- ✓ на основе анализа, выводимой наглядно в диаграммах можно увидеть эффективность планируемого стартапа, количество необходимых вложений как в сумме, так и по периодам;
- ✓ ввод информации по результатам проведения нововведения, т.е. постоянной информации по периодам отчета (месяц, квартал, год) от инвестора, можно оперативно регулировать процесс финансирования стартапа;
- ✓ соответственно, риски инвестора могут быть минимальными, за счет полного контроля сотрудником инвестиционной операции. Они могут возникать при исключительных форс-мажорных обстоятельствах, либо...

Эффект от внедрения целостной системы экспертной оценки бизнес проектов состоит в следующем:

- Создание единой методики расчета «бизнес-плана», для системы целевого финансирования (привлечения инвестора);
- Оперативная работа инвесторов (индивидуальный инвестор, инвестиционный банк, инвестиционные фонды) с клиентом индивидуально по каждому проекту;
- Получать на регулярной основе оперативной информации по проекту;
- Повышение общего уровня оценки проектов благодаря внедрению единой методики и возможности оперативного контроля инвестиционных проектов;
- Возможность маневрирования с целью перераспределения финансовых ресурсов благодаря наличию цифрового плана финансирования каждого проекта;
- Создание системы мониторинга исполнения работы по проекту финансирования, что ведет к повышению уровня возврата привлеченных финансовых ресурсов, и ускорению оборачиваемости финансовых ресурсов и снижению финансовых рисков.

Нами разработана экономическая модель системы экспертной оценки бизнес проектами. Мы готовы внедрить нашу разработку при проявлении интереса со стороны представителей малого бизнеса и предпринимательства, кем могут быть технопарки при местных районных хокимиятах. Думаем это даст возможность привлечь заинтересованных инвесторов, как отдельных индивидуальных, так и представителей инвестиционных банков и финансовых фондов – финансовых ангелов.

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МАГНИЙСОДЕРЖАЩЕЙ ИЗВЕСТКОВО-АММИАЧНОЙ СЕЛИТРЫ С ДОБАВКОЙ ДОЛОМИТА И ФОСФОГИПСА

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Аннотация: Изучен процесс получения гранулированной магнийсодержащей известковой аммиачной селитры на основе смешения плава аммиачной селитры (АС) с доломитовой мукой (ДМ) и фосфогипс при массовых соотношениях АС : ДМ = 100 : (3-35). А добавку фосфогипса (ФГ) брали в количестве 5, 10 и 15% от общей массы смеси. Для гранулирования нитратно-карбонатно-гипсового расплава применён метод приллирования или окатывания. Изучены состав и свойства продуктов. Показано, что добавление как ДМ, так и ФГ к селитре значительно увеличивает прочность гранул последнего. Если для чистой АС она равна 1.32 МПа, то у удобрения с массовым соотношением АС : ДМ = 100 : 20 с добавкой 3% ФГ этот показатель составляет уже 8.14 МПа.

Ключевые слова: аммиачная селитра, доломит, фосфогипс, магнийсодержащая известково-аммиачная селитра, состав and strength of granules.

Узбекистан среди стран СНГ самый крупный производитель хлопка, на её долю приходится свыше 65% производства этого сырья. Хлопчатник занимает 43,3% посевных площадей Республики [1].

Однако из-за дефицита воды и недостаточного внесения минеральных удобрений урожай хлопка-сырца по республике составляет всего 26%. Основной дефицит приходится на долю азота, фосфора и калия. Доказано, что хлопчатник без удобрений даёт урожай 12 ц/га, а при внесении 225 кг/га N, 150 кг/га P₂O₅ и 100 кг/га K₂O получается гарантированный урожай в 30-35 ц/га. Особенности вегетационного развития хлопчатника требуют внесения под него быстрорастворимых удобрений. Исходя из специфики, наилучшим образом для возделывания подходит аммиачная селитра (АС). Она является концентрированным, дешевым в мире азотным удобрением. АС используется для подкормки всех выращиваемых культур и на любых типах почв. По данным IFA, мировые мощности по выпуску карбамида с 2014 по 2019 гг. выросли более чем на 3 млн. т в действующем веществе, АС – более чем на 1 млн. т д.в. [2]. Основной прирост приходится на долю США и России. Доли каждой этих стран в общемировых мощностях оцениваются чуть более 13% [3].

В странах СНГ лидерами на рынке азотных удобрений, включая АС являются Россия (17 заводов), Украина (6 заводов), Беларусь (1 завод) и Казахстан (1 завод). В данной группе производителей ведущее положение занимает Россия, где общий объем АС превышает 12 млн. т. Здесь лидируют АО «ОХК Уралхим», ОАО «Акрон», АО «МХК ЕвроХим», ОАО «ФосАгро» ОАО «СДС Азот», осуществляющие совместный выпуск порядка 8,0 млн. т [4]. На Украине выпуском

АС занимаются: «Азот», «СДВО Азот», «Ровноазот», концерн «Стирол» [5]. Общий объем превышает 1,2 млн. тонн.

В Узбекистане АО «Махам-Чирчиқ», «Navoiyazot» и «Ferganaazot» выпускают АС в объеме 1,7 млн. т [6]. Однако она обладает неблагоприятными для хранения свойствами: гранулы АС в воздухе слеживаются в крупные агрегаты из-за гигроскопичности, растворимости в воде и способности к полиморфизму, приводящему к разрушению гранул АС. В последние годы на мировом рынке прослеживаются четкие тенденции уменьшения спроса на это удобрение, что связано с высоким уровнем взрывоопасности NH_4NO_3 . Это провоцируют окислительные свойства NH_4NO_3 , что способствуют поддержанию его горения и взрываемости [7].

Из-за взрывоопасности Китай, Индонезия, Турция, Колумбия, Австралия, Германия, Ирландия, Филиппин, Алжир, Перу и др. ввели полный запрет на ввоз и использование АС. В странах ЕЭС, США на АС установлена заградительная пошлина, во Франции, импортируемая АС подвергается обязательному антидетонационному тестированию [8].

Доказано, что взрывоопасность АС можно снизить доведением в нём содержания азота до 26-28% путем введения в её состав различных веществ [9].

В качестве веществ - добавок, снижающих уровень потенциальной опасности АС, используют: карбонат-, калий-, фосфорсодержащие и прочие балластные вещества (гипс, фосфогипс и др.) [10].

Мы решили апробировать процесс получения магнийсодержащей известково-аммиачной селитры на основе АС путём введения в её расплав сразу двух перспективных добавок - доломитовой муки (ДМ) «Шорсу» Ферганской области и фосфогипса (ФГ) отхода производства экстракционной фосфорной кислоты (ЭФК) на Алмалыкском АО «Amphos-Maham». В отвалах этого завода скопилось около 80 млн. т ФГ.

В качестве исходных компонентов мы использовали чистую АС (34.96% N) и кристаллическую ДМ, полный химический состав образца которого приведен в таблице 1.

Таблица 1

Химический состав доломита месторождения «Шорсу» Ферганского областа

Содержание оксидов на воздушно- сухое вещество, %											
SiO ₂	TiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	MnO	CaO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	CO ₂
2.87	0.02	0.32	0.29	19.17	0.01	31.48	0.05	0.15	0.03	0.30	45.00

ДМ предварительно размалывали в фарфоровой ступке. ФГ в отвалах Алмалыка находится в виде дигидрата сульфата кальция ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) с содержанием влаги 18-20%. Поэтому, прежде чем добавлять его к АС, он высушивался в термостате при 90°C и затем измельчался в фарфоровой ступке. Состав сухого ФГ (масс. %): $\text{P}_2\text{O}_{5\text{общ}}$.1.59; $\text{P}_2\text{O}_{5\text{усв}}$.1.48; $\text{P}_2\text{O}_{5\text{водн}}$.1.12; $\text{CaO}_{\text{общ}}$.37.47; $\text{CaO}_{\text{усв}}$.19.08; $\text{CaO}_{\text{водн}}$.11.26; $\text{SO}_{3\text{общ}}$.54.49; $\text{SO}_{3\text{усв}}$.27.4; $\text{SO}_{3\text{водн}}$.16.88. Опыты проводили следующим образом: Навеска АС марки х.ч. расплавлялась при 175°C в металлической чашке путём электрообогрева. ДМ добавлялась к АС в таком количестве, чтобы массовое соотношение АС : ДМ в смеси варьировало от 100 : 3 до 100 : 45. А ФГ брали в количестве 3, 5, 7 и 10% от общей массы смеси. Смесь тщательно перемешивалась. Расплавы выдерживались при температуре 170-175°C. Общее время взаимодействия компонентов составляло 10 мин. Нитратно-карбонатно-гипсовой расплав после окончания взаимодействия компонентов переливался в фарфоровую чашку и по мере остывания интенсивно размешивался стеклянной палочкой, в результате чего происходило

гранулообразование. Масса охлаждалась, а затем рассеивалась по размерам частиц. Частицы с размерами 2-3 мм подверглись испытанию на прочность по ГОСТ 21560.2-82 [11]. После чего продукты измельчались и анализировались. Содержание азота в продуктах определяли по Кьельдалю – отгонкой аммиака в щелочной среде со сплавом Декарда с последующим титрованием [12]. Содержание SO_3^{2-} -ион определяли весовым - осаждением в виде сульфата бария [13]. Содержание P_2O_5 определяли дифференциальным способом [14]. Определение содержания CaO осуществляли комплексонометрическим методом [15].

Результаты приведены в таблице 2.

Результаты показывают, что чем больше доля ДМ в смеси, тем ниже содержание азота, тем выше содержание кальция и магния в продукте. С увеличением количества добавки ФГ увеличивается содержание серы в продукте, но при этом снижается содержание азота, кальция и магния. Так, в получаемом магнийсодержащей известково-аммиачной селитре при массовых соотношениях АС : ДМ от 100 : 3 до 100 : 45 при 3% добавке фосфогипса содержание азота снижается от 32.94 до 23.39%, а содержание SO_3 , CaO и MgO увеличивается от 1.56 до 1.68%, от 2.0 до 10.58% и 0.52 до 5.74% соответственно. При этом сумма питательных компонентов (N+ SO_3 + CaO+MgO) находится в пределах 37.02-41.39%.

Таблица 2

Состав и прочность гранул образцов ИАС, полученных введением в расплав аммиачной селитры доломитовой муки и фосфогипса

Массовое соотношение АС : ДМ	Содержание ФГ в смеси, %	Содержание компонентов, мас. %				Прочность гранул МПа
		N	SO_3	CaO	MgO	
NH_4NO_3 «х.ч.»		34.96	–	–	–	1.32
100 : 3	3	32.94	1.56	2.0	0.52	4.36
100 : 3	5	32.21	2.75	2.75	0.51	4.52
100 : 3	7	31.56	3.81	3.47	0.49	4.81
100 : 3	10	30.55	5.44	4.55	0.48	5.03
100 : 10	3	30.83	1.62	3.89	1.65	6.29
100 : 10	5	30.21	2.71	4.56	1.62	6.51
100 : 10	7	29.56	3.79	5.26	1.59	6.72
100 : 10	10	28.61	5.42	6.31	1.53	6.96
100 : 20	3	28.27	1.63	6.21	3.06	8.14
100 : 20	5	27.67	2.71	6.84	3.01	8.31
100 : 20	7	27.09	3.82	7.49	2.95	8.68
100 : 20	10	26.21	5.43	8.45	2.84	8.82
100 : 30	3	26.09	1.62	8.15	4.26	10.02
100 : 30	5	25.54	2.71	8.76	4.18	10.25
100 : 30	7	25.02	3.81	9.36	4.09	10.47
100 : 30	10	24.19	5.41	10.27	3.96	10.72
100 : 40	3	24.21	1.63	9.84	5.28	11.90
100 : 40	5	23.71	2.71	10.39	5.17	12.13
100 : 40	7	23.22	3.79	10.95	5.06	12.32

100 : 40	10	22.46	5.43	11.81	4.89	12.55
100 : 45	3	23.39	1.68	10.58	5.74	12.81
100 : 45	5	22.26	2.72	11.14	5.61	13.07
100 : 45	7	22.41	3.79	11.69	5.49	13.29
100 : 45	10	21.72	5.39	12.49	5.31	13.68

Основными достоинствами магнийсодержащей ИАС перед традиционной АС является то, что помимо азота она имеет три дополнительных компонента – серу, кальций и магний. Сера входит в состав белков и аминокислот при формировании урожая. По физиологической роли в питании растений серу следует поставить на третье место после азота и фосфора [16]. Известно, что кальций помогает движению углеводов и повышает растворимость многих элементов питания в почве, способствуя тем самым лучшему их поглощению растениями. Магний входит в состав хлорофилла, принимая участие в фотосинтезе. Кроме того он активизирует ферменты, которые ответственны за поглощение и усвоение фосфора растениями. При дефиците магния происходит замедление и остановка роста растений. Необходимо отметить, что от кальция и магния зависит прочность стенок клеток и их сцепление, обеспечивая рост и развитие корневой системы [17]. Таким образом, можно говорить, что состав АС дополнительно обогащается тремя макроэлементами – серой, кальцием и магнием.

Но самое интересное заключается в том, что с ростом долей ДМ и ФГ в расплаве селитры увеличивается прочность гранул получаемого удобрения. Как ранее уже отмечалось, прочность гранул чистой АС составляет 1.32 МПа. При расплаве с массовым соотношением АС : ДМ = 100 : 3 и с 3 %-ной добавкой фосфогипса прочность гранул получаемого удобрения составляет уже 4.36 МПа. При расплаве с массовым соотношением АС : ДМ = 100 : 25 и с такой же 3 %-ной добавкой фосфогипса прочность гранул удобрения возрастает до 9.10 МПа. А при расплаве с массовым соотношением АС : ДМ = 100 : 45 и с такой же 3 %-ной добавкой фосфогипса прочность гранул удобрения возрастает до 12.81 МПа, а с 10 %-ной добавкой фосфогипса уже 13.68 МПа. Чем выше прочность гранул, тем меньше их пористость и внутренняя удельная поверхность её гранул, тем меньше дизтоплива попадает внутрь гранул, и как следствие, тем в меньшей степени детонационная способность селитры.

Таким образом, на основе результатов лабораторных исследований показана возможность процесса получения магнийсодержащей ИАС на основе плава АС с ДМ месторождения Шорсу Ферганской области и ФГ отхода производства экстракционной фосфорной кислоты (ЭФК) на Алмалыкском АО «Аммофос-Махам». ДМ и ФГ позволяет устранить ряд недостатков АС, в частности закисление почв при длительном применении данного удобрения, улучшает физико-химические и потребительские свойства удобрения: увеличивает прочность гранул, уменьшает слеживаемость и взрывоопасность.

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The History of Flags of States on the Territory of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. This article provides information and a comparative analysis of the national symbols and flags of the Golden Horde, the Timurid states, the Bukhara, Khiva and Kokand khanates and the Turkestan autonomy that exist in our country.

Key words: State symbols, flag, Hun Empire, Turkic states, image of a wolf's head, Timurid flag, image of three circles, period of the Khanate, crescent and five-pointed star, autonomy of Turkestan.

After the demise of the Timurid Empire the Khanate of Bukhara was established in 1533; it became an Emirate in 1785 which lasted until 1920. The only known flag from this period was the elaborate Royal Standard of the last Emir, Alim Khan. Meanwhile, in the western Khorezm area the Khanate of Khiva had existed since 1511. It was conquered by the Russian Empire in 1873 and became a quasi-independent Russian protectorate. It is not certain, but a white flag with a light blue crescent may have existed during that time. Meanwhile, the Khanate of Kokand in the western Fergana Valley had been established in 1709 but was annexed by the Russian Empire in 1883, becoming part of the vast territory of Russian Turkestan; there are no known flags of this period.

The flag of Emirate of Bukhara

In 1550 the Khanate of Bukhara was established and it became an Emirate in 1785 upon the assumption of rulership by the Manghit emir, Shah Murad. It is not known if there was a national flag, but the Royal Standard of Emir Mohammed Alim Khan, who ruled from 1910 to 1920, displayed on a three-pointed green field the Islamic crescent and star, the Hand of Fatima (the Prophet Muhammad's daughter), a sign of protection and the name of the emir written in Arabic script near the hoist and the "Shahada", the Muslim Article of Faith, near the fly, all in gold. It had an orange border with black ornamentation and the three points of the flag also had black diamond shaped tassels.

After the Russian Revolution in 1917 there were also calls for reform in the traditional lands of Central Asia. In 1917 an anti-Bolshevik Kokand Autonomous State was proclaimed, hoisting a flag of red over dark blue with a white star and crescent in the centre. This lasted until 20 February 1918 when Soviet troops demolished much of Kokand and massacred thousands of its people. In Khiva a civil war broke out in 1917, between pro- and anti-monarchists; the latter joined with the Bolsheviks and in 1920 Khiva's last

Khan, Sayid Abdullah, abdicated, the Khanate was abolished and the Khorezm People's Soviet Republic was declared. During this civil war a flag consisting of a black field within broad green stripes and a yellow crescent and star in its centre, was flown, followed by a flag showing a yellow crescent and star on a red field, with a green border and a red flag with, in a green canton, a yellow crescent and star; its points pointed towards the fly or upwards. This changed in 1922 when, in the canton, also a crossed spade, sickle and cotton plant appeared. In 1923 the country's name changed to Khorezm Socialist Soviet Republic and its flag took on much more of a communist and Soviet symbolism.

Bukharan People's Soviet Republic (BXSR) 1920

When in 1920 the last Emir of Bukhara, Alim Khan, fled, the Bukharan People's Soviet Republic was established. It was reported there was a red flag with a crescent in the centre and the initials of the state, BNSR in Russian Cyrillic the hoist, in white or gold. That same year a flag, green over red with, in gold, the crescent and star appeared; both the green colour and the crescent and star are associated with Islam. In the hoist the initials of the state, in gold, were now in the Uzbek "Yanga imlâ" Arabic script: BKhShJ (Buxoro Xalq Sho'ro Jumhuriyati). A year later a small red hammer and sickle emblem appeared inside the gold star, combining Islamic and Soviet symbols. The initials of the state were again in Russian Cyrillic: BNSR (Bukharskaya Narodnaya Sovyetskaya Respublika). On 11 October 1923 a new constitution was adopted and the background of the flag was changed to red, with the initials of the state's name, in gold, again in the Uzbek "Yanga imlâ" Arabic script. A year later, on 19 November 1924 the name of the state was changed to the Bukharan Soviet Socialist Republic and 5 days later it was incorporated in the Uzbek SSR.

On 30 April 1918, following the Russian revolution of 1917, the Bolsheviks in Tashkent created the Turkestan Socialist Federative Republic, soon renamed the Turkestan Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic (ASSR), an autonomous republic of the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic. Its flag, possibly dating from 1919, was plain red with in the upper hoist in yellow, the letters "TASSR" in both Yanga imlâ Arabic lettering and Russian Cyrillic. Meanwhile in September 1921 the Union of Central Asian Islamic National Insurgent Organisations instituted an all-Turkestan flag, with nine alternating red and white stripes, an orange rectangle bearing a white star and crescent and a narrow light-blue border around it. This very popular flag was used until January 1924 when the last part of Turkestan territory fell to the Red Army. It was associated with the Basmachi movement, an uprising, since 1916, against Russian Imperial and Soviet rule by the Muslim peoples of Central Asia. Because the Bolsheviks excluded the Muslim people, they battled against Soviet rule.

Bukharan people's Soviet Republic

When after calls reform and Russia invasion, on 31 august 1920 Emir Mohammed Alim Khan fled to Dushanbe and later Afganistan, Bukharan People's Soviet Republic was established. It was reported to have flown a red flag qith a cresent in the centre and the initials of the state, BNRS (Buharskaya Narodnaya Sovyetskaya Respublika) in Russian Cyrillic at the hoist. Probably this was in white or gold.

On 27 October 1924 the Uzbek SSR was proclaimed, one of the 5 Soviet Socialist Republics created along ethnic lines as determined by Joseph Stalin, Vladimir Lenin's Commissar for Nationalities, out of the Turkestan and the Bukharan and Khorezm Soviet Republics. Its capital was in Samarkand until 1930. The flag was red with in the canton the abbreviation of the republic's name, Uz.S.S.R., in both Yanga imlâ Arabic lettering (in which Uzbek was written) and Russian Cyrillic, surrounded by a thin border, all in yellow. It included the Tajik ASSR, that had its own flag, until 1929, when that autonomous republic was upgraded to a full SSR. In 1928 the modified Arabic script, new script or New Alphabet, was abolished in the Soviet Union and the Latin "Yangalif" (New Alphabet), that had been developed since 1924, was now mandated; the flags were changed accordingly. This lasted until 1941 when the Latin scripts were abolished and Cyrillic was mandated, causing the flags to be changed accordingly. In 1952 all Soviet Socialist Republics obtained flags with striped designs, based on the red flag of the USSR with at the upper hoist the hammer and sickle emblem in gold, with above it a gold-fimbriated red star. The new flag for the Uzbek SSR was adopted on 29 August 1952 and displayed a light blue horizontal stripe through the centre, with white fimbriation. The flag was slightly changed after the hammer and sickle emblem was redesigned.

On 20 June 1990 the Uzbek SSR became a sovereign state within the USSR and on 31 August 1991 it declared independence as the Republic of Uzbekistan. A new flag was adopted on 18 November 1991:

light blue over white over light green, with thin red stripes separating the three stripes. In the upper hoist is a white crescent and 12 white stars. Those may stand for Islam (or the rebirth of the nation) and the 12 districts of Uzbekistan; another interpretation is the zodiac and the historical traditions of the Uzbek people, as well as the ancient solar calendar. Blue stands for water as a source of life, white for peace, green for nature and red for the life force; there are other interpretations as well. The autonomous Republic of Karakalpakstan, that had been added to Uzbekistan in 1936 and whose flags had also changed over the years, adopted a flag, similar to that of Uzbekistan, but with an ochre band as the central stripe and 5 stars, standing for the 5 districts of Karakalpakstan. The State emblems are similar too and retain some elements from the Soviet-era emblems.

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Sinfdan Tashqari Mashg'ulotlar Jarayonida Kichik Yoshdagi Maktab O'Quvchilarining Divergent Fikrlashini Shakllantirish

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada ta'lim muassasasida tizimli ta'limning dastlabki bosqichida kichik yoshdagi maktab o'quvchilarining turli xil fikrlashlari bevosita ularning hayotiy tajribasiga va kattalar tomonidan boshqariladigan va rag'batlantirilgan kognitiv faoliyatda o'quvchining shaxsiy faolligi namoyon bo'lishi haqida fikr mulohazalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy ta'lim, ijodiy fazilat, intellektual, divergent, divergent fikrlash, ta'lim, eksperiment, motivatsion, kognitiv va shaxsiy-refleksiv.

Divergent fikrlashning mohiyati uning tarkibiy qismi – divergentsiya orqali o'rganiladi. Divergentsiya umumiy ilmiy hodisa bo'lib, uning turi (yoki xilma-xilligi), alohida sifat, faoliyat, mavjudlik va rivojlanish xususiyati sifatida tavsiflanadi. Har qanday turdagi obyektlar davrida integral obyektning mulki yoki qobiliyati qismlarga bo'linadi va yangi bir butunga birlashadi.

Divergent fikrlashga bag'ishlangan asarlarda kichik maktab o'quvchilarining turli xil fikrlashlarining xarakterli belgilari aqliy faoliyat jarayonida obyekt belgilarining chegaralarini xiralashtirishni o'z ichiga oladi; ularning bir-biriga "oqishi", tushunchalarning moslashuvchan tuzilishi. Bu xususiyatlar boshlang'ich maktab yoshini divergent fikrlashni shakllantirish uchun sezgir yosh deb belgilashga imkon beradi.

Tafakkurni talqin qilish inson psixikasining faoliyat tabiati asosida amalga oshiriladi, bu bizga shakllanishi va rivojlanishiga oid savollarni ko'tarish va hal qilish imkonini beradi. Rus olimlaridan A.N. Leontiev, P.Ya. Galperin, Rubinshteylar kichik maktab o'quvchilarini maqsadli o'rganish natijasida fikrlashini kengaytirib, boyitib borishini o'rgangan.

Yosh talabalarning tafakkuri turlicha mahsuldorligi past, tanqidiyligi past va refleksliligi bilan ajralib turadi, u yuzaki, beqaror, ozgina ongli; uning amaliy tomoni og'zaki-mantiqiy tomondan ustunlik qiladi; talablarda divergent fikrlash mahsuli uchun g'oyalar, mezonlar yetarli emas yoki zaif ifodalangan.

Yosh bolalarda divergent fikrlashni shakllantirishning psixologik-pedagogik mexanizmini to'liqroq ochib berish uchun maktab o'quvchilari uchun asosiy mezonlarni (motivatsion, kognitiv va shaxsiy refleksiv) sanab o'tamiz.

Motivatsion mezon divergent fikrlashda qidiruv motivatsiyasining intensivligini aks ettiradi. Idrokning motivi va maqsadi mos kelsa, jarayon fikrlash rivojlanadi, shu jumladan jarayonning o'z-o'zidan harakatlanishi, chiqish imkoniyati "ijodiy maydon" holatidan tashqarida. Kognitiv mezon taklif qiladi kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilar ongida uning aqliy faoliyati natijalarini aks ettirish, ichkilashtirish jarayonlarini amalga oshirish, birlashtirish, analoglarni topish, obyektlarni qayta qurish, resurslardan oqilona foydalanish qobiliyati; ochiq turdagi muammolarni ularning bilimlaridan kelib chiqqan holda hal qilish; qiziquvchanlik, kognitiv faollik. Shaxsiy-refleksiv mezon boshlang'ich maktab yoshida kam rivojlangan, ammo shaxsiy strategiya va taktikalarni izlash, kashf qilish, ishlab chiqish jarayonida yetakchi rol o'ynaydigan faoliyat natijalarini tushunish va introspeksiya qilishning ichki jarayonlari bilan belgilanadi. fikrlashning kognitiv, motivatsion va shaxsiy jihatlari va yagona funktsional maydonning organik aloqasi va kirib borishini ta'minlaydigan "nostandart" muammoni aks ettirish orqali hal qilish. Yoshlarda divergent fikrlash ko'proq darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar jarayonida muvaffaqiyatli shakllanib, rivojlanib boradi.

Sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar umumta'lim muassasasi ta'lim jarayonining ajralmas qismi. Maktab o'quvchilarining intellektual va ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish uchun zarur bo'lgan tanlov, o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash, ixtiyoriylik tamoyillariga asoslangan va ularga vitagenik o'sish bilan bog'liq ijtimoiy, shaxsiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan tajribaga ega bo'lish imkoniyatini beradi.

Kichik maktab o'quvchilarining sinergetik yondashuv asosida divergent fikrlash, buxgalteriya hisobini shakllantirish asoslarini funktsional aniqlashga yordam berishini, o'quv jarayoni sub'ektlarining quyi tizimlar sifatida almashish imkoniyati ma'lumot, kognitiv faoliyatni o'z-o'zini tashkil etish va o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish istagilar o'rgatiladi. Tizimli-faollik yondashuvi modelning tizimli xususiyatlarini o'rnatishga, strukturaning morfologik tavsifini amalga oshirishga, bosqichlar, kutilayotgan asosiy va oraliq natijalar, jarayonni qurish kognitiv faoliyatda muvaffaqiyatga olib keladigan, ularning tashqi va ichki motivlarini hisobga olishga yo'naltirilgan kichik maktab o'quvchilarida turlicha fikrlashni shakllantirishga qaratiladi. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv buxgalteriya hisobini belgilaydi shaxsiy xususiyatlarning divergent fikrlashini shakllantirish jarayoni kichik maktab o'quvchilari, hayotiy tajribani yangisiga aylantirish imkoniyati operativ, predmetli va fanlararo bilimlar, natijalar beradi shaxsiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan divergent fikrlashni shakllantiradi.

Kichik maktab o'quvchilarida sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar jarayonida divergent fikrlashni shakllantirish modelini muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirishni ta'minlash uchun o'quvchilarning darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda motivatsiyasiga yo'naltirish zarur.

Muvaffaqiyatli vaziyatlarda qatnashish, masalan, oldindan maqtov orqali, bolaning haqiqiy rivojlanish zonasi, shakllari asosida vazifalarni tanlash yosh o'quvchilarning kognitiv faoliyatga doimiy ehtiyoji; tengdoshlari, o'qituvchilari bilan ijtimoiy aloqalarni kengaytirishi bilan bog'liq. Bunday aloqa jarayonlarida muvaffaqiyat holatlarini muntazam ravishda yaratish Divergent tipdagi muammolarni hal qilish motivatsion jihatdan konsolidatsiyaga olib keladi. Kichik maktab o'quvchilari sohasida ichki motivatsiya, muvaffaqiyatga erishish motivi barqaror shaxsiy ta'lim sifatida yuzaga keladi.

Umumta'lim muassasasining ta'lim va maktabdan tashqari faoliyatning yaxlitligini ta'minlaydigan rivojlanayotgan ta'lim muhitini yaratishni nazarda tutadi. Ushbu shartning ma'nosi o'zini anglash orqali shaxsning samarali rivojlanishida yotadi umumiy ta'lim muassasasining yaxlit ta'lim makonining boy muhitiga bo'lgan ehtiyoji o'quvchilarning darsdan tashqari faoliyatining o'ziga xosligini isbotlaydi, rolini ochib beradi. Samarali vositalarni: mashqlar, eksperimentlar, divergent tipdagi vazifalar, o'z-o'zini diagnostika va boshqalar, kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilarning mustaqil kognitiv faoliyatini rivojlantirishga imkon beradi; yangi, ilgari noma'lum natijaga erishish uchun dastlabki vaziyatni o'zgartirish qobiliyati, aks ettirish, "sezuvchanlik" ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish, fikrlash avtonomiyasini saqlab qolgan holda tashqaridan yordam berish kerak bo'ladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda kichik maktab o'quvchilarining turlicha fikrlashlari o'rganishda, uchta mezon bo'yicha baholash ko'rib chiqildi: motivatsion, kognitiv va shaxsiy-refleksiv. Yosh bolalarning divergent fikrlash shakllanishining uch darajasi idrok, o'zgartirish, bilimlarni ijodiy qo'llash kabi xususiyatlari tavsiflab berildi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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Уровень Жизни В Узбекистане И Его Устойчивое Развитие

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются различные показатели, характеризующие уровень и качество жизни, совокупный доход, экономическое состояние Республики Узбекистан, а также пути повышения уровня жизни населения.

Ключевые слова: *Популяция, уровень жизни, экономический рост, валютный курс, инфляция, совокупный доход.*

Не зависимо от того, какие политические социальные действия осуществляется каждая страна, их конечной целью является повышение интереса народа повышение уровня жизни населения, выход в ряды стран - лидеров.

Численность населения Узбекистан по состоянию на 1 января 2023 года составила 36 млн 24 тысяч. 946 человек. За год увеличено на 753,6 тыс. 18 млн 335,7 тысяч. человек проживает в городах, а 17 млн 689,2 тысяч. человек - в сельских районах. Численность мужского пола составляет 18 млн 128 тысяч 578 , женского пола - 17 млн 896 тысяч 368 .

Доля доходов от производства в общих доходах населения составила 71,5 % , из них 69% получено от трудовой деятельности 2,1 % получено от бытовых услуг, производственных для личного потребления.

В развитых странах заработная плата составляет 60-80 % всех доходов населения который служит основой для обеспечения их нормально жизнедеятельности , а в Узбекистане не так, в нашей стране зарплаты остаются неизменными но растут цены на продукты питания и услуги. Общеизвестно, что если никого не волнует условия жизни простых людей, то это отражается в гармоничном развитии общества страны.

Простой пример - на одну среднюю зарплату автомобиль не купишь, даже на годовую среднюю зарплату.

В условиях кризисной ситуации и ограничительных мер малообеспеченных слои населения будут более чувствительны к изменению цен на основные потребительские товары. Учитывая, что основная часть малообеспеченного населения работает в неформальном секторе экономики, снижение экономической активности в первую очередь сказывается на их доходах. Многие бизнесмены ради собственной выгоды в кризисном периоде поднимает цены не думая о населении. Например, когда не было света спрос на свечу увеличился, и из-за этого росли цены на свечи. К сожалению, таких примеров много...

Рассмотрим уровни « богатство и бедности » Узбекистана :

Американское издание « Global Finance Magazine » составило рейтинг самых богатых стран мира, в который были включены 185 государств. Узбекистан занял 127 место в рейтинге самых богатых стран мира. Общий объем совокупного дохода населения достиг более 371,3 трлн. сумов. Об этом сообщает Госкомстат Узбекистана.

Узбекистан традиционно входит в топ-10 стран мира по добыче золота. Так, в 2019 году - 101,6 тонны. Это позволило Узбекистан занять восьмую строчку рейтинг. Крупнейшим горнодобывающим предприятием Узбекистана, специализирующемся на добыче и переработке золота, является Навоийский ГМК. Объем его производства составляет около 80 тонн золота в год.

Определение черты бедности в стране: Минимальные потребительские расходы повышены на 13,2% - с 440 тысяч до 498 тысяч сумов в месяц.

Объем внешнего долга Узбекистана в 2021 году увеличился на 16% и приблизился к 40 миллиардам долларов. Это 57% ВВП. В частности, в 2021 году государственный внешний долг увеличился на 11% и достиг 23,7 млрд долларов. Частный внешний долг увеличился на 24% по сравнению с началом 2021 года и составил 15,8 млрд долларов.

Несмотря на разработанные стратегии и решения, Узбекистан входит в число бедных стран. Потому что многие госорганы в основном думают о своей выгоде а не об экономике государства !

Я считаю что для повышения уровня жизни населения надо:

- осуществление замены специалистов по каждому направлению. Рациональное организации системы управления , для этого необходимо искоренить коррупцию.
- умение правильно оценивать умственную и физическую работу.
- справедливая цена на товары.

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Xxi Century is – a Century of Intellectual Generations

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Annation. The population of Uzbekistan hopes on the younger generation. If you ask any of our compatriots about the meaning of life, they will reply without hesitations: seeing the happiness and well-being of their children. It stands to reason why the first order of Uzbekistan was named “Soglom Avlod Uchun” (For a Healthy Generation), and a monument to a mother and child stands on Independence Square. It is not easy to find a country in the world where people treat children so kindly, love and praise them infinitely.

The government has been paying close attention to the upbringing of healthy and comprehensively advanced generation. The state youth policy ranks among priorities. Every step in this direction is supported by the population, causing excitement among the people.

Development of children's sports has become another important component of raising a healthy generation. More than 2 million children are regularly engaged in 30 kinds of sports in modern sports complexes in all regions of the country, including remote villages. The involvement of girls in sports as future mothers, and strengthening of their health is of special attention.

As our first President Islam Karimov said: “The interest, enthusiasm and love for sports in our children should be formed from early childhood. Only in this case can we make sports a constant companion in the people’s lives”. “We can reach the intended goal by attracting children to sports at preschool and early school age. At the same time, we must not forget that each child has a vast inner world, and a special attention should be attached to this,” he underlined.

“Only those children who regularly go in for sports at an early age will grow physically strong and healthy. This will allow each parent to achieve his or her dream – to raise healthy children and to establish a healthy lifestyle in the society. “Sports from an early age strengthen the child’s character, through participation in competitions he or she form such qualities as strength and courage, the desire to victory, first of all victory over himself or herself, and foundations for strong will are laid. By victory over oneself I mean that this is primarily self-education, strong discipline, elimination of shortcomings and overcoming difficulties,” Islam Karimov said.

It’s explicit that without the development of children’s sports, we cannot ensure the future of the Uzbek sports and increase its fame on the international arena.

It is not a secret today that sport is becoming the most efficient and effective way of demonstrating the potential of the nation and raising the national pride and honor. If in 2005, absolutely healthy children accounted for 52.7 percent, in 2010 this figure reached 62.6 percent. Considering that in the developed world, the figure is 70 to 72 percent, it is obvious that Uzbekistan has achieved significant growth in this direction.

In 2010, compared to 2005, the incidence of acute respiratory viral infections among students fell by 12.8 per cent, pneumonia by 15.5, bronchitis by 16.2 and scoliosis by 11.6 percent. Over the past five years, the height of boys aged 10-14 increased by an average of 2.3 centimeters and girls by 2 centimeters, while weight increased by 2.6 and 2.9 kilograms respectively, Islam Karimov said.

“The children’s sport plays an immeasurably important role in achieving the great goal we set, which is upbringing the harmoniously developed generation, making our children the decisive force in the society,

and Uzbekistan's gaining its rightful place among the developed countries. I think there is no need to dwell on this issue.

“In this regard, I would like to note once again that in the 21st century of uncompromising competition, only a generation and a nation that is physically strong, spiritually mature and intellectually rich may win.

It is important that the girls, who go in for sports today, will bring the love to sports to their children when they become mothers. This is the essence and value of the “Healthy mother – healthy child” program implemented in the country

Uzbekistan has many reasons for being proud of its young people with firm convictions and active civic position, devoted to the Motherland. One cannot but be proud of, for example, our Olympians and Paralympians who brought an unprecedented ‘harvest’ of medals from Rio de Janeiro, and raised high the prestige of the Uzbek sports. One cannot but be proud of our students, who win subject Olympiads each year, suggesting the uniqueness of the National Staff Training Program, which already produces an “explosive” effect, our young artists, as they demonstrate the value of the national culture at home and abroad.

Coming to this theme first of all let me say that young generations are very smart ones. Day by day their number is increasing. It is the fact that this is influence of our government. Of course our country is paying more attention. That's why the intellectual ones are doing their best on every side of science. But not only from science but also from sport. Uzbekistan pays great attention to the development and promotion of sports and physical culture. Over the years of independence the country has established an effective system of training of professional athletes, coaches and referees. The implementation of these objectives in every way contributes to promotion of healthy life-style, education of harmoniously developed young people, further development of physical culture and sports in the country. An important legal basis for ongoing reforms in this area is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Physical Culture and Sports” and other laws and regulations directed to involvement of people, especially young people, women and children, to physical culture and sports.

Young boys and girls, professionals of individual and game disciplines, are showing exclusive preparation and phenomenal skills at representative forums; eloquently confirm that they represent a country with rich sports traditions. The results of the measures can be seen in the growing number of our fellow citizens who are involved in sports and won prizes at various international tournaments.

Since the Olympic Games in Atlanta in 1996 and till the London Olympic Winter Games in 1994 in Lillehammer till the Olympic Winter Games in Sochi in 2014, our athletes won 6 gold, 5 silver, and 10 bronze medals. In 2014, at the XVII Summer Asian Games and Paraasian Games held in the South Korean city of Incheon, our athletes have successfully defended the honor of the country. In the Asian Games 2014, 61 Uzbek athletes ranked among the winners, and at Paraasian games our compatriots 22 times rose to the highest step of podium. In addition, 15 of our Paralympic athletes have already won the license to the XV Paralympic Games to be held in Rio de Janeiro in 2016.

The country has a strong focus on the selection of talented young athletes from among the pupils clubs, teams and organization of training to improve sport skills, creation of necessary conditions for strengthening the sports reserve on the basis of further development of the high school of sports and colleges of Olympic Games.

Achievements of Uzbekistan in Integration of Education and Science

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***Annation.** For over the years of independence the Republic of Uzbekistan has carried out fundamental, structural and substantive reforms that have encompassed all levels of education system and its components, which were aimed at ensuring its compliance with the long-term objectives and interests of the country, modern requirements, as well as international standards. The appropriate legal framework reforming this sector was created, which defined as a priority the growth of investment, as well as the investments in human capital, training of educated and intellectually developed generation, which is the crucial asset and a decisive force in the achievement of democratic development, modernization and renewal, ensuring stable and sustainable growth of the economy.*

Today's rapidly globalization period requires renewal and growth of integration in every field, innovative thinking and the collective innovative environment based on them. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "...the most important task is to form innovative thinking in the minds of our people. Without innovation, they will be no development and no competition..."

Collective innovation is the achievement of integration in the field of social and economic sectors, the creation of conditions for the expression of original inventions on the basis of inheritance and the development of the principle of "knowledge through science" to the level of innovation. The modern world has shown that the integration of innovative knowledge begins with an idea that arises from a deep understanding of these problems, active cooperation of scientific and technical personnel in this area, a prosperous life based on renewal, a factor that ensures social and economic growth, i.e. market.

In order to ensure the integration between science and education, in 2020, 65 academicians of the Academy of Sciences visited 33 academic lyceums, 27 professional colleges, 29 higher education institutions and 36 economic organizations, 21 agricultural research and production centers of Uzbekistan. Academicians and corresponding members were attached to 8 academic lyceums, 8 professional colleges, 8 higher education institutions and 13 economic organizations of the Republic.

A total of 162 action plans have been developed for the work carried out in educational institutions and organizations attached to academics, including 125 for academicians of the Academy of Sciences, 37 for academicians and corresponding members of the Uzbek Agricultural Research and Production Centre.

Universities are endowed with independence in integrating education and science in the world. For example, in terms of increasing scientific indicators in production, academic and scientific independence, independent determination of their scientific direction and forms of conduct research, educational institutions have the approach to work and management of education and research too. In this regard, we are also declining the functions of state control in the field of education and science year by year as well as creating ample opportunities for freedom of scientific activity. As a result of the on-going works to ensure the integration of education and science, overcoming the existing restrictions on the involvement of talented young people in scientific activities, the organization of research on the basis of PhD and strengthening scientific capacity and selection of highly qualified persons are being created to further enhance the prestige of scientific institutions and form new scientific institutions in the country. As a result of science management is supported a number of initiatives to establish cooperation between universities and research institutes. One of the most important events in the country is also the

establishment of both financial incentives and advocacy to raise the social status of scientific and scientific-pedagogical persons.

As a result of reform in the awarding of academic degrees, the potential of personnel with academic degrees has increased 5 times in the country over the past 5 years. This means that more and more young people are interested in scientific researches. In terms of sectors, the following significant figures can be cited 44% (2308 people) of those certified in DSc, PhD degrees are in the field of exact, natural and technical sciences, 40% (2095 people) in socio-humanitarian sciences and 15% (805 people) in medicine. During this period, about 200 graduates worked in foreign universities, among them the share of exact, technical and natural sciences – 59% (98 people), social and humanities sciences – 30% (50 people), medical sciences – 11 % (18 people) respectively. For comparison, in the period up to 2016, the approval of diplomas abroad was difficult, in 3 years only 7 diplomas were recognized, the existing artificial barriers were overcome, and the reforms in education and science in the country were based on the principle of international integration.

As a result of increasing the participation of women in society and scientific activities, creating good conditions for their effective participation, the share of women in the scientifically proven structure is about 40% (31% for DSc, 36% for PhD).

Currently, another important reform that is taking place to strengthen the scientific and academic status of universities should not be missed. In the previous period, the role of the state was gradually reduced in supervising the activities of universities, and a decision was made at the political level to give universities the authority to approve academic degrees and academic titles independently in the country. Certainly, this is expected to be done gradually, but in 10 years it will be possible to increase the scientific potential of universities have a good opportunity to attract foreign professors and create a basis for the integration and internationalization of education. In 2019, the National University of Uzbekistan for Binary Defence was authorized to independently approve candidates for the degrees of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) and Doctor of Science (DSc), in 2020 the Institute of Mathematics and the Institute of Plant Chemistry, Institute of Polymer Chemistry and Physics, Uzbekistan National University, Institute of Biophysics and Biochemistry, Institute of Botanic, Karakalpak State University, Institute of Mineral Resources and Tashkent University of Information Technologies have been given the right to certify employees in academic titles.

Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan has developed 39 approved projects for the commercialization of research results and their introduction into the state economy. They belong to different sectors of the economy and are expected to be implemented in collaboration with manufacturers and scientists.

International experience also shows that many developed countries, such as South Korea, China, Japan, France, Turkey, Indonesia, Israel, Singapore, have mechanisms to encourage young people to study abroad, return home and use their scientific potential. This international experience will serve as an important experience for the development of other developing countries.

The start of promising reforms in Uzbekistan is also reflected in an increase in the number of young people studying abroad. Over the past three years, more than 3000 young Uzbeks have been trained at prestigious international universities, including France, Italy, Spain, Germany, Denmark, Austria, Czech Republic, Ukraine, the Baltic countries and the Balkans. The qualified youth trained at these universities contributes to the comprehensive development of our country.

There are a number of notable works in the science of Uzbekistan to support young people. In 2020, the activities of the Council of Young Scientists of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Laboratory of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology of the Institute of Zoology and the Department of Zoology of the Faculty of Biology of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek. The subject of “Applied Molecular Zoology” was introduced, which revealed its great potential. Its purpose is to train young scientists in the field of taxonomy, biogeography, and evolution and phylogenetic of the animal world using molecular data.

It is noteworthy that the bilateral relations of the institutes of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan with international research centres have been strengthened. An Uzbek-Chinese centre for the production of medicines has been opened, and joint Uzbek-Chinese research laboratories have been established at a number of institutes. Relations with international organizations such as UNESCO, IAEA, MAAN and TWAS have been strengthened. Bilateral cooperation of research institutions of the Academy of Sciences with leading research centers and organizations of foreign countries is carried out. South Korean and Turkish companies have signed Memorandums of cooperation and investment agreements worth \$ 236.6 million.

By the way, the Startup ecosystem, which is an important link in the integration of science, has opened up new and prospective directions for the country. Over the years, a number of startup platforms have been established, including the Tech Central Asia Tashkent Startup Project Competition in partnership with the Turkish Council for Scientific and Technological Research (TUBITAK) and the US Embassy in Uzbekistan, the Startup initiatives in partnership with the Chamber of Commerce and Industry, as well as the United Nations Development Program. Of course, the link, which is important for the startup ecosystem, also supports government initiatives to develop venture funds. In particular, according to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to organize the activities of the National Venture Fund” UzVS” dated November 3, 2020 No 684, the first venture fund with a charter capital of 15 billion soums was established in our country.

Indeed, one of the most important areas is the commercialization of scientific developments and their introduction into production in several formats:

- On the basis of a new system of commercialization of scientific developments with the participation of the trio “scientist-entrepreneur bank” 19 developments were commercialized for 22.3 billion soums,
- The portal “customer-researcher-investor” was launched, more than 529 developments and 167 problems were registered. Negotiations were held with the participation of 10 authors of innovative projects included in the portal database, as well as local and foreign investors. Currently, work has begun on the implementation of 3 developments.

Indeed, the annual International Week of Innovative Ideas – InnoWeek is also important for the development of innovative entrepreneurship, and many foreign companies are interested in this process every year (more than 20 foreign countries in 2018, 257 foreign representatives from 96 organizations among 34 countries in 2019 attended). In particular, Memorandums of cooperation with companies from South Korea, Turkey, Armenia, Israel, Poland, Russia, China and India worth a total of 109.5 million USD investment agreements were signed during the week. In the framework of InnoWeek.uz – 2019 in cooperation with the Organization of Islamic Cooperation for the first time was held the international robotics competition “The Frist OIC Robotics Challenge”. It was attended by 160 foreign participants from 24 countries. This innovative field has shown its effectiveness despite the quarantine in 2020. In InnoWeek.uz 2020 online platform <https://www.innoweek.uz/> was visited by more than 22,500 observers from 86 countries, which are 5,599 watched the exhibition.

Therefore, it is also important to pay special attention to rejuvenate science and intensify the work on supporting the initiatives of talented youth, ensure the international competitiveness of science in the country as well as further strengthen the capacity of existing scientific institutions and develop their innovative potential. The Youth Academy and the Fund for Support of talented Youth under the Ministry of Innovative Development were established with a fund of 3.8 billion soums. Until now, the number of members of the Youth Academy in Uzbekistan has reached 1,800. In the regions of the country, 15 leaders were elected and 83 projects are being implemented by young talented people.

As a continuation of this work, there is a plan to gradually establish “Youth Technopark” in 13 areas of Uzbekistan. The purpose is to support young people of the regions in their interest in innovation and technological knowledge. Therefore, the first international robotics competition was organized between

the member states of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, the International Robotics Challenge and the RoboCUP television competition are of great interest for youths of all ages. The winners of the competition were given the opportunity to participate in the Asian Science Camp in China and to enter the Polytechnic University of Turin in Tashkent. The winners were awarded cash prizes in the amount of 21 thousand US dollars.

The integration of education and innovation, science and industry is a step-by-step process and its first step is to understand the innovative ecosystem, prepare the legal framework for its creation and its participants on human resources. Another important task is to build educational standards on the basis of integration of knowledge and science, involve young people in the development of science, direct fundamental research to innovative scientific activities, and increase knowledge on the commercialization of new developments. In this regard, the fact that the state has begun to act as a general customer, rather than a general inspector, shows that there is a healthy environment in this process that works on the path of development is carried out on the basis of equality.

Today's world is developing very dynamically, current innovation may be outdated tomorrow, so the strategic task for Uzbekistan is to develop science in a forward-looking way, implement hi-tech and integrate education, science and industry in a way that guarantees future success. All this plays an important role in achieving the goals of Uzbekistan at a new level.

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Religious Relations in the Philosophy of Jalaliddin Rumi

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Annotation. *In this article Jaloliddin Rumi's thoughts on science and his call for people to study. The Thoughts of the Mutafakkir also contain the views on the importance of acquiring knowledge.*

Key words: *Science, wisdom, state, humility, spiritual heritage.*

It is well known that in the Middle Ages, the science of science developed in Movarounnahr and Khurasan. In particular, the science of Sufism developed rapidly. It is noteworthy that the main reason for the rapid development of this science is that the people of Sufism concentrate on understanding human essence in believing in Allah. The great scholar of the great East, Jalal al-Din Rumi, is also one of the most outstanding and famous scholars of his time. Aside from studying and understanding the philosophical and philosophical views of Jaloliddin Rumi, we begin to adopt a number of actual issues of philosophy. In the philosophical views of Jaloliddin Rumi, many issues of gnoseology, ontology, dialectics, ethics and aesthetic theories and logic have been solved.

His attitude towards science and enlightenment in Jalaluddin Rumi's scientific heritage is particularly striking. One of the main ideas leading to Rumi's philosophical views is that there is a certain basis for everything in existence. Therefore, the basis of knowledge is knowledge. Rumi refers to learning, learning, learning, and research as one of the basic characteristics of man. Thus, knowing the universe, knowledge and enlightenment are shaped by thinking. Therefore, knowing the universe is the foundation of all good and society, and the idea that a person who understands each one of his own self is the one who takes the lead in the view of the individual.

According to Rumi, there is another food besides eating and sleeping. This is science. Human beings often forget about this food and work day and night for material food. It is not always possible for human beings to acquire knowledge. It is possible to use this opportunity effectively. Science is infinite. As human beings learn and learn, knowledge remains a part of the river. Science does not come, it is wanted.

The wise say: "There is a great deal of knowledge in the world and a person's life is limited. So, do not worry about having all the knowledge, but you can not do it all. You do not have the patience and the life to do so. Take what you need amongst the sciences, and choose the one that suits your purpose of life so that you can read it carefully and learn what you know to fit into a stone's scroll and be able to achieve the happiness of the two worlds."

Imam al-Ghazali compared the ignorant heart to a place where it was not cultivated. They will not benefit from both of them. "Knowledge and wisdom are the food of the heart. If the heart is deprived of knowledge and wisdom for three days, it will die ", says the mystic.

Jalaliddin Rumi has the following wisdom: "Work in the knowledge that the world is behind you". When a person becomes mature in spiritual maturity, when there is knowledge, there is reason. A knowledgeable person will enjoy all the blessings of the world due to his knowledge and potential. If the human being is knowledgeable, both the state and the government are waiting for him.

The blessed hadith-i-sherifs state as follows: "Be a scientist, or be a scholar, or be a listener to the knowledge or to be a believer. Fifth (the enemy of knowledge) and you will perish."

Mevlana Rumi writes in the 6th book of Masnavi Spirituality: "It is better to sleep well and to worship without knowledge".

Яхшидир тоатдин олим уйқуси,

Чунки бедорликни билгай билгиси. (6 - 3889 - байт)

Engaging in science is primarily of spiritual enlightenment. When it comes to spiritual enlightenment. When it comes to the sphere he likes, it is spiritual prosperity in the process of reading his favorite artistic or scientific work. According to Mevlana Rumi, science revives the mind and saves the minds of the people. Science is an infinite sea, its mold does not look. The scholars of science are like diving. The heart of the heart never learns to acquire knowledge. The Sacred Caliphate of Allah is one of the commandments of Allah, there are two, and never will be satisfied: One is a taliban and one is a world. In the commentary of this hadith, Rumi mentions the following lines:

Толиб уд – дунё ва тавфиротиҳо,

Толиб ул – илм ва тадбиротиҳо. (6- 3895 байт)

If we analyze the above-mentioned by-order philosophical aspect, the world wishes the pursuit of what it wishes - the measure it wants. The heart that burns with eagerness to learn will find its way in any case, and it will always serve its interests. Yahya ibn Khalid said to his son, "Learn all sorts of knowledge. An enemy of what he does not know. I do not want you to be an enemy of some kind of science! "

Man always considers himself intelligent and knowledgeable. But one should not forget that there are always people who are more knowledgeable than ever before.

The desire to learn is not limited to age. It is not declared in the hadith-i-sherifs that searching for knowledge from cradle to tomb is necessary. As in all areas, getting a science also has its own challenges and difficulties. A person who endures these difficulties will gain knowledge and gain a reputation among the people. Those who are given to it will not be able to gain knowledge. Because they enjoy material advantages. Continuity, especially in the pursuit of knowledge, is recognized as one of the most important conditions for acquiring knowledge.

"Science is to know yourself. You do not know what it's trying to do? "Said the great Turkish poet Yunus Emro. Knowledge is also to know yourself at the same time. Scholarship is not a matter of being aware of the universe and the human being, and not to be mistaken. The light that is poured out in the heart of knowledge. Science is the key to unlocking the problems of life and society. Knowledge - language, drowsiness. Science has changed over the centuries. Periods and times are vividly differentiated and limited. The way to man's reach to the universe is the path of knowledge.

It can be said that the great thinker Mevlana Jaloliddin Rumi's scientific research and study of philosophical doctrine, which has left a rare spiritual heritage, serves as a worthy spiritual heritage in the implementation of new and sustainable methods of man's spiritual and moral perfection.

Rumi is a virtuous person when knowledge comes from the heart. Its creator is the creator. Knowledge is like a trust, and it must also be fulfilled. This task comes about by following it and sharing the share. A person achieves the level of humility by knowledge. A person who is proud of his knowledge is like a painting without painting. For this reason, Mawlana Rumi says that the essence of science is to be embodied in the heart. A heart filled with knowledge leads one to humility. The knowledge of the heart is the light of reason.

International Harmony is the Main Effecting Factor of Social Stability

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Abstract. *The article raises and discusses the issues of the proper understanding and interpretation of the fundamental nature of the reforms carried out in the cultural, economic, political, and social humanitarian spheres, that are considered to be the most crucial components of sustainable development. Also, it makes the remarks on the positive solution of ethnic problems occurring in our society.*

A key tenet of the extensive changes being implemented in Uzbekistan is the protection of human rights and interests. The leader of our country Shavkat Mirziyoev states “It is obvious to us all that we cannot envision human interests in isolation from the peace of the nation, the atmosphere of reciprocal respect, generosity, kindness and harmony in our society. This is all our priceless wealth, and it is our sacred duty to protect it like an apple of our eye” [1].

A stable and unifying strategy has been developed in our country from the early years of our independence; this initiative has been greatly supported by a number of different nations and serves as a symbol of solidarity for the members of various ethnicities who reside on the territory of Uzbekistan. According to our President Sh. Mirziyoev, Uzbekistan does not engage in political rivalry with other nations; on the contrary, it promotes the concepts of unity and solidarity through further strengthening friendly and neighborly relations with them. According to the Holy Qur’an “All Muslims are brothers without a doubt” [2]. Allah is the one who has established brotherhood between them. The kinship bond He makes cannot be untied. [3] The issue of strengthening international harmony and cooperation is considered one of the most crucial and concurrently essential in the political life of our country. Additionally, a rational policy is being developed to effectively address the ethnic problems in our society.

There are no legal restrictions on the number of religious organizations that may operate in the Republic of Uzbekistan or certain time for their existence. The development of the noble human qualities e.g., unity, religious tolerance, solidarity etc. ingrained in the mental character of the Uzbek people, has a long history. It dates back to the beginning of human evolution. Central Asia was regarded as the birthplace of civilization, and for this reason a lot of craftsmen, scientists, jewelers, and traders from other countries frequently visited it, and majority of them settled in these lands. As a result of developing friendly relations with the representatives of many nations and peoples, the idea of interethnic harmony has therefore taken on a more active role in our daily social life. The main focus of today’s progression in our country is adherence to our eastern values and traditions, persistent continuation of democratic reforms, and the goal of building a civilized, free and prosperous state. Different religious beliefs will always exist in our country as long as there are representatives from different nationalities and human communities living here. Particularly, the rights of citizens living in our country and believing global and national faiths such as Christianity, Buddhism, Baha’i, Ayurveda, Krishna etc. are being controlled and protected by the state through responsible institutions and organizations. There are now no barriers in our country preventing people of different religions from openly and pressure-free celebrating their religious rituals and holidays. On the initiative of the first President of Uzbekistan I. Karimov religious holidays of other faiths, such as Easter, Christmas, Purim, Hanukkah, etc. have been celebrated by the public for several years alongside our national holidays, such as Eid al-Adha and Ramadan Eid etc. Such factors may serve

as a bright example of glorification of our universal values such as tolerance, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance in the stable policy of Uzbekistan. The Council was established for the purpose of promoting and supporting the activities of various religious denominations in the Republic of Uzbekistan, establishing cooperation with various religious organizations on the basis of the principles of religious tolerance, and encouraging interreligious harmony and unity. Paying attention to religious activities, that is considered to be the primary source of knowledge, culture, spirituality, and morality, and promoting and upholding the concepts of religious tolerance is crucial for maintaining the tenets of peace and stability in the social life of the society. International harmony is based on international friendship. It is the concept expressing the fact that the representatives of different ethnicities coexist peacefully and cooperatively without encountering any conflicts. Interethnic harmony is sometimes referred to the spiritual basis for interethnic respect, generosity, friendship, and solidarity between people of different nationalities and peoples who coexist in one community and strive to achieve a common goal. The basis for the development of ancient values is not to lose the aims of common good goals between the nations.

The representatives of many nationalities have been living peacefully and in harmony since ancient times. For centuries there haven't been any inter-national conflicts between them. Since ancient times, our people have shown universal human qualities such as tolerance, hospitality, forgiveness, and respect for other people's traditions and beliefs. International harmony is a universal value that determines the national development of regions and countries where people with different backgrounds live together, and serves as a guarantee of peace and stability.

During the years of the war, Uzbek hospitality and tolerance were particularly striking. Over a million people, including 200,000 children, were evacuated to Uzbekistan at that time. The Uzbek people treated and raised orphans of different nationalities as if they were their own offspring. For instance, the family of Shoakmad Shomakhmudov from Tashkent set a high example for humanitarianism. During the Second World War Shoakmad Shomakhmudov and his young wife Bakhri Akramova adopted and educated children of different ethnicities. In a multi-ethnic country like Uzbekistan, harmonizing the interests of different nationalities and ensuring harmony among them is one of the key components of the development. The growth of other nations and countries, as well as the situations and opportunities in the whole world, are the main factors that influence a nation's perspective. If there isn't peace, tranquility, stability, solidarity, and equal relations among the peoples living side by side in the world, and especially in the neighboring countries none of them will be able to guarantee its bright future.

The emphasis on interethnic cooperation creates the basis for people living in Uzbekistan and trying themselves in a variety of professions and being aware of traditions and customs. This directly contributes to the growth and enrichment of spiritual values across the country. At present, our state is paying close attention to the issues relating to the preservation of national traditions and values of different nations and peoples, as well as their further growth and enrichment.

Today, our secondary schools provide education in seven different languages, including Uzbek, Karakalpak, Russian, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, Kazakh, and Tajik, while the media has become available for people in ten languages, representing different ethnicities residing in Uzbekistan.

Today, when the threat of the coronavirus pandemic is causing serious problems on a global scale, it is crucial to maintain unity and confidence in the successful outcomes of the reforms we have started, taking into account the fact that we are one of the multi-ethnic nations, considering the possibility of raising the risk of inter-ethnic conflicts in the area where multi-ethnic peoples live and operate. In Uzbekistan, the population's multi-ethnicity is viewed as a favourable factor of socio-economic development.

Uzbekistan's reputation in the international arena is increasing due to maintaining social and economic stability, and fostering harmonious inter-religious and inter-ethnic relations. To be very specific, state educational institutions in our country offer teaching in seven different languages. Newspapers and periodicals are published in more than ten different languages, while the Uzbek television and radio company broadcasts its programs in twelve different languages. There are 138 national cultural institutions under the patronage of the Committee of International Relations and Friendship with Foreign

Countries, as well as about 2,300 religious organizations belonging to 16 denominations. In this respect, a comprehensive, deeply-thought policy and practical measures are actively implemented with a focus on fostering inter-ethnic and inter-religious harmony. First and foremost, particular focus was placed on ensuring equal rights and freedom of citizens regardless of their gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, faith, personal and social status and their equality before the law. Equal rights of citizens, social justice, the rule of law, and mutual respect for cultural, linguistic, and religious values, traditions, and customs of different nations and peoples are some of the guiding principles of the official policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan carried out in this area.

Citizens can participate in public and state building thanks to the constitutional assurances, regardless of their gender, ethnicity, nationality, language, religion, or socio-economic origin. It is important to note that the Republic of Uzbekistan conforms completely with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and other international legal and regulatory documents in its strategy to promote inter-national and inter-religious harmony. The fundamental objective of the modern state is to ensure the unity and stability of the society as well as effective protection of human rights and freedom. In this sense, our main law, the Constitution, serves as both a high-level political-legal framework that directs societal and governmental development and a crucial foundation that guarantees a decent life for every citizen living in our country.

In conclusion, it should be highlighted that establishing friendly relations with the representatives of other nationalities that reside in our country and showing high respect towards them would help to rise Uzbekistan's prestige in the international arena. Shavkat Mirziyoev, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, at present is particularly concerning with the development of socio-economic sector of our country. In this process, all necessary conditions have been created for the representatives of different nations and peoples living in Uzbekistan to live freely and legally operate in their fields. All these aspects demonstrate how universal human values such as tolerance, solidarity and unity etc. have been exalted in our country.

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Professional Training of Future Primary School Teachers in the Field of ICT

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Annotation. *This article describes the change in the requirements for the professional training of primary school teachers as a result of the emergence of new processes related to informatization, integration, technologization, etc. in education.*

Key words: *primary school teachers, competence, respondent, information and communication technologies, professional competence, questionnaire, pedagogical observation, conversation.*

The consistent modernization of the entire educational system is associated with general trends in World Development, one of which necessitates the transition to a post-industrial and informational society. The main stage of this transition process involves not only the active use of computer technologies in the educational process, but also the informatization of education, the management of educational institutions and the educational system as a whole, the creation of an infrastructure that provides the process of informatization, which is associated with the introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT)

A new qualitative level of vocational education leads to a change in the requirements for professional training of a specialist in the conditions of informatization of Education, which, of course, includes professional training in the field of ICT. And these changes also affect the professional training of future teachers.

Analysis of state educational standards of higher professional education in the specialty of pedagogy made it possible to draw conclusions about the fact that along with the daily professional tasks of the teacher, there are goals and objectives such as the ability to use modern scientifically based methods, methods and means of teaching subjects, including technical means of teaching, information and computer technology.

Of particular importance today is the first teacher of children, that is, the primary school teacher, in the formation of an adequate perception of the modern world by a child, his readiness for a big life in an informed society.

In a modern informatized society, the effective organization of the educational process in primary school is no less important than the professionalism of the first teacher, the quality of the technical means used in the course process and the content of computer programs. V. K. Vlasova noted that "it is necessary to improve the qualifications of specialists who are able to qualitatively teach primary school students the basic subjects prescribed in the school curriculum using new information technologies, as well as introduce children to the complex world of modern computer science. These specialists should be well versed in child psychology, master the methodological methods of teaching school-age children, and become mature specialists in the field of Information Technology."

However, in the modern educational space, which is in harmony with informatization processes, many unresolved problems are still visible, including the problems of using ICT tools in the professional activities of primary school teachers.

The mandatory minimum of the subject "the use of modern information and communication technologies in education in the educational process" is as follows:

1. The main concepts and definitions of the field of science - informatization of Education.
2. Goals and objectives of the use of information and communication technologies in education.
3. Information and communication technologies in the implementation of models of information and information activities in education.
4. Information and communication technologies in increasing the cognitive activity of students.
5. Information and communication technologies in the implementation of the system of control, assessment and monitoring of educational achievements of students.
6. Methods of analysis and examination of electronic software and methodological and technological tools in educational purposes.
7. Methodological aspects of the use of information and communication technologies in the educational process.

The analysis of the target component, as well as the content of the educational and methodological implementation of the process of professional training of future primary school teachers in the field of ICT, was carried out on the basis of educational programs and educational and methodological complexes developed in the section of the subjects mentioned above.

The following goals and objectives were set for teaching the subject "mathematics and informatics": "the unity and interdependence of mathematics and Computer Science in the minds of students, the formation of their significance in the conditions of the formation of a modern informatized society", "teaching students theoretical knowledge and practical skills in mathematics and Computer Science in order to freely operate in modern information, formation of the idea of mathematical modeling and the introduction of information theory", "familiarization of students with the basic concepts of mathematics and informatics, mathematical methods, information methods and tools used in the humanities; study of modern information technologies, trends in their development, the formation of practical information processing skills in students, the use of mathematical methods and information technologies in educational and; "The ability to form the foundations of theoretical knowledge in mathematics and computer science, necessary to solve everyday problems encountered in the student's professional activities, and, using the knowledge and skills mastered in the field of Informatics and mathematical competence, to eliminate the typical problems of professional activity corresponding to his qualifications", etc.

Analysis of educational and methodological support in the section of disciplines aimed at professional training of future primary school teachers in the field of ICT determined the orientation of the content of general professional orientation and materials on the formation of knowledge and skills in the subject "Informatics and ICT".

There is no information about the narrow specialization of the professional activities of future specialists in the field of primary education.

Conclusions:

This article describes the change in the requirements for the professional training of primary school teachers as a result of the emergence of new processes related to informatization, integration, technologization, etc. in education.

Based on the existing work of modern scientists, a specific theoretical understanding of the problem, an analysis of the educational and methodological support of the professional training of future primary school teachers in the field of ICT, as well as preliminary studies carried out, the problems of using ICT tools in the professional activities of primary school teachers were described, and the problems

All this made it possible to show contradictions that indicate the importance of the problem under study, and also contributed to the search for ways to solve these contradictions.

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The Interpretation of Ethical Categories in the Works of Al-Farabi

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Annation. *There is no doubt that Eastern culture, philosophy, and the philosophies of ancient social life served as the foundation for the advancement of Western culture, science, and technical achievements. If we go back to history, we can see genius figures such as Al-Khwarizmi, Abu Reikhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina (Avicenna) originated in the East. Among them there were six scholars who had a strong influence on the world civilization e.g., Al-Khwarizmi, Al-Farabi, Akhmad Al-Fargani, Abu Reikhan Beruni, and ibn Sina, all five representatives of the East were born in Uzbekistan; however, one of them Ibn Rushd (Averroes) was of the Spanish-Arab origin.*

Knowledge increases by knowledge and thought leads to another thought. History witnesses a number of places where the scientific discoveries of the world were made, obviously, those places achieved strong links and advancement in different fields. For example, Baghdad and Khorezm that had the status of “Dar al-Hikma” (Hall of wisdom) in the 9-11th centuries, were one of the well-known centers of science development. Another sample may refer to the times of Mirza Ulugbek and Ali-Shir Navai when the main concentration was on the advancement of science.

Many scientists and scholars of both East and West throughout the Renaissance period attempted to understand human behaviour in a social way. They were also eager to know about the nature of human being, to determine the ways to educate and perfect them. With the help of this knowledge they wanted to find the right means of managing the human communities and strive to create rules for justice-based regulations and governance.

The socio-philosophical heritage of our outstanding scholars covers all aspects of human activity. In particular, the works of Abu Nasr Farabi, one of the earliest Islamic intellectuals, preserved up to the present time, can be of high importance for both individuals and the society as a whole. The problem of human and the improvement of society, which is closely tied to this problem, takes a central place in Farabi’s philosophical teachings.

Farabi’s famous treatises such as “*The Attainment of Happiness*” (“*Kitab at-tanbih ala sabil as-sa’ada*”), “*The Civil Politics, The Political Regime*” (“*Kitab as-siyasi al madaniyya*”), and especially “*The Virtuous City*” (“*Arsu ahli madinatul-fazila*”) serve as valuable heritage leading to human happiness.

The great thinker states: “Happiness is such a goal that it can be attained via virtuous deeds such as acquiring knowledge, studying different arts (e.g., jobs, handcrafts etc.) and doing various activities worthy of the acquired knowledge and skills.” In this context, the term “art” refers to a very wide spectrum of efforts occurring in the society. First of all, it is necessary to acquire and master knowledge about beauty and goodness in order to educate people on the path to happiness. Knowing the truth and having verified and accurate knowledge is the main goal of philosophy. “The art (science) that aims at achieving beauty and goodness is called philosophy or, in a broad sense, wisdom” says Farabi in his book “*The Virtuous City*.”

In his work “*Aphorisms of the Statesman*” (“*Kitab fusus al-madaniyya*”), the scholar says the following about the qualities of a perfect person: “Human body tends to be healthy and sick, the same qualities are equally relevant to human’s soul (nafs). The harmony between the internal condition of the soul and its

numerous components is an expression of the well-being of the soul. This, in turn, makes it possible for someone to constantly do virtuous and noble deeds and possess impeccable manners.”

Farabi thinks about not only spiritual, but also physical development of a person. The scholar’s teachings lay a strong emphasis on the human problem and the issues related to perfecting the society, establishing a virtuous society, and developing certain strategies to open the doors of happiness to a person.

According to the thinker human virtue is not only an abstract concept with a certain content, but also a unique moral trait measured by practical actions on the path to spiritual perfection of a person. Virtue is a clear manifestation of a person’s efforts to pursue beauty and goodness. The scholar defines virtue as the following: “It is a set of internal (moral) traits that motivate a person to do good deeds and display excellent behavior. Passions that encourage a person to do bad and evil deeds are called beastliness (razolat), they are the expressions of a person’s flaws or imperfections.”

Farabi makes a distinction between wisdom and justice: according to the scholar, a state governor who does not possess these two qualities risks destroying the country. His moral ideal is the image of a perfect person. A perfect person is a mature man with active mind. It is a master who has a high thinking ability and shows the way to happiness with the skill of educating people science and art.

The works of Farabi were widely read throughout the globe in the 12th and 13th centuries after being translated into Latin, ancient Jewish, Persian, and later other languages. Many libraries and institutions across the world keep the copies of the works duplicated in recent centuries. At the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Beruni in Tashkent one can find 107 treatises of the Eastern philosophers, including “*The Collection of Manuscripts of Judges*” (“*Majmuat rasoil al-hukamo*”) that constitutes of 16 treatises in the Arabic language. This unique manuscript is very significant in studying the works of the scholar. Farabi’s treatises included into the collection were partially translated into Uzbek and published in 1975.

Farabi was renowned as a great scientist in his time. There are various stories and legends about him created by the peoples of the East. The scientists of the medieval period such as Ibn Khallikon, Ibn al-Qifti, Ibn Abi Usabi’a, and Bayhaqi studied the works of the scholar and developed his concepts and ideas in their works. The works of Al-Farabi were specifically examined by ibn Rushd, who also added his own commentaries on them (e.g., “*Al-Farabi’s opinions on syllogism*”, “*Explanations of the propositions expressed in Abu Nasr’s work on logic*”, “*Al-Farabi, in particular, various commentaries on his “Organon” etc.*). The formation of his philosophical doctrine, known as Averroism, was initially associated with the teachings of Farabi and Ibn Sina. Averroism was widely spread as an advanced direction representing scientific advances and had an impact on the worldview of many advanced thinkers and intellectuals of the Renaissance period.

Progressive humanity respects Al-Farabi’s heritage and deeply studies his works. Specific contributions to the study of the scholar’s heritage have been made by a number of European scientists such as B.M. Schrenschneider, Carra de Vaux, T.W. Buhr, R. Hammond, R. de Erlange, F. Deterici, G. Farmer, N. Rishar, G. Ley etc. and the Eastern scientists such as Nafisi, Umar Farrukh, Turker, M. Mahdi and others. In the following years, several studies and works dedicated to Farabi’s works and teachings were created. The moral views and teachings of the thinker today serve as a model for educating the young generation and the development of the scope of the reforms being carried out in our country.

Виртуал Технологияларнинг Таълим Жараёнидаги Аҳамияти

Raximov Farux Boltayevich

BuxDPI, Harbiy talim fakulteti dotsenti

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada virtual технологиялар асосида нофилологик таълим йўналишлари талабаларининг инглиз тилидаги билимларини оширишида онлайн репетиторлик ва яққа дарсларни ташкил этиш мақсадга мувофиқдир.*

Kalit so'zlar: *замонавий таълим, инновацион технологиялар, мобил телефон, интерфаол, видео, телевидение, видеотақдимотлар, филмлар, виртуал технология.*

Замонавий таълим жараёнида инновацион технологиялар, андроид операцион тизимга эга бўлган мобил телефонлар ва ҳоказоларнинг жадал ривожланаётган давридамиз. Ушбу воситалар масофа ва вақтдан қатъий назар мулоқот қилувчилар ўртасида мувоффақиятли ўзаро ҳамкорлик (мулоқот) учун шарт-шароитлар яратиш, тезкор маълумот алмашинувига қулай имконият яратмоқда. Ҳозирги пайтда алоқа воситаларини синтез қилиш учун тўғридан-тўғри оғзаки мулоқот (юзма-юз), матн (босма, қўлёзмалар), аудио-визуал воситалар (видео, телевидение, видеотақдимотлар, филмлар), компьютер дастурлари, ахборот-коммуникация технологиялари асос қилиб олинмоқда [1]. Мулоқот воситалари қуйидаги параметрлар асосида таснифланади: ўзаро мулоқотда қатнашувчилар сони; интерфаоллик даражаси (мулоқот қилувчиларининг фикрлари мавжудлиги); алоқанинг синхронизацияси-асинхронлиги (тезкор кечиктирилган тесқари реакция); хабарни ёзиб олиш, кейинчалик такрорлаш ва ўзгартириш имконияти; хабарни қайта ишлашнинг мураккаблиги (махсус техник воситалардан фойдаланиш, харажатлар, меҳнат харажатлари ва бошқалар); мулоқот иштирокчиларининг ижтимоийлашув даражаси[2]. Тўғридан-тўғри оғзаки мулоқот сўзловчи ва тингловчи ўртасидаги ўзаро таъсирнинг кўплаб турларини ўз ичига олади. Юзма-юз мулоқотнинг ижобий 47 хусусиятлари, масалан, саволлар, кизиқиш уйғотиш, илгари сурилган ва қарши кўрсатмалар ва ҳоказолар шаклида эришиладиган синхрон ва мулоқотнинг интерактивлигини ўз ичига олади. Оғзаки мулоқотнинг муваффақияти иштирокчилар сонига боғлиқ: уларни сони қанчалик кўп, тингловчиларнинг жавобларини бошқариш қанчалик қийин бўлса, интерфаоллик шунчалик заиф бўлади [3]. Барчамизга маълумки, маърузалар кўп сонли тингловчилар аудиториясига мўлжалланган, аммо маърузачи ва тингловчи ўртасидаги мулоқот чегараланганлигини ҳисобга олсак ўзаро мулоқот жараёнида янги билимларни яратиш ўз самарасини бермайди ва амалда эгаллаб бўлган билимларни пассив ўтказиш учун самаралироқ. Узлуксиз таълим жараёнида виртуал тушунчаси кенг маънода қўлланилмоқда. Масалан виртуал таълим, виртуал технологиялар, виртуал хотира, виртуал синф ва х.к. Бугунги кунда таълим сифатини ошириш мақсадида жараёнида виртуал технологиялардан фаол фойдаланилаётгани ҳеч кимга сир эмас. Бу эса таълим жараёнига замонавий АКТ воситаларини кўпроқ жорий этилишини талаб қилади. Талабаларнинг таълим жараёнида виртуал технологиялари ёрдамида матн билан ишлашни, тасвирий объектларни ва маълумотлар базасини яратишни, электрон жадваллардан фойдаланишни ўрганади. Дарсларда виртуал технологияларининг қўлланилиши ўқишга бўлган мотивациясини, талабаларнинг қизиқувчанлигини, таълим самарадорлигини оширади. Бедрул Хан томонидан таклиф этилган электрон таълим концепциясида саккизта: педагогик, технологик, педагогик интерфейс дизайни, баҳолаш, бошқариш, ресурсларни қўллаб-қувватлаш, этик асослар, асбоб ускуналар жиҳати мавжуд [4]. 48 Шу билан бирга, таъкидлаш лозимки, технологиялар шу қадар тез ривожланиб, бўшлиқни тўлдириб бормоқдаки, ҳатто энг илғор ўқитувчининг ҳам бу жараёнга дархол киришиб кетишга улгурмай қолмоқда. Агар тил таълими ҳақида гапирадиган бўлсак, унда 5 йил олдин дарсликларга CD-гомлар асосий илова сифатида тикиларди, ҳозирда эса бутун дарслик ва унинг барча таркибий қисмлари, жумладан, аудио, видео, ўқитувчи китоби ва

бошқалар унинг ичига киритилган бўлиб, ҳар қандай компьютер ёки планшетда онлайн фойдаланиш, ҳамда дарсга ортиқча нарса олиб киришнинг хожати қолмади, дарсда бор-йўғи гаджет ёки қурилмадан фойдаланиш мумкин бўлиб қолди. Оддий фойдаланувчи учун пайдо бўлган бу технологиялар дарҳол таълимда ўз ўрнини топади. Бу деярли барча технологияларга, ҳатто виртуал технологиялар каби футуристларга ҳам тегишлидир. Google компанияси бир неча йилдан бери таълимда виртуал технологиядан фойдаланиш бўйича тадқиқотлар олиб бормоқда, натижада ўзига хос Google Expeditions иловаси яратилиб, у синфхонадан чиқмасдан жуда кўп жойларга ташриф буюриш имконини беради. Бу улар томонидан ишлаб чиқилган дастур ҳисобланиб, ўз ичига виртуал саёхат қилиш учун 200дан ортиқ саёхат манзиллини камраб олиб, ўз ўрнида у ерларга индивидуал ёки гуруҳ билан саёхат қилиш имконини беради, бу эса ўқув машғулоти учун янада қулай ҳисобланади. Бундай виртуал ташриф таъсири ҳар қандай ўқитувчининг ҳикоя, фотосурат ёки тарихий ёдгорликни кўрсатишининг ўрнини бемалол боса олади, сабаби талаба маълум бир жойга ташрифи орқали уларни виртуал саёхатда жонли солиштириш мумкин. Ушбу дастур кўплаб мамлакат таълим муассасаларида фаол равишда қўлланилиб, география, тарих, маданият, санъат ва бутун дунёвий билимларини бутунлай бошқа даражага олиб чиқади. Шуни таъкидлаш керакки, ҳозирги замон рақамли авлоди онлайн режимда ишлашлари учун анча қулай бўлганлиги сабабли бу аллақачон «табиий муҳит» бўлиб улгурди, улар технология ичида яшамоқдалар. Нозирги замон рақамли авлодининг асосий хусусиятлари орасида АКТ компетенциялари юқори даражада қайд этилади, шунингдек ҳаёти ва ўрганишда технологиядан фойдаланишда юқори мотивация беради, тезкор фикрлаш ва бир вақтнинг ўзида кўп топшириқларни бажариш қобилиятини шакллантириш имконини беради, бу эса виртуал технологияни янада қизиқарли, тушунарли ва самарали бўлишини таъминлайди [5].

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Развитие Химической Промышленности В Республике Узбекистан В Период С 2017 По 2021гг

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается развитие химической промышленности Узбекистана, выявляются основные проблемы и факторы, препятствующие развитию химической промышленности страны. Проанализирован уровень технического развития химических предприятий и отрасли в целом.

Ключевые слова: Промышленное производство, технологический процесс, химическая отрасль, химическая промышленность.

Химическая промышленность является одной из базовых отраслей промышленности Узбекистана, которая сформировалась исходя из потребностей интенсификации сельскохозяйственного производства, путем создания производств минеральных удобрений.

На сегодняшний день химическая промышленность Узбекистана является одним из базовых сегментов экономики страны, закладывающим основу ее долгосрочного и устойчивого развития. Именно химическая промышленность является крупным поставщиком сырья, различных материалов и работ практически во все отрасли промышленности и серьезно влияет на объемы, направления и эффективность их развития. [5]

В настоящее время такие предприятия, как «Максам-Чирчик», «Фаргоназот» и «Навоиазот» производят азотные удобрения: аммиачную селитру, карбамид и сульфат аммония. Предприятия «Аммофос», «Самаркандкимё» и «Жуконский суперфосфатный завод» производят фосфорсодержащие удобрения, аммофос, суперфосфат, простой аммонизированный суперфосфат, аммоний-сульфофосфат и нитрокальций-фосфат. Кызылкумский фосфорный комбинат поставляет сырье для этих производств. ООО «СПЭлектрохимзавод» производит различные виды химических средств защиты растений.

Большая часть предприятий химической промышленности находятся в составе Государственно-акционерной компании «Узкимёсаноат» (Химическая холдинговая компания), которая объединяет 12 крупных промышленных предприятий, 13 региональных распределительных организаций. Региональные распределительные организации занимаются реализацией химических продуктов в такие сферы, как агропромышленный комплекс, проектные и научно-исследовательские учреждения, транспортно-экспедиторские компании.

В 2017 году согласно стратегии действий по пяти приоритетным направлениям развития Узбекистана в сфере химической промышленности проделаны значительные преобразования. В том числе, в соответствии с постановлением Президента Республики Узбекистан «О мерах по совершенствованию структуры управления АО «Узкимёсаноат» от 12 апреля 2017 года всецело был обновлен состав правления акционерного общества, реорганизованы структуры отделений и аппарат управления химической индустрии.[4]

Программа становления химической промышленности на 2017-2021 годы утверждена постановлением Президента Республики Узбекистан от 23 августа 2017 года. Данный документ предусматривает реализацию 43 инвестиционных проектов, общая стоимость которых составляет

3,1 миллиард долларов, увеличение объемов промышленного производства в 2,4 раза, а их экспорт – в 2,7 раза, увеличение доли локализованной продукции до 42,5 процентов и освоение производства 43 новых видов продукции, формирование более 3,2 тысяч рабочих мест. Для осуществления контроля экспортно-импортной деятельности сферы, обеспечения прозрачности внешнеторговых процессов, а главное, увеличения объемов экспорта путем расширения географии реализации химической продукции на внешнем рынке для последующего повышения ее конкурентоспособности.[1,2]

Проводимые масштабные реформы позитивно сказываются на химической отрасли. Впрочем, еще ждут своего решения, накопившиеся за предыдущие годы системные проблемы в отрасли химической промышленности. Следовательно, промышленные предприятия по производству минеральных удобрений оказались в тяжелом финансовом положении.

Также причиной возникновения недостатков в системе взаиморасчетов в сфере сельского хозяйства является поверхностный подход к финансированию, как сказал Президент Республики Узбекистан.

Затраты, связанные с минеральными удобрениями для нужд сельского хозяйства, не покрываются. В результате этого химические предприятия ограничены в платежеспособности за потребление природного газа, электроэнергии, фосфатного сырья, серной кислоты и других видов товаров и услуг, и, следовательно, увеличивается их кредитная задолженность.

В связи с этим, начиная с 2018 года, поставку минеральных удобрений потребителям планируется осуществлять посредством биржевых торгов при посредничестве «Единого агента», организованных при АО «Узкимёсаноат».[3]

Вместе с тем имеются недостатки в вопросах снижения себестоимости минеральных удобрений и повышения рентабельности предприятий отрасли. В частности, 67 процентов стоимости азотных удобрений составляют затраты на энергию. Предприятия «Ферганаазот», Дехканабадский завод калийных удобрений, Кокандский суперфосфатный завод, компании «Аммофос-Максам» и «Максам-Чирчик» заканчивают 2017 год с низкой рентабельностью, а предприятие «Навоиазот» с убытками. В таких условиях предприятия полностью ограничены в формировании собственных оборотных средств и вынуждены решать проблемы за счет привлечения кредитов под 16-18 процентов годовых.

В связи с этим АО «Узкимёсаноат» поручено разработать совместно с соответствующими министерствами и ведомствами программу конкретных мероприятий по снижению себестоимости производства химической продукции и повышению ее конкурентоспособности в 2018-2019 годах.

Износ основного технологического оборудования является проблемой, которая требует значительного внимания. Так как в результате, из-за отсутствия средств оборудования, которая остается без текущего и капитального ремонта, нарушается технологический процесс.

Исходя из этого, имеется необходимость разработки отраслевого плана по проведению капитальных ремонтов, как отметил глава Республики Узбекистан.

В ходе рассмотрения, вопросов, которые касаются обеспечения сельского хозяйства фосфорными удобрениями, было отмечено, что существующая потребность в объеме 639,6 тыс. тонн обеспечена всего лишь на 25процентов. В связи с этим было предусмотрено, что в 2019 году за счет модернизации действующих мощностей увеличить производство до 177 тыс. тонн, а в 2021 году – до 550 тыс. тонн за счет строительства нового комплекса по производству фосфорных удобрений.[2]

Ни одна современная отрасль индустрии не может обойтись без продукции нефтехимического и химического сегмента. Здесь важно отметить, что отечественная химическая продукция экспортируется более чем в 30 стран. Сегодня данная отрасль Узбекистана занимает 8-е место в

мире по производству азота, фосфора и калия. Несомненно, выпуск вышеупомянутых новых видов продукции увеличит экспортный потенциал республики.

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Diplomatik Atamalarning Lug'atini Tuzish Tamoillari

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Annotatsiya. Har birimiz o'z sohamizdan kelib chiqib, kerakli ma'lumotni tez va oson topish uchun lug'atlarga murojaat qilamiz yoki notanish atamaga duch kelganimizda ham lug'atlarga tayanamiz. Ushbu maqola diplomatiya terminlari va terminologiyasini o'rganilayotgan tillardagi terminologiyaning ishlashi va uning o'ziga xos jihatlariga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: termin, tadqiqot, diplomatik, xalqaro, semantika, siyosiy, lingvistik, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, leksik, axborot.

Terminologiya tushunchasi. Diplomatik va siyosiy atamalarning mohiyati va ma'nosini ochishdan oldin, boshqa manbalar nuqtai nazaridan "termin" va "terminologiya" so'zlarining mohiyati va ma'nosiga qisqacha ekskursiya qilib o'tsak. Termin (lotincha terminusdan - "chegara, chegara") - bu kontseptsiya va uning alohida sohadagi boshqa tushunchalar bilan aloqasini aniq va aniq ko'rsatadigan so'z yoki ibora. Bu atamalar bu sohaga xos bo'lgan ob'ektlar, hodisalar, ularning xossalari va munosabatlarining ixtisoslashtirilgan, cheklovchi belgilari bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Umumiy so'z birikmalaridan farqli o'laroq, ko'pincha ko'p ma'noli va hissiy ma'noga ega, qo'llanilish doirasidagi atamalar aniq va ifodasizdir. Terminologiya maxsus bilim sohasi sifatida tadqiqotchilar e'tiborini tobora ko'proq jalb qilmoqda. Bu integratsiyalashuv jarayonlari natijasida kelib chiqqan zamonaviy ilmiy bilimlarning xalqaro tabiati va natijada, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy faoliyatning turli sohalarida til to'siqlarini yengish usuli sifatida atamalarni birlashtirish istagi bilan bog'liq. "Termin" tushunchasini semantik nuqtai nazardan aniqlayotganda, tegishli lingvistik birliklarning leksik ma'nosiga bog'liqligi, shuningdek, terminologik foydalanish imkoniyati (alohida so'zlar bilan birga) va so'z birikmalarini hisobga olinadi. ayniqsa, yangi terminologiyalar uchun xosdir. Yangi atama yaratishda, mavjud lingvistik tajribaga asoslanib, kerakli "imo -ishorali" ma'lumotni qidirish, uni maxsus "tilning axborot -terminologik sohasida" aniqlash va bu yo'nalishdagi yangi yutuqlarni bashorat qilish amalga oshiriladi. Yangi atamaning semantik aniqligi lingvistik belgining bir -biriga aniq bog'liqligiga va u uzatgan haqiqatga asoslanadi, shuning uchun chet tillarini, ayniqsa, rivojlangan sanoat bazasi bo'lgan mamlakatlarni jalb qilishning to'g'riligi ko'rinadi. Yangi atamaning shakllanishiga yangi fanlarning vujudga kelishi jarayonlari va boshqa yutuqlar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan tildan tashqari omil katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ayrim hollarda, ekstalingvistik omillar hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, bu atama tushunchani manba tilidan olishiga yordam beradi. Terminlar ma'lum bir atamashunoslik doirasida mavjud bo'ladi, ya'ni ular tilning o'ziga xos leksik tizimiga kiradi, faqat ma'lum bir terminologik tizim orqali. Umumiy til so'zlaridan farqli o'laroq, atamalar kontekstizatsiyalanmagan. Berilgan tushunchalar tizimida bu atama bir ma'noli, tizimli, stilistik jihatdan neytral bo'lishi kerak (masalan, "agreman", "ekzekvatura", "denonsatsiya"). Muayyan adabiy tilning so'z boyligi o'z tarkibida maxsus tushunchalarni ifodalovchi terminologik leksikani u yoki bu darajada qamrab olishi lingvistikada e'tirof etilgan voqelik hisoblanadi.

Lug'atning vazifasi hamda turlari. Lug'atning asosiy vazifasi so'zlarning ma'nolarini tavsiflashdan iborat bo'lib, lug'at tavsiflari yoki talqinlari, iloji bo'lsa, izohlangan so'zning o'zidan kamroq tarqalgan va tushunarli bo'lmagan so'zlardan foydalanmasdan, aniq va tushunarli bo'lishi kerak. Odatda, avval ko'p qo'llaniladigan ma'nolar izohlanadi, keyin esa kamdan-kam uchraydigan ma'nolar izohlanadi. So'zning aniq ma'nosi ko'pincha kontekstga bog'liq bo'lganligi sababli, batafsilroq lug'atlarda so'zlarning turli kontekstlarda qanday ishlatilishiga misollar keltirilgan. Izohlar va foydalanish misollaridan tashqari, lug'atlar lingvistik ma'lumotlarning boy zaxirasini o'z ichiga oladi. Ular so'zlarning to'g'ri yozilishi va talaffuzi, afzal va muqobil talaffuzlar va bir nechta ruxsat etilgan imlolar haqida qabul qilingan ma'lumot manbaidir. Lug'atlarda grammatik ma'lumotlar, so'zlarning etimologiyasi (ularning kelib chiqishi va

tarixiy rivojlanishi), noodatiy yoki shakllanishi qiyin bo'lgan hollarda hosila shakllari, sinonim va antonimlar ham berilishi mumkin. Lingvistik lug'atlarda so'zlarning tavsifi - ularning ma'nosi, qo'llanish shakllari, tuzilish xususiyatlari, mosligi, boshqa tillarning leksik tizimlari bilan bog'liqligi va boshqalar. Normativ lug'atning maqsadi so'zning ma'nosini noto'g'ri tushunish bilan bog'liq bo'lgan so'zlarning noto'g'ri ishlatilishini emas, balki kommunikativ vaziyatga mos kelmaydigan qo'llanishlarni ham istisno qilgan holda, so'zdan foydalanish normasini berishdir. O'z tabiatiga ko'ra izohli lug'atlar umumiy va xususiya bo'linadi. Yuqorida muhokama qilingan izohli lug'atlar umumiy lug'atlardir. Xususiya izohli lug'atning tipik misoli frazeologik lug'atlar bo'lib, ular turli darajadagi idiomatiklikka ega bo'lgan barqaror so'z birikmalari bilan cheklangan. Frazeologik lug'atlarining muhim xususiyati frazeologik birliklar shaklidagi o'zgaruvchanlikni aks ettirish zaruratidir. Dialekt lug'atlari orasida umumiy va mintaqaviy lug'atlar ajralib turadi. Umumiy dialekt so'zlarning lug'atlari ko'p (yoki kamida bir nechta) dialekt va dialektlarning lug'atini o'z ichiga oladi. Etimologik lug'atlar so'zlarning kelib chiqishini tushuntirishga qaratilgan. So'zlarning tarixi va ularning etimologiyasi haqidagi ma'lumotlar ba'zi yirik izohli lug'atlarda keltirilgan. Vaqti-vaqti bilan nashr etiladigan yangi so'z lug'atlari (neologizmlar) tilga yaqinda kirib kelgan so'zlar va so'zlarning yangi ma'nolarini o'z ichiga oladi, ularni tushunish va ishlatish qiyinchiliklarga olib kelishi mumkin. So'nggi paytlarda nutq madaniyati uchun kurashning kuchayishi munosabati bilan, ayniqsa og'ir holatlarda so'zlardan foydalanish normalarini ko'rsatadigan maxsus lug'atlar nashr etilmoqda.

Diplomatik atamalar lug'ati va tuzilishi. Shu o'rinda hamma sohalar kabi diplomatiya tili ham o'z terminlari tizimiga ega ekani, uning lug'at boyligi diplomatik, tarixiy, madaniy, lingvistik, huquqiy va boshqa xil iboralardan tashkil topganini eslatib o'tish lozim. Diplomatiya tili uchun uzun jumlar, iboralar, kirish so'zlari va bog'lovchilarning ko'pligi xos. Diplomatik til rasmiy tildan, xususan, xalqaro siyosat tilidan, jumalistika tilidan, ma'lum darajada badiiy-adabiy tildan ham ancha farq qiladi. Ta'kidlash joizki, diplomatik atamalar asosan lotin, ingliz, fransuz tillarida yaratilgan yoki ular orqali vositachi tillar sifatida kirib kelgan. Har qanday zamonaviy tilda diplomatiya va siyosatga tegishli terminlar faol rivojlanmoqda, shuning uchun insonning diplomatiya va tashqi aloqalar bilan bog'liq aqliy faoliyati natijalari terminlarda ifodalanmoqda, deb taxmin qilish mantiqan to'g'ri. Lug'atdagi atamalarni tanlashda o'zbek tili mezonlariga, til normalariga rioya qilinadi. Lug'at tuzishda sohadan kelib chiqib, lug'atchilikning barcha an'ana va qoidalariga rioya qilishga hamda xalqaro hayotda, siyosatda qo'llanayotgan diplomatik terminlarni imkon qadar to'plashga harakat qilish lozim. Diplomatik terminologiyada, har qanday boshqa fan terminologiyasida bo'lgani kabi, tilshunoslik nuqtai nazaridan ham atamalarning ikki turi mavjud:

1. Bir so'zli so'zlar.
2. Murakkab (ikki so'zli va so'zma-so'z) atamalar.

Diplomatiya, siyosatshunoslik, aniqrog'i, siyosatshunoslik bo'lagi bo'lib, boshqa, unchalik mashhur bo'lmagan va muhim fan - yurisprudensiya bilan, aniqrog'i, xalqaro huquq kabi tarmoq bilan chambarchas bog'liq.

Amaldagi diplomatik terminologiyani ikki turga bo'lish mumkin:

- 1) aniq talqin qilingan siyosiy, diplomatik va umumiy huquqiy xarakterdagi atamalar;
- 2) xalqaro huquqiy atamalar.

Birinchi guruhga siyosiy atamalar kiradi - suverenitet, xalqlar va millatlarning o'z taqdirini o'zi belgilashi, tinchlik, xavfsizlik, urush, tajovuz; diplomatik - diplomatik munosabatlar, diplomatik immunitetlar, konsullik okrugi, xalqaro tashkilotlar;

Ikkinchi guruhga huquqiy - umumiy yuridik - huquqiy norma, huquq manbai, yuridik shaxs, yuridik javobgarlik va boshqalar kiradi. Ularning xalqaro huquqiy talqini lotin iboralarini keltirib chiqardi: davlatlarning suveren tenglik tamoyili, xalqaro xavfsizlik, qonun, tajovuzni xalqaro jinoyat sifatida aniqlash va tajovuzkorlik uchun javobgarlik, diplomatik va konsullik huquqi, xalqaro -huquqiy norma,

xalqaro huquq manbasi, xalqaro -huquqiy shaxslik va boshqalar. Shunisi e'tiborga loyiqki, atamalarni o'rganish uchun juda keng usul va uslubiy bazaga ega bo'lgan holda, diplomatik va xalqaro siyosiy terminologiya to'g'ri o'rganilmagan. Bu yo'nalishdagi ilmiy izlanishlar ko'p tizimli tillarda, tojik tili atrofida asosiy poydevor sifatida ishlatilishi va rolini hisobga olgan holda amalga oshirilishi kerakligini alohida ta'kidlash lozim. Ko'pgina lug'atlar bir nechta funksiyalarni bajaradi va shuning uchun bir nechta sohalarga tegishli. Zamonaviy hayotning tez sur'atlari tilning doimiy o'zgarishlari bilan birga bo'lganligi sababli, lug'atlar zamon talablari asosida yangilanishi kerak. Tez-tez yangilanadigan lug'atlarga yangi so'zlar qo'shilish tartibida kiritilishi kerak.

Xulosa. Ikki davlat o'rtasidagi diplomatik munosabatlarni o'rnatishga doir kelishuvlarda, konsullik munosabatlarini o'rnatishda, shuningdek, davlatning diplomatik vakolatxonalarining konsullik bo'limlari tomonidan amalga oshiriladigan ishlarda diplomatik atamalar va ularning lug'atlariga duch kelamiz. Har qanday tilning so'z boyligi u tarixiy yoki zamonaviy tusda bo'lmasin, insonlar tomonidan tuziladigan rang-barang lug'atlarda ma'lum darajada aksini topadi. Lug'at til so'z boyligini o'zida saqlovchi akkumulyator vazifasini bajaradi. Bugun muayyan tilshunoslikning qay darajada rivojlangani, takomil topgani ayni tilda yaratilgan lug'atlarning turi, miqdori va sifati bilan o'lchanmoqda. Xulosa qilib shuni ta'kidlash joizki, diplomatik terminologiya juda keng lingvistik xususiyatlarga ega. Masalan, diplomatik hujjatlar hujjatning diplomatik atamalardan foydalangan holda tarjimai kabi o'ziga xos xususiyatga ega - tarjimaning haqiqiyliigi, o'ziga xos uslubi va xushmuomalalik, rasmiyatchilik va hokazo. Maqolaning qisqartirilishi kabi xususiyat tufayli biz berilgan boshqa lingvistik xususiyatlarni ochib bera olmaymiz.

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Kamtarlik Badiiy Adabiyotda Konseptual Metafora Sifatida. Jeyn Ostinning “Andisha Va G’urur” Asari Misolida

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Annotatsiya. Metafora asl narsaning biz odatda sezmaydigan yoki hatto muhim deb hisoblamaydigan yangi va qiziqarli xususiyatlarini ochib berishga qodir. Majoziy tildan foydalanish uslubiy rang-baranglikni oshirishdan iborat bo’lib, u Andisha va G’urur asarida ham uning mazmuniga o’zgacha chiroy qo’shadi. Agar o’quvchi ikki xil narsa o’rtasidagi o’xshashlikni tushunsa va kinoya romanda mazax qilish, inson obro’sini tushirish yoki uni ruhiy yaralash uchun mo’ljallangan dialogni hech qanday qiyinchiliksiz tushinishi mumkin. Bunday holatda o’quvchining asardagi voqealarga nisbatan his-tuyg’ulari aniqroq va keskinroq bo’ladi.

Kalit so’zlar: metafora, kamtarlik, konseptual metafora nazariyasi, axloqiy me’yorlar.

Kamtarlik insonni, uning hayotiy mavqeini, shaxsiy fazilatlarini va ijtimoiy xulq-atvorini belgilaydigan sadoqat, qadr-qimmat va or-nomus bilan bir qatorda turli til va madaniy dunyo hamjamiyatlarining qadriyatlar tizimidagi eng muhim elementlardan biri hisoblanadi. Kamtarlikning lingvistik xususiyatlari asosan leksik semantik va kognitiv nuqtai nazardan tavsiflanadi. Jumladan, Mushaeva (2008) kamtarlik “tartibga soluvchi lingvomadaniy tushuncha” deb ta’riflagan. Uning fikricha, kamtarlik so’zlovchi va tinglovchiga o’zini namoyon qilishning axloqiy me’yorlarini saqlashga qaratilgan aqliy birliklar sinfiga kiradi. Hoffman (2016), Villiams (2014) kamtarlik ma’lum bir til va madaniy hamjamiyatning axloqiy talablariga muvofiq shaxsning o’zini o’zi ko’rsatishini tavsiflaydi. Uning tarkibiy xususiyatlari etnik-madaniy, tarixiy va diniy masalalarga bog’liq.

Shevchenko (2011) kamtarlik kommunikativ xulq-atvorning atributiv tartibga soluvchi konsepsiyasi bo’lib, u axloq domenida, asosan uning kichik domenidagi kommunikativ xatti-harakatda tasvirlanganligini da’vo qiladi. Domenni semantik birliklarni tavsiflash mumkin bo’lgan konseptualizatsiyaning izchil sohasi sifatida tushunadigan standart va hisoblash konseptual metafora nazariyalari orasida deb hisoblaydi. Domenlar quyi darajadagi sxematik birlik - tushunchalarni o’z ichiga oladi. (Kovecses, 2017)

Mavhumlik bo’lgan holda, kamtarlik metaforik nomlanish jarayonida aniqroq tushunchalar orqali idrok etiladi. “Standart” konseptual metafora nazariyasida manba domenini (korrelyatsiya) va maqsadli domenni (referent) o’zaro xaritalash (bog’lash) konseptual metaforani keltirib chiqaradi. Shunisi e’tiborga loyiqki, bitta referentning metaforik konsepsiyasida bir nechta korrelyatsiyalar ishtirok etishi mumkin yoki aksincha bo’lishi ham mumkin. Shunga ko’ra, Kövecses “metafora diapazoni”ni, ya’ni ma’lum bir maqsadli domenni (referent) tushunish uchun foydalaniladigan bir nechta manba sohalari (konseptual korrelyatsiyalar) guruhini va metafora doirasini yoki “maqsadli domenlarni, ma’lum bir manbani ajratib turadi degan tushuncha amal qiladi”

Kovecses, shuningdek, argument, baxt va boshqalar kabi mavhum tushunchalarning misollarini taqdim etar ekan, ular maqsadli sohaning bir qator manba sohalari bilan tavsiflanishi natijasida konseptual metaforalar to’plami orqali tavsiflanadi. O’zaro xaritalashning bunday holatlarida “markaziy xaritalash (bog’lash) - bu boshqa xaritalashlardan kelib chiqadigan va manbaning asosiy ma’nosini nishonga qaratadigan xaritadir” deya ta’kidlaydi.

Kikleovich (2017) ta’kidlaganidek, dunyoning lingvistik konstruksiyasini leksik material asosida qayta qurish so’z nominatsiyasidagi referentlar yoki denotatlar va tushunchalarning haqiqatda mavjud bo’lib,

individlar ongida ularning ma'nosi aqliy tasvirlar sifatida mavjud ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Eng so'nggi ko'p tomonli yondashuvlar til, madaniyat va anglash o'rtasidagi interfeysni o'rganib chiqdi (Sharifian, 2017). Kognitiv tilshunoslik konseptualizatsiya sifatida ma'noga e'tibor qaratadi. Sharifian (2017) ta'kidlaganidek, "Madaniy tilshunoslik ochiq ma'noda madaniy asosga ega bo'lgan va tillar xususiyatlarida kodlangan va muloqotda bo'ladigan konseptualizatsiyalarni o'rganadi".

Zamonaviy kognitiv tilshunoslikda metaforik konseptualizatsiya konseptual metafora nazariyasiga asoslanadi (Kövecses, 2002, 2017; Lakoff & Jonson, 1980; Sullivan, 2013 va boshqalar) va o'zaro xaritalash (bog'lash) nazariyasida aniqlangan (Lakoff, 1993, 1993). 245-bet), unga ko'ra manba domenining ma'lum xususiyatlari maqsadli domenning ma'lum xususiyatlariga prognoz qilinadi yoki o'xshatiladi. Ushbu dizaynda aniqlangan maqsad va manba domenlarining umumiy xususiyatlari o'zaro xaritalash (bog'lash) zonasini tashkil qiladi (Lakoff, 1993, 203, 245-betlar). Fauconnier (Fauconnier, 1997, 1-bet) nuqtai nazaridan, o'zaro taqqoslashda ikkita taqqoslanadigan obyektlarning faqat bir nechta xususiyatlari ishtirok etadi.

Metaforaning manba sohalari tasodifiy tanlanmagan; ular til va madaniy hamjamiyat tomonidan oldindan "kelishilgan" maqsadli domenlarning muayyan konseptual ekvivalentlaridir. Shunday qilib, manba sohasi sifatida kamtarlik muntazam ravishda maqsadli domen shaxsidagi ma'lum tushunchalar bilan bog'liq bo'lib, ko'plab konseptual metaforalarni keltirib chiqaradi. Ularning paydo bo'lishi, "kengayish" (Lakoff, 1993, 60-bet) yoki konseptual metaforaning bo'linishi, bir maqsadli tushunchaning manba sohasining turli tushunchalari bilan o'zaro bog'liqligi natijasidir. Xususan, bu maqsadli domen axloqi elementlari va manba domenining shaxsi o'rtasidagi xaritalar to'plamining paydo bo'lishini tushuntiradi, Bu yerda bitta referent kamtarlik yordamchi, mutafakkir, qutqaruvchi va boshqalar bilan bog'lanishi mumkin deb hisoblanadi.

Karasikning fikricha, kamtarlik tushunchasi lingvomadaniy tushunchadir, ya'ni "ongga mansub, madaniyat bilan belgilanadi va tilda obyektivlashadi". Vorkachev ta'biri bilan aytganda esa lingvomadaniy tushuncha milliy va global ma'naviy qadriyatlarni o'zida mujassam etgan. U ma'lum bir jamiyatning axloqiy me'yorlari va bilimlari tizimi mahsuli bo'lib, butun nutq jamoasiga tegishlidir. Yaxshilik, yovuzlik va boshqalar kabi madaniy tushunchalar insoniyatning sivilizatsiya merosini tavsiflaydi va Karasikning fikricha unda "murakkab ko'p o'lchovli jamoaviy aqliy shakllanish bo'lib, unda tushuncha, qadriyat va majoziy tarkibiy qismlar ajralib turadi". Bu esa o'z navbatida ingliz va o'zbeklarning kamtarlik tushunchalari o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik va sezilarli farqlarni ochib beradi.

Xornbi tadqiqotlari davomida "Modesty" [kamtarlik] so'zining ma'nosini tadqiq qilar ekan, lug'atlarda kamtarlik so'zining leksiko-semantik tahlili (Oxford Etymology Dictionary; Oxford Learner's Thesaurus) shuni ko'rsatadiki, kamtarlik ma'nosi quyidagilardan iborat:

- 1) e'tiborni jalb qilishni istamaydigan odamning kamtarona xatti-harakatlarini tavsiflovchi komponentlar;
- 2) o'z qobiliyati, fazilatlarini haqida gapirishdan qochish;
- 3) kamtarona turmush tarzini saqlash;
- 4) yalang'ochlikdan uyalishni his qilish;
- 5) maqtanish niyatida bo'lmagan inson.

Ingliz tilida *MODEST* leksemasi "having moderate self-regard" [o'z-o'zini hurmat qilish] ingliz tilidagi lug'atlarga 1560-yilda kiritilgan. 1590 yilda lug'atga ushbu so'zning yangi ma'nosi – "noto'g'ri yo'lda bo'lmagan, fohisha bo'lmagan ayol" - birinchi navbatda ayollarga nisbatan qo'shilgan bo'lsa, 1600-1610 yildan boshlab, kiyim-kechak, talablar, ehtiyojlar va boshqalarga nisbatan uning lug'aviy ma'nosining bir qismi sifatida qayd etildi.

Turchenkoning (2014) fikricha, ingliz tilida kamtarlik [Modesty] tushunchasi uchta mikro ma'nolarga va ularning kengaytmalariga kiruvchi "Kamtarlik" sohasi leksemalari bilan ifodalanadi:

- “HUMBLE” [Kamsuqum] mikro ma’nosi kengaytmalari bilan “Sheepish” [Ahmoqroq] ma’nosida “bashful, constrained, diffident, meek” (qo’rqinchli, qattiqqo’l, o’ziga qaram, muloyim) va “Unprentious”[O’zboshimchalik] “reserved, cautious, demure, detached, humble, etc.” (e’tiborli, ehtiyotkor, muloyim, o’ziga xos, kamtar va boshqalar);
- “DECENT” [Odobli] mikro ma’nosi kengaytmalari bilan “Unostentatious” [Ko’zga tashlanmaydigan] - decent, delicate, demure, discreet, etc. (odobli, nozik, muloyim, ehtiyotkor va h.k.); “Proper” [Xushxulq] - becoming, chaste, coy, decorous, delicate, quiet, reserved, virtuous, etc. (munosib, iffatli, xushchaqchaq, xushchaqchaq, nozik, sokin, o’zini tuta bilish, odobli va h.k.); “Demure” [Uyatchan yoki Sipo] - chaste, celibate, innocent, prudish, virgin (pok, turmush qurmagan, begunoh, ehtiyotkor, bokira);
- Moderate [O’rtacha, Mo’tadil] mikro ma’nosida “Minor” [Biroz] (yetarli emas, past, maqomi past, yumshoq, kichik va h.k.) va “Low”[Past] ma’nosida (ijtimoiy maqom/professional daraja: past sinf, oddiy, kichik, o’rtacha va h.k.).

“Kamsuqum” va “Odobli” mikro ma’nolarining elementlari “Kamtarlik” konsepsiyasini to’g’ridan-to’g’ri ifoda etadi, “Mo’tadil” elementlari esa insonning axloqiy xususiyati sifatida kamtarlik tushunchasini ifodalamaydi va boshqa tushunchalarni bilvosita tanlash uchun metaforalarning o’zaro munosabatlar zonasini tashkil qiladi.

Ingliz tilidagi kamtarlik tushunchasi “Kamsuqum” va “Odobli” mikro ma’nolaridagi so’zlarning ma’nolariga mos keladigan ikkita bo’shliq bilan tuzilgan. Ular konsepsiya xususiyatlarini belgilaydigan identifikatsiyaning aqliy sxemasi asosida bog’liqlik hosil qiladi.

Madaniyat tushunchasi sifatida “Modesty” (kamtarlik) aniq ijtimoiy-madaniy asosga ega. Sharifianning (2017) fikricha, madaniy tilshunoslik nazariyasi nuqtai nazaridan, kamtarona xatti-harakatlarning “madaniy konseptualizatsiyasi” “madaniy sxemalar va madaniy metaforalar” shaklida sodir bo’ladi. Arutiunova (1990) fikriga ko’ra, kamtarlik konsepsiyasining metaforik aktualizatsiyasi metafora “obyektning u haqiqatan ham tegishli bo’lgan sinfga tegishlilikini inkor etishi va uni aqliy ravishda bog’lab bo’lmaydigan toifaga aloqadorligini tasdiqlaydi. Ingliz va o’zbek fantastika nutqida kamtarlikning konseptual metaforalarining doirasi ham, ko’lami ham doimiy darajada o’zgarib turadi, bu qisman ingliz va o’zbek dunyosining konstruksiyalaridagi turli xil axloqiy qadriyatlar va me’yorlar tizimi bilan izohlanadi. Madaniyat tushunchalari qay darajada farqlanadi va bu o’zgaruvchanlikni nima tushuntiradi degan savol tug’iladi. Irina Shevchenko va Vira Shastaloning (2021) ta’kidlashicha: “madaniyatlararo nuqtai nazardan, madaniyat tushunchalarining metaforik o’zgarishi lingvistik motivatsiya emas, balki madaniy sabablarga ko’ra ekanligini ta’kidlash mumkin”.

Zoltan Kovacs - kamtarlik [Modesty] konseptual metafora sifatidagi qarashlari.

Kovacsning fikricha (2002) ingliz tili konstruksiyasidagi “Modesty” (kamtarlik) metaforalarining diapazoni “MORALITY” (axloq) domenida tasvirlangan kamtarlikning maqsadli konsepsiyasiga moslashtirilgan manba domenlari tomonidan shakllantiriladi. Manba sohalari orasida shaxs (eng yuqori metaforizatsiya darajasiga ega), artefakt, konteyner, modda, sabab va o’lim mavjud.. Maqsadli kamtarlik konsepsiyasiga o’zaro bog’langan manba domenining bo’linishi ingliz tilida ikkita maxsus holatni hosil qiladi: kamtarlik - bu kuchli shaxs va kamtarlik - aktyor.

Birinchi holat quyidagicha tasvirlangan:

Harry’s modesty stopped him from speaking in public about the full extent of Cristian’s praises.

Garrining kamtarligi unga Kristianning maqtovlari haqida omma oldida gapirishdan to’xtatib qoldi.

Bu yerda “**modesty stopped him from speaking**” - kamtarlik uning gapirishdan to’xtatgan iborasi man qilish, ruxsat berish, majburlash va hokazo huquqiga ega bo’lgan “boshliq yoki rahbar” sifatidagi kamtarlikni bildiradi.

Ikkinchi holda, manba subdomen “aktyor”ning elementlari metafora hosil qiladi.

Modesty in Islam extends to all aspects of one's life, including attire.

Islomda hayo inson hayotining barcha jabhalariga, jumladan, kiyim-kechakka ham taalluqlidir.

Ushbu misolda ham hayo [modesty] ning o'rniga alohida to'xtalar ekan, bunda u qattiq nazorat qiluvchi inson sifatida gavdalanishi mumkin.

➤ **“Modesty is a thinker” (kamtarlik – bu chuqur fikrlovchi):**

“its “modesty”, combined with its great ferocity when cornered, suggests that it would have been troublesome.” [cat]

uning kamtarligi, ba'zida o'zgarganda yovvoyiligi bilan birgalikda, uning muammo chiqaruvchi bo'lishi mumkinligini ko'rsatishi mumkin;

➤ **“Modesty is an assistant” (kamtarlik yordamchidir):**

modesty that makes you avoid social events may allow you more time and motivation to pursue your solitary goals.

sizni ijtimoiy voqealardan qochishga majbur qiladigan uyatchanlik sizga yolg'iz maqsadlaringizga erishish uchun ko'proq vaqt va motivatsiya berishi mumkin;

➤ **Modesty is a person who is able to produce emotions, to move or disappear (kamtarlik - bu his-tuyg'ular paydo qilish, harakat qilish yoki yo'q bo'lib ketish va hokazolarga qodir bo'lgan odam):**

If you have no modesty, then do whatever you wish

Agar hayo qilmasangiz, xoxlagan narsangizni qiling.

In Islam, men and women share responsibility in upholding modesty and controlling their desires in society

Islom dinida erkaklar va ayollar jamiyatda hayoni saqlash va o'z nafslarini nazorat qilishga mas'uliyatlidirlar.

Now, albeit shee loved him very dearly, and all his behaviour was most pleasing to her, yet maiden modesty forbad her to reveale it, till Love (too long concealed) must needes disclose it selfe. [Decameron, Jiovanni Bokachcho]

Garchi u qiz uni juda yaxshi ko'rib va uning barcha xatti-harakatlari unga yoqqan taqdirda ham, toki Sevgi (juda uzoq vaqt yashirin bo'lgan) o'zini-o'zi oshkor qilmaguncha, uning qizlik kamtarligi uni oshkor qilishni taqiqlardi.

Bu misollarda “hayo” [modesty] insonlarni turli buzg'unchi holatlardan saqlash, yoki hayosiz narsalardan to'sib turuvchi inson sifatida talqin qilinadi.

✓ **modesty is an obstacle (kamtarinlik to'siqdir)** Bunda kamtarlik negativ ma'noda ishlatiladi ya'ni bunda kamtarlik insonlarni asl yuzlarini ko'rsatishdagi to'siq ma'nosida qo'llaniladi.

John asked some of the other participants to cast modesty aside and reveal the reasons for their success.

Jon ba'zi qatnashuvchilardan kamtarlikni bir chetga surib, ularning muvaffaqiyatining sabablarini ochib berishini so'radi.

✓ **modesty is a cover (kamtarlik bu yashirish).** Bu holatda ham yuqoridagiga o'xshash “yashirish” ma'nosida, faqat pozitiv ma'noda qo'llaniladi. Aynan mana shu kamtarlik ortida turgan ko'plab bilim, iqtidorlarni yashirib turadi. Bu o'zbek tilda “tavozeli” bo'lish ma'nosiga to'g'ri keladi.

Modesty cloaks many talents.

Kamtarlik ko'plab talantlarni yashiradi.

Maqsadli domen "Morality" va manbali domen "Plant" o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'lanishlar kamtarlik haqida uning ildizlaridan o'sadigan o'simlik metaforasini yaratadi, ya'ni "Modesty is a plant" (Kamtarlik bu o'suvchi narsa) ma'nosida qo'llanilishi mumkin.

This modesty can stem both from personality and lack of confidence.

Ushbu uyatchanlik shaxsiyatdan ham, o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchsizlikkan ham paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Bunda kamtarlikning paydo bo'lishiga ildiz sifatida shaxsiy xarakter yoki ishonchsizlik nazarda tutiladi.

Bugungi kunda ushbu ijobiy fazilatning an'anaviy qiymatini qayta ko'rib chiqish orqali salbiy metaforalar paydo bo'ldi. Bunda hayo [modesty] o'lim [death] bilan tenglashtiriladi:

"Awaited you? quoth Diana, and tossed her head archly disdainful. "La! [an expression of an emotion, such as surprise or anger] Sir Rowland, your modesty will be the death of you." [Mistress Wilding, Rafael Sabatini]

"Sizni kutayotgandi?!"-, dedi Diana. Nafrat bilan boshini ko'tardi va dedi: "Xa! Ser Roulend, sizning kamtarligingiz bir kun sizning boshingizga yetadi."

Haredi women are dying of modesty and living in a ghetto of silence.¹

Haredi ayollari kamtarlikdan o'lib, sukunat ichida yashashmoqda.

his engaging modesty and diffidence of manners endeared him to all those who shared his acquaintance...²

uning jozibali kamtarligi va uyatchanligi uni taniganlarning barchasida iliq taasurot uyg'otdi.

"Andisha va g'urur" asarida kamtarlik konseptual metafora sifatida.

"Believe me, my dear Miss Elizabeth, that your modesty, so far from doing you any disservice, rather adds to your other perfections."

➤ Ishoning, azizam, miss Elizabeth, sizning kamtarligingiz, hozircha sizga yomonlik yetkazishdan ko'ra, boshqa qo'shimcha mukammalliklaringizni ko'rsatib bermoqda.

Ushbu gapda "modesty" kopseptual metafora bo'lib, Zoltan Kovecses va Shevchenkoning **"Modesty is an assistant"** (kamtarlik yordamchidir) ta'rifi sifatida talqin qilinmoqda.

"since the refusal that his cousin had steadfastly given him would naturally flow from her bashful modesty and the genuine delicacy of her character."

amaktivachchasi unga bergan rad javobi tabiiy ravishda uning o'ta kamtarligi [uyatchan ma'nosida ham qo'llanilishi mumkin] va fe'l-atvorining chinakam nozikligi sabablidir.

Ushbu gapda ham kamtarlik **"modesty is a cover"** ya'ni insonning haqiqiy his tuyg'ularini yashiruvchi vosita sifatida, ijobiy ma'noda qo'llanilmoqda.

And you may be certain when I have the honor of seeing her again, I shall speak in the very highest terms of your modesty, economy, and other amiable qualification.

Yana ishonchingiz komil bo'lsin, aga uni ko'rishga muyassar bo'lsam, sizni kamtarligingiz, tejamkorligingiz va boshqa yaxshi fazilatlaringizni oshirib, so'zlab beraman.

Asarning ushbu parchasida ham janob Kollinz Elizabet xonimning kamtarlik xususiyatini tilga olar ekan, bu o'rinda ham kamtarlik konseptual metafora sifatida, insonning qadrini oshirishda yordamchi vosita **"Modesty is an assistant"** sifatida talqin qilinadi.

Your humility, Mr. Bingley,' said Elizabeth, 'must disarm reproof.

¹ <https://rootfunding.com/campaigns/charedi-breast-cancer-awareness>

² Smith, H. W. (1880). *Life and Correspondence of the Rev. William Smith* (Vol. 2).

Sizning kamtarligingiz har qanday tanqidchini quolsizlantirib qo'yadi.

Ushbu misolda ham **“humility”** kamtarlik ma'nosida qo'llanilar ekan, **“Modesty is a person in Power”** koseptual metaforasiga to'g'ri keladi. Ya'ni kamtarlik har qanday tanqidchini to'xtatib qo'ya oladigan inson sifatida ko'riladi.

“Nothing is more deceitful than the appearance of humility. It is often only carelessness of opinion, and sometimes an indirect boast.”

Kamtar ko'rinishdan ko'ra aldovchi narsa yo'q. Ko'pincha bu faqat bironing fikriga nisbatan beparvolik, ba'zan esa bilvosita maqtanishning yashirin ko'rinishidir.

Ushbu gapda kamtarlik salbiy ma'noda qo'llanilib, u inson aldashiga yordam beruvchi vosita **“Humility is an assistant”**, kamtarlik yashiruvchi vosita **“Humility is a cover”** sifatida qaralmoqda.

“And which of the two do you call MY little recent piece of modesty?”

Unda mening kichkinagina kamtarligimni ikkisidan qaysi biri deb ataysiz?

Ushbu gapda so'zlovchi konseptual metafora sifatida kamtarlikni insondagi ma'lum bir miqdordagi o'lchovga ega narsa sifatida ta'riflamoqda. Bundan ko'zlangan maqsad esa so'zlovchi tinglovchiga nisbatan **“piching, kinoya”** qilish uchun foydalanmoqda.

“He made a little mistake to be sure; but it is to the credit of his modesty.”

U ishonch hosil qilishda biroz xatoga yo'l qo'ydi; ammo bu uning kamtarligi sababidan.

Bu gapda kamtarlik insonni xato qilishga sabab bo'luvchi vosita sifatida qaralmoqda. O'z navbatida, ushbu gapda kamtarlik mister Bennetga nisbatan so'zlovchining chuqur hurmatini ko'rsatish maqsadida ham qo'llanilgan. Bunda “agar u kamtar bo'lmaganda, bunday xatoga yo'l qo'ymagan bo'lardi” degan tushuncha kelib chiqadi.

But Bingley has great natural modesty, with a stronger dependence on my judgment than on his own.

Ammo Bingli o'zinikiga qaraganda, mening mulohazalarimga ko'proq bog'liq bo'lgan ajoyib tabiiy kamtarlikka ega.

Ushbu gapda “natural modesty” konseptual metafora sifatida, kamtarlik insonni bironing mulohazalariga qo'shilishga, uni ma'qullashga yordam beruvchi [“modesty is an assistant”] vosita sifatida qaralmoqda. Ushbu gap orqali Darcy kamtarlikni tug'ma qobiliyat singari ta'riflamoqda.

I consider the clerical office as equal in point of dignity with the highest rank in the kingdom—provided that a proper humility of behaviour is at the same time maintained.

Men ruhoniyluk lavozimini, agar xulq-atvorida kamtarlik saqlanib qolsa, shohlikdagi eng yuqori martabaga teng deb bilaman.

Jeyn Ostin “humility” ya'ni kamtarlik insonni yuqoriga olib chiquvchi vosita sifatida ko'rsatmoqda. Kamtarlik **“an assistant”** ya'ni yordamchi sifatida, inson tutgan o'rnini eng yuqoriga qo'yuvchi vositadir. U bo'lmasa, xuddi inson aslida hech kimdek, yoki uning yordamisiz yuqoriga ko'tarila olmaydi.

Xulosa.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlash joizki, biz kundalik hayotda ishlatuvchi so'zlar, aslida konseptual metafora bo'lishi mumkin. Badiiy adabiyotdagi misollar orqali ularning tilimizdagi o'rni ifodalab berildi. Ularning o'rnini tahlil qilmasdan oldin bilib bo'lmaydi. Konseptual metaforalar tilimizga shunchalik moslashib ketganki, ba'zida ularning borligini anglamaymiz ham. Bu esa “konseptual” ya'ni onga bog'liqlikni ifodalovchi dalillardan biri deyishimiz mumkin. Umuman, metaforalar kundalik hayotimizning bir qismidir.

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Lug'atning Turlari Va Ularning Inson Hayotidagi O'rni

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Annotatsiya. Axborotlar jadal to'planib borayotgan asrimizda kerakli ma'lumotlarni tez va qulay tarzda olish uchun birinchi navbatda lug'atlarga murojaat qilamiz. Mutaxassisligimizdan qat'i nazar, unga doimo ehtiyojimiz tushadi. Ushbu maqolada lug'atning turlari va ularning inson hayotidagi o'rniga alohida to'xtalib o'tildi.

Kalit so'zlar: leksikografiya, tematik, terminologik, ensiklopediya, grafuka, morfema, ideografik, lug'at, ibora, kognitiv.

Lug'at tushunchasi. Turli manbalar lug'atga turlicha ta'rif beradi. *Lug'at*- ma'lum bir tamoyilga muvofiq tartibga solingan so'zlar (yoki morfemalar, iboralar, idiomalar va boshqalar) to'plamini o'z ichiga olgan va ularning ma'nosi, qo'llanilishi, kelib chiqishi, boshqa tilga tarjimasini va boshqalar haqida ma'lumot beruvchi ma'lumotnoma. Lug'at tuzishda muhim masala - materialning tartibi masalasidir. Ko'pincha, alifbo tartibida, ba'zan bir yoki boshqa tartibga solish tamoyillari bilan kombinatsiyada qo'llaniladi. Misol uchun, uyalar ko'p hollarda qo'llaniladi, ya'ni alifbo tartibini buzsa ham, umumiy ildiz bilan bog'liq bo'lgan so'zlarni bitta "uya" (bir lug'at yozuvi ichida)ga birlashtirish. Aslida, bu holatlarda so'zlarning alifbo tartibidan ildizlarning alifbo tartibiga chekinish mavjud. Bu lug'atlarning ayrim turlari uchun, masalan, derivativ va etimologik lug'atlar uchun juda qulay bo'lib chiqadi. Teskari lug'atlarda alifbo prinsipidan maxsus foydalanish mavjud bo'lib, so'zlar alifbo tartibida so'zning bosh harfi bo'yicha emas, balki oxirgi harflari bo'yicha joylashtirilgan. Lug'at tilning o'ziga xos ensiklopediyasi bo'lib, tilshunoslik sohasidagi nazariy tadqiqotlar sohasida eng boy materiallarni taqdim etadi. Ko'pgina nazariy masalalar birinchi navbatda o'z yechimini lug'atda oladi. Lug'atlar tilshunoslik nazariyasi natijalarini hayotga tatbiq etadi va sinovdan o'tkazadi, ko'pincha lug'atlar hali o'rganilmagan muammolarning amaliy yechimlari bilan fandan oldinda turadi. Leksikografik tavsiflarning o'zi lingvistik tahlil natijalarini o'z ichiga oladi va shuning uchun katta ilmiy ahamiyatga ega. Har bir lug'atda tuzuvchi ham, foydalanuvchi ham shug'ullanishi kerak bo'lgan leksikografiyaning asosiy tushunchalari va atamalari bilan tanishib chiqamiz. Zamonaviy ma'noda lug'at - bu bir xil darajadagi til birliklarining (odatda so'zlarning) tartiblangan (tizimlashtirilgan) ro'yxati ma'lum lingvistik sharhlar, talqinlar va boshqalar bilan, odatda alohida kitob yoki turkum ko'rinishida bo'ladi. Shunday qilib, biz atamaning asl tor ma'nosi (so'zlar yig'indisi) endi keng tushunilganini ko'ramiz: so'zlar shart emas, chunki bular morfema yoki frazeologik birliklarning lug'atlari va boshqalar bo'lishi mumkin. Biz "lug'at" tushunchasini ta'riflashda yana uchta fikrni ta'kidlaymiz: tartiblash - tavsiflangan birliklar topish tezligi yoki boshqa maqsadlar uchun ma'lum bir tarzda joylashtirilgan: ko'pincha alifbo tartibida, lekin lug'atni tashkil qilishning boshqa usullari ham bo'lishi mumkin (ichki, chastota, semantik va boshqalar), biz keyinroq muhokama qilamiz; lingvistik sharh - so'z tavsifining u yoki bu tomoni (imlo, talaffuz, qo'llanish, ta'lim, semantika va boshqalar); odatda alohida kitob shaklida - ammo lug'at darslik yoki boshqa kitobning ilovasi ham bo'lishi mumkin (birinchi lug'atlar xuddi shunday edi). Materialni joylashtirishning alifbo bo'lmagan tamoyillari orasida eng muhimi leksik birliklar bilan ifodalangan tushunchalarni sistematika (mantiqiy tasniflash) tamoyilidir. Aynan shu tamoyil asosida ideografik lug'atlar («mafkuraviy» yoki «tematik» lug'atlar deb ham ataladi) tuziladi. Tushunchalarning u yoki bu mantiqiy tasnifi ishlab chiqilgan va lug'atga kiritilishi kerak bo'lgan barcha narsalar ushbu tasnifning sarlavhalari ostida joylashgan. Ideografik lug'atlar ikki va ko'p tilli bo'lishi ham mumkin. Lug'atlarni tuzish juda qiyin ish. So'z, uning ma'nolari va qo'llanilishi, grammatik va fonetik xususiyatlari haqidagi umumiy lingvistik qoidalarga qo'shimcha ravishda, lug'atlarni tuzish texnikasini bilish va lug'at tarkibini tushunish kerak: 1) lug'at, ya'ni lug'atlar tanlovi (bosh so'zlar) o'zaro murojaatlar va havolalar bilan; 2) ma'lum bir lug'atning ma'nolarini ajratib ko'rsatish; 3) so'zlarga va

ularning ma'nolariga stilistik, grammatik va fonetik izohlar yoki belgilar; 4) tasviriy misollar, 5) idiomatik va frazeologik birikmalar; 6) tarjima (ko'p tilli lug'atlarda) yoki talqin (tushuntirish - bir tilli lug'atlarda).

Leksikografiya (yunoncha leksikosdan - va so'ziga ishora qiladi...*grafika*) - tilshunoslikning kompilyatsiya qilish amaliyoti va nazariyasi bilan shug'ullanadigan bo'limi. Amaliy shakllarni ishlab chiqishda leksikografiya turli xalqlarda 3 ta o'xshash davr ajratiladi: 1) so'zgacha bo'lgan davr. Asosiy vazifa - tushunarsiz so'zlarni tushuntirish; 2) ilk so'z boyligi davri. Asosiy vazifasi adabiy tilni o'rganish bo'lib, u ko'plab xalqlar uchun so'zlashuv nutqidan farq qiladi; 3) rivojlanish davri leksikografiya milliy adabiy tillarning rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq. Asosiy vazifa - tilning lug'at tarkibini tavsiflash va normallashtirish, jamiyatning til madaniyatini oshirish. Zamonaviy leksikografiya ma'lum bir davr jamiyati haqidagi bilimlar to'plamini qayd etadigan lug'atlarning muhim ijtimoiy funksiyasini ta'kidlaydi. Leksikografiya lug'atlarning tipologiyasini ishlab chiqadi. Monolingual leksikografiya (tushuntirish va boshqa lug'atlar), ikki tilli leksikografiya (tarjima lug'atlar) alohida ajralib turadi: ta'lim leksikografiyasi (til o'rganish uchun lug'atlar), ilmiy-texnikaviy leksikografiya (terminologik lug'atlar). Terminologik lug'atlar - bu bilim yoki faoliyatning bir yoki bir nechta maxsus sohalari terminologiyasini o'z ichiga olgan lug'atlar. Har qanday lug'at lug'at yozuvlaridan iborat. Lug'at yozuvi lug'atning asosiy tarkibiy birligidir; lug'atdagi sarlavha birligini tushuntiruvchi va uning asosiy xususiyatlarini tavsiflovchi matn. Lug'at yozuvining tuzilishi lug'atning vazifalari bilan belgilanadi. Ammo har qanday lug'atning lug'at yozuvi bosh so'z bilan boshlanadi [boshqa tarzda: bosh so'z, lemma, qora so'z (odatda bosh so'zni belgilaydigan qalin turdan)]. Sarlavhali yozuvlar to'plami lug'atni yoki lug'atning chap tomonini tashkil qiladi. Lug'atning o'ng tomoni sarlavha birligini tushuntirib beradi. Izohlovchi lug'atning o'ng qismi, qoida tariqasida, zonalarni o'z ichiga oladi: so'zning grammatik xususiyatlari, talqini, ma'no turi (to'g'ridan-to'g'ri, ko'chma); rasmlar (iqtiboslar, so'zlar); hosila uyasi; "zarhomb" deb ataladigan qism (frazeologizmlar) va boshqalar. Har bir lug'at uchun o'ng qismning zonalari ishlab chiqilgan. Barcha lug'at yozuvlarining yig'indisi lug'at korpusini tashkil qiladi. Korpusga qo'shimcha ravishda har qanday lug'atda so'zboshi, "Lug'atdan qanday foydalanish kerak" bo'limi mavjud (ba'zi sabablarga ko'ra uni hech kim o'qimaydi); shartli qisqartmalar ro'yxati va boshqalar. Lug'at muammosi leksikografiyada markaziy masalalardan biridir, chunki so'zlarni tanlash lug'at turini ham, so'zlarni tavsiflash xususiyatini ham belgilaydi. Masalan, me'yoriy izohli lug'atda faqat adabiy tilning so'zlari lug'at tarkibiga kiradi, shuning uchun soxta lug'at chiqarib tashlanadi: xalq tili, jargon, sheva so'zlari. Orfoepik lug'atning lug'ati faqat qiyinchilik va talaffuz variantlari va boshqalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Lug'atlar har xil turda bo'lishi mumkin. Avvalo, ular aniq ikki guruhga bo'linadi: ensiklopedik va lingvistik. Ensiklopediya va ensiklopedik lug'atlarning o'ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, ular so'zlarni emas, balki ma'lum so'zlar bilan ifodalangan voqelikni (ob'ektlar va shaxslar, hodisalar va tushunchalar) tushuntiradi. Ensiklopediya so'zi qadimgi yunonlardan kelib chiqqan bo'lib, ular tomonidan "bilim doirasi", "bilimning butun doirasida o'rganish" degan ma'noni anglatadi. Har qanday ta'lim darajasidagi har qanday o'quvchi ensiklopediyadan qiziqqan mavzu bo'yicha kerakli ma'lumotlarni topishi mumkin. Ensiklopediya o'z-o'zini tarbiyalashning muhim vositasidir. Bu ensiklopediyaning tuzilishini, materialni yoritishning mazmuni va tamoyillarini belgilaydi. Umumjahon ensiklopediyalar va ensiklopedik lug'atlar bilan bir qatorda falsafa, tarix, texnologiya, matematika, fizika, qishloq xo'jaligi, tibbiyot, konchilik, diplomatiya, pedagogika, adabiyot va boshqa ko'plab sohalarga oid ensiklopediyalar va qomusiy lug'atlar mavjud. Bular maxsus ensiklopediyalar va ensiklopedik lug'atlardir. Ularning vazifasi tegishli bilim, san'at, ishlab chiqarish va hokazo sohasi tushunchalarini (hodisalar o'zini) ma'lum bir doirada tushuntirish, bu tushunchalarni bildiruvchi so'zlarni alifbo tartibida joylashtirishdir. Lug'atda tasvirlangan so'zlar (lug'atlar) soni lug'at hajmi. Odatda lug'at hajmi haqida ma'lumot lug'atning sarlavha sahifasida yoki izohida beriladi. Lug'atga kirish komponentlari to'plami lug'at turiga qarab belgilanadi. Misol uchun, komponentlarning eng to'liq to'plami tushuntirish lug'atlarida, eng kami - imlo va shunga o'xshash bir tomonlama lug'atlarda keltirilgan. Ba'zi tushuntirish yoki o'quv lug'atlari shunchalik ko'p tavsif parametrlarini qamrab oladiki, ularning har biri maxsus zonada (vizual, grafik jihatdan) ajralib turadi: grammatika zonasi, moslik zonasi, ma'no zonasi, rasmlar zonasi va boshqalar. Lug'atlar tipologiyasi. Lug'atlarning tipologiyasi ideal lug'at (ya'ni lug'at turi, namunasi sifatida) tushunchasiga asoslangan ilmiy tasnifdir. Biroq, u odatda amaliy asosda qurilgan, ya'ni, mavjud lug'atlar bo'yicha. Shuning uchun biz bu ma'noda lug'atlarning ilmiy tipologiyasi haqida emas, balki faqat

uni qurish tamoyillari haqida gapirishimiz mumkin. Shunday qilib, lug'atlarni tasniflashning bir nechta yo'nalishlari yoki parametrlari mavjud bo'lib, biz ularni asos qilib olamiz: *lingvistik, semiotik, rasmiy va ijtimoiy-pragmatik*.

Lug'atlarning inson hayotidagi o'rni. Bizning zamonamizda, ilm-fan taraqqiyoti asrida, axborotning jadal to'planishi sharoitida bilimning barcha sohalari bo'yicha nashrlar oqimi keskin ortib bormoqda. Bularning barchasi ilmiy, amaliy yoki kognitiv xarakterdagi ishonchli ma'lumotlarni tez va qulay olish uchun mo'ljallangan turli xil ma'lumotnoma adabiyotlarining ahamiyatini beqiyos oshiradi. Hozirgi vaqtda lug'atlarsiz, ma'lumotnomalarsiz qilish mumkin emas, chunki ular alifbo tartibida joylashtirilgan ulkan insoniy bilimlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Lekin har doim ham odam o'z nutqida madaniyatli bo'la olmaydi. Barcha bilimlarni, ayniqsa, nutq madaniyatiga oid bilimlarni boshlang'ich sinfdan olish kerak. Shunday qilib, balog'at yoshida u allaqachon savodli bo'ladi va qo'shimcha bilim manbalaridan foydalanish uning muhitiga, kasbiga va boshqalarga asoslanadi. Tilning rivojlanishi bilan birga uning me'yorlari ham takomillashtiriladi. Adabiy til me'yorlarini bir marta o'rganishning iloji yo'q, nutq madaniyatini muntazam oshirib borish zarur. Bunday hollarda yordam uchun turli lug'atlarga murojaat qilishadi.

Hozirgi vaqtda lug'at ishining quyidagi yo'nalishlarini ajratish mumkin:

- A) ikki tilli leksikografiya, eng avvalo, tillararo muloqot funksiyasi bilan bog'liq;
- B) ona tili va ona tili bo'lmagan tilni o'rgatish funksiyasi bilan bog'liq o'quv leksikografiyasi;
- C) tilning lug'at, semantika, grammatikasini ilmiy o'rganish va tavsiflash funksiyasini bajaradigan tavsif yoki akademik leksikografiya;
- D) har xil turdagi me'yoriy lug'atlar yaratish, tegishli murojaat funksiyasini bajaradigan leksikografiyani normallashtirish (tartibga solish).

Har bir lug'at faqat ma'lumotnoma emas, balki nazariy tilshunoslik bilan bir xil ilmiy maqomga ega bo'lgan tilning muayyan bo'limiga oid nazariy insho hamdir. Shuning uchun lug'at eng muhim o'quv qurolidir. Lug'at nafaqat vaqt va kuchni tejaydi, oldingi avlodlar tomonidan to'plangan bilimlarga yo'l ochadi, balki buni didaktikaning eng muhim talabiga muvofiq amalga oshiradi. Shuning uchun har qanday lug'at, birinchi navbatda, o'rganish uchun mo'ljallangan ishdur. Bu xususiyat maxsus o'quv lug'atlarida eng aniq namoyon bo'ladi.

Xulosa. Lug'atlar va ma'lumotnomalar hayotimizning doimiy hamrohi bo'lib, bilimimizni kengaytirish, til madaniyatimizni yuksaltirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Ular haqli ravishda sivilizatsiya yo'ldoshlari deb ataladi. Lug'atlar chinakamiga milliy tilning bitmas-tuganmas xazinasidir. Aynan lug'atlar xalq taraqqiyotining moddiy va ma'naviy madaniyat sohasidagi muvaffaqiyatlarini aks ettirishga da'vat etilgan. Fransuz lug'atshunosi Alan Rey "zamonaviy sivilizatsiya lug'at sivilizatsiyasi" deb to'g'ri ta'kidlagani ajablanarli emas. Bu bilan u lug'atlarning zamonaviy dunyoda hayotimizning barcha jabhalariga kirib borishi muhim rolini ta'kidlamog'chi edi. Mashhur fransuz yozuvchisi Anatol Frans shunday yozgan edi: "Lug'atlar alifbo tartibida butun koinotdir! O'ylab qarasangiz, lug'at kitoblar kitobidir. U boshqa barcha kitoblarni o'z ichiga oladi, siz ularni faqat undan chiqarib olishingiz kerak."

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Place Names in Proverbs and Idioms: A Comparative Study of English and Uzbek Languages

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Annotation. *The study of English and Uzbek phraseological units, including place names, is the focus of this article. Attempts are being made to identify and study the origins of origin from a linguocultural standpoint.*

Key words: *toponyms, proverb, saying, comparative study.*

Toponymy is an integral part of onomastics, which studies place names (toponyms), their meaning, structure, origin and distribution. The totality of toponyms in any territory constitutes its toponymy. Traditionally, a toponym is understood as a proper name of any geographical object, any object on the surface of the Earth or in its bowels, allocated by a person as an independent unit defines toponyms as “historically, socially and culturally determined geographical names of any natural or artificial objects created by man on land or in the water area of the Earth. Geographical names are very stable, they are preserved for a long time, becoming a kind of historical monuments; therefore, toponymy, according to many researchers, also to a certain extent refers to history and source studies. The status of a toponym is determined by its main functions in the linguistic culture of an ethnos:

- a) nominative (naming);
- b) individualizing (identification);
- c) cumulative;
- d) cultural content.

These phraseological units reflect the history of people; therefore, to understand them, you need to know specific historical facts. In all languages of the world, many phraseological units are based on the names of cities, streets, rivers, oceans, as well as on the realities associated with toponyms.

PU with a toponymic component reflect a person's centuries-old observations of the world of toponymy, convey the attitude of people to this sphere of reality. There are many place names formed as part of the PU. It is important to examine how and when they appeared, as well as the determinants of their appearance. In some cases, these PUs undergo semantic transformations over time. Consequently, in the study of such phraseological units, the motivation and etymology of toponymic components play a vital role. In the process of researching the sources of origin, the following groups of software were discovered: Shipshape and Bristol fashion -for everything to be in order (in the middle of the 19th century, Bristol was known as a port city in England. The expression emphasized the commercial prosperity of the port of Bristol and its good navigation conditions cross the Rubicon -take irreversible action (The Rubicon was a small river in northeastern Italy. By moving his army across the Rubicon to Italy in 49 BC, Julius Caesar violated the law forbidding a general to withdraw an army from his own province, and therefore entered the war against the Senate and Pompey.

In the Uzbek language there is PE with toponymic components related to customs and everyday life:

Beva xotinga Buxorodan it huradi-so that the widow should live alone, as they gossip about her;

Eshonbozorda it olsa "yigirma" sidan kuruk kolmaidi -a person who goes everywhere, especially for ceremonies (Eshonbozor is a village in the south of Kazakhstan, yigirma is a religious ceremony that is held after death);

ahmoqqa Quva bir tosh -used when a person who does not do something completely and must do it again; PUs that came from other languages: idioms and borrowings It is almost impossible to find exact synonyms for such units in other languages, thus the toponymic PUs are borrowed in most cases: in English, discover America also exists in Uzbek, Amerika ochmoq -to say or declare what has already been discovered;

There are phraseological units that exist in both languages, but in some cases they differ in meaning, for example, the Chinese wall means a barrier in English, since there has never been a unique plan for its construction, and in the Uzbek Xitoy devoir means there is something stable and durable ... The two languages took into account different features of the same phenomenon. It should be emphasized that they are associated with world famous historical events and phenomena. Archaic place names in PU In English and Uzbek languages, toponymic PU, which have archaic place names in their structure, eventually become archaic phraseological units: perfidious Albion is the nickname of England (Albion was the ancient name of Great Britain).

Thus, place names have various meanings and connotations due to culture specific associations. Symbolic and stereotypical meanings of place names that were formed for long periods of time affect the overall connotation of a unit. Thus, in toponymical phraseologies, whether the unit is positively or negatively marked heavily depends on the place name in the structure of a phraseological unit.

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Surxondaryo Viloyati Ikkinchi Jahon Urushi Yillarida

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada XIX asrning 30-40-yillarida sodir bo'lgan ikkinchi jahon urushi davrida Surxondaryo aholisining ko'rsatgan jasorati, olib borgan jonbozlik ishlari keltirib o'tilgan. Shuningdek, o'sha davrda sodir bo'lgan xalqning noroziliklari, turli xil nohaqliklar ham alohida ajratib ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: 1941-yilning 22-iyun, "Pattakesar", "Hovdak", "Hazarbog'", Otay Raxmonov, "Pravda gazetasi", Tanya Pankratova, "qizil chegara", "Harbiy safarlar va janglar", "Shuhrat" ordeni.

Xalqimiz bosib o'tgan ko'p ming yillik tarixni xolisona tarzda milliy istiqloq g'oyalari asosida yoritish tarixshunoslik fanining bugungi kundagi asosiy vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Bu borada amalga oshirilishi lozim bo'lgan asl tamoyillarni anglab olish va tarixga yangicha nazar bilan yondashishda muhtaram birinchi Prezidentimiz I.A.Karimovning quyidagi fikrlari diqqatga sazovordir: "Kim bo'lishidan qat'iy nazar jamiyatning har bir a'zosi o'z o'tmishini yaxshi bilsa, bunday odamlarni yo'ldan urish, har xil aqidalar ta'siriga olish mumkin emas. Tarix saboqlari insonni hushyorlikka o'rgatadi, irodasini mustahkamlaydi"[1]. Shu asnosida Surxondaryo hududining tarixini o'rganish ham ham shunday dolzarb va qiziq mavzu hisoblanadi. Shulardan bu hududning ikkinchi jahon urushi davridagi holati ayniqsa eng qiziq mavzulardan biridir. Urushning boshlanishi Surxon vohasida yashayotgan tinchlikparvar kishilarning ham qalblarini larzaga soldi, ularda fashizmga nisbatan qahr-g'azab va nafrat hissi uyg'ondi. Urushning sovuq xabari eshutilgan onlardan oq voha mehnatkashlari ham ushbu boshlangan urushni qoralovchi, fashizm bilan bo'ladigan jangga doimo tayyor ekanligini bildiruvchi va ayni vaqtda ishlab chiqarishda yangi g'alabalarga erishib fashizm ustidan qozonilgan g'alabani yaqinlashtirishga undovchi mitinglar o'tkaza boshlaganlar.

1941-yilning 22-iyun kuni, ya'ni sovuq urush xabari tarqalgan kunidayoq Termiz tumani "Pattakesar" qishloq kengashi a'zolarining ko'p ming kishilik mitinggi bo'lib o'tdi. Unda "Kerak bo'lsa ketmonlarimizni miltiqqa aylantiramiz, biroq qora kuchlarning go'zal polizlarimizga cho'chqa tumshuqparini tiqishiga yo'l qo'ymaymiz", degan murojaat qabul qilingan bo'lsa, 23-iyun kuni "Hovdak" neft koni ishchilari esa fashizmga qarshi bo'lib o'tgan mitingda: "Biz shu kundan boshlab o'zimizni safarbar qilingan deb hisoblaymiz", degan xitobnomani qabul qildilar. Denov tumani "Hazarbog'" davlat xo'jaligi 4-bo'lim traktorchisi Otay Raxmonov o'zini frontga jo'natishlarini so'rab harbiy komissariatga yozgan arizasida: "Men texnikani boshqarishni bilaman, avtomashinada ishlashim mumkin. Uyda ota-onam va xotinim bor. Ularning hammasi mehnatga layoqatli, meni frontga jo'natishlaringizni so'rayman. qasamyod qilib aytamanki, ishonchni oklayman, fashistlarni beomon savalayman", deb yozgan edi. Termiz shahar "Pravda gazetasi" nomli maktab o'qituvchisi F. Hakimova shahar harbiy komissariatiga o'zini harakatdagi armiyaning sanitariya drujinasiga qabul qilishlarini so'rab ariza beradi. Shuningdek, sherobodlik Tillo Fayzieva, termizlik Vera Vyalochkina, Anna Shumixina, A.I.Fomina kabi o'nlab ayollarning nomlari yurt ozodligi uchun janggohlarda jon olib, jon bergan jasur xotin-qizlar qatorida harbiy-tarixiy solnomalarda qayd etilgan[2].

Gapning indallosiga ko'chsak, yana mavzuyim Ikkinchi jahon urushidagi g'alabaga O'zbekistonning qo'shgan hissasi. Bu gal Surxondaryo viloyatida olib borilgan ishlar to'g'risida to'xtalsam. Ikkinchi jahon urushida viloyat aholisining g'alabaga qo'shgan hissasi Alpomishning jasoratidan aslo kam emas deb o'ylayman. Surxondaryo viloyati mudofaa ishlari boshqarmasi xodimlari tomonidan Ikkinchi jahon

urushiga taalluqli turli xildagi eksponatlar to'planib, hujjatlar, buyumlar, anjomlar va fotosuratlar jamlandi. To'plangan ma'lumotlarga asoslanadigan bo'lsak, to'rt yil davom etgan urush davrida 53 365 nafar surxondaryoliklar frontga jo'natilgan. Shulardan 11 000 nafari jangda halok bo'lib, yaqinlari qora xat oldi. Urushning boshlarida viloyatning 18-harbiy o'quv punktida mutaxassislar armiya uchun jangchilar tayyorlaganlar. Harbiy-o'quv punktida 5000 ortiq pulemyotchilar, minamyotchilar, tankka qarshi qiruvchilar tayyorlanadi. Bir vaqtda mudofaaga ko'maklashuvchi tashkilot yo'l-yo'rig'i bilan 18000 harbiy mutaxassis tayyorlangan. 1942-yil 6 ta maxsus ayollar va qizlar bo'linmalari tuzilgan. Bir yil ichida 246 nafar o'quvchi qiz tayyorlanadi. 1942-yil Termiz shahridan 20 injenerlik qo'shinlarida xizmat qilish uchun frontga jo'natiladi. Qizil xoch va yarim oy jamiyatlari ko'rsatmasi bilan 25 ta sanitar drujinalari tuziladi. Ularda 260 nafar hamshira va feldsherlar tayyorlanagan. Urushning eng og'iri birinchi kunlarida bo'ladi. Masalan, Brest qal'asini mudofaa qilishda Surxondaryolik Tanya Pankratova halok bo'ladi. Ushbu urushning birinchi kunlari fojiasi haqida, talofatlarini va hujumga o'tish voqealarini hikoya qiluvchi eksponatlar Surxondaryo viloyat tarixi va madaniyati davlat muzeyida mavjud. O'sha davrda ko'pgina rassomlar o'z asarlarini yaratganlar. Kozlovning "Oxirgi granata", O.Kravanogovning "Kursk yoyi" ko'chirma nusxa asarlari yaratildi. Surxondaryoliklar Stalingrad ostonalaridagi janglarda muvaffaqiyatli qatnashadi. Shulardan R.Zokirov, V.Novikov Riga yonidagi janglarda, A.Qaysarov Kursk yonidagi, J.To'rayev va boshqalar janglarda halok bo'lishadi. B.Eshonqulov, A.Gogoleva-Karchenko, YU.Normurodov Berlinni shturm qilishda qatnashadilar[3]

Umuman, urush boshlangan davrda harbiy komissariatlarga o'zlarini frontga safarbar qilishlarini so'rab viloyat miqyosida ikki mingdan ortiq ariza tushadi. 1941-yilning iyun-iyul oylarida esa 20 ming kishi ko'ngilli bo'lib frontga jo'naydi. Fashizm balosini yo'qotish uchun o'zining turmush o'rtog'ini jangga kuzatayotgan ayollar ularga dushmanga ayovsiz qirg'in solish topshirig'ini bera boshladilar. Termiz tumani "qizil chegara" jamoa xo'jaligi a'zosi Shomirbob Mirzaev o'z o'g'lini askarlikka kuzatib bunday degan edi: "O'g'lim, mard bo'l, botirlik bilan kurash. Men ham shu yerda sening o'rningni bosib, yurtimizni yov kira olmas qo'rg'onga aylantirish uchun bor kuchimni sarf qilaman". 1941-yilning 15-oktabriga qadar bo'lgan vaqt mobaynida viloyat bo'yicha 800 nafar xotinqiz "frontga ketgan yigitlarning o'rnini olish kerak", degan chaqiriq bilan chikdi. Hayot harbiy izga solingan mamlakatda urush bo'layotgan ekan, harbiy tayyorgarlikka beparvo qarab bo'lmaydi. Fuqarolar qanchalik harbiy texnikani kuchli o'rgansa, g'alaba daqiqalari shunchalik yaqinlashadi. Zero, qo'lida qurol ko'tarib, o'z ozodligini himoya qilishga o'rganmagan xalq ozod qolishi mumkin emas. Shu munosabat bilan sobiq SSSR Mudofaa qo'mitasining 1941-yil 23-iyuldagi "Fuqarolarni umumharbiy tayyorgarlikdan o'tkazish to'g'risida"gi qaroriga muvofiq urushning dastlabki oylarida viloyatda 21494 kishi harbiycha yurish, granata irg'itish va boshqa turli harbiy mashg'ulotlarni o'rgandi. Shuningdek, 1941-yilning iyulavgust oylarida 1800 kishi ishtirokida piyodalarning 1025 km masofaga harbiy yurishi o'tkazildi[4].

Ivan Kolodiy (1912-1954 y.y.) haqida ikki marta Sovet Ittifoqi qahramoni general P.Batov o'zining "Harbiy safarlar va janglar" nomli kitobida hikoya qiladi. U ilg'or otryadlar safida Dnepr daryosini kechib o'tishda qatnashadi. Sharqiy qirg'oqni kechib o'tish vaqtida qayiqqa snaryad tegib, parchalanib ketadi. Aloqachi yelkasidan og'ir yaralanadi, lekin qirg'oqqacha suzib borib, rasiyani joylashtirib, narigi qirg'oqdagi batareyalarimizga qo'shinning muhim o't ochish nuqtalarining koordinatalarini beradi. Batareyalar ishonchli ma'lumotlarni olgandan so'ng, dushmanning 16 ta o't ochish nuqtasini, 3 ta nemis batareyasini, 60 ta fashistni yakson qildi. I.Kolodiyning shaxsan o'zi qarshi hujumga o'tib, 15 fashistni o'ldirdi. Yarador bo'lishiga qaramasdan gospitalga yotishdan bosh tortdi va safda qoldi. Dnepr daryosini kechib o'tishdagi qahramonligi uchun unga Sovet Ittifoqi qahramoni unvoni berildi. F.Volkov, I.Kolodiy, L.Lyubimov, K.Prosenko, S.Chernishev, A.Shamkayev Sovet Ittifoqi qahramoni unvonini oldi. Uch kishi – N.Oreshnikov, A.Tikachyov, R.Tukayev "Shuhrat" ordeni sohibi bo'lishdi[4].

O'sha jangovar yillarda Surxondaryo viloyatiga ham O'nga yaqin sanoat korxonalarini evakuatsiya qilindi. Ko'chirib keltirilgan sanoat korxonalarini asosan viloyatning Termiz shaxri va Denov tumanlarida joylashtiriddi. Jumladan, Pavlograd, Chertkov, Prikolotensk yog' zavodlari Denov tumanida, Chernyanskiy, Stavropolskiy yog' korxonalarini esa Termiz shahriga joylashtirildi. Biroq, shu narsani alohida qayd etish lozimki, sanoat korxonalarining viloyatga ko'chirib keltirilishi va ishga tushirilishida

jiddiy qiyinchiliklarga duch kelindi. Bu qiyinchiliklar birinchi navbatda malakali texnik xodimlarning va moddiy resurslarning yetishmasligi natijasida yuzaga keldi. Jumladan, Ukrainaning Pavlograd viloyatidan keltirilgan o‘simlik moyi ishlab chiqarishga moslashgan asbob-uskunalar Denov paxta tozalash zavodi sushilkasi binosida joylashtirildi. Shu bilan Denov yog‘ekstraksiya zavodi qurilishiga poydevor qo‘yildi. Zavod respublika Mudofaa qo‘mitasi Asosiy savollarsiga binoan 1944-yilda ishga tushirilishi va 60 ming tonna chigitni qayta ishlashi lozim edi. Lekin mavjud vaziyatdan to‘g‘ri va unumli foydalangan zavod ahli qurilishmontaj ishlarini jadal sur‘atlarda boshlab yubordi. Ayniqsa, P.Morozova va I.Vasilenko brigadasi ishchilari kechanikecha, kunduznikunduz demasdan mehnat qiddilar. Natija kutilgandan ham ziyoda bo‘ldi va zavod 1943-yil yanvar oyiga kelib o‘zining birinchi mahsulotini bera boshladi. 1943-yilning IV choragida zavod ishga tushdi, mazut bo‘lmaganligi sababli u sheluxa yoqilib isitilgan. Zavod har bir smenada uch yuz, to‘rt yuz kilogrammgacha moy ishlab chiqara boshladi. Shu yillar mobaynida yiliga 979 tonna o‘simlik moyi ishlab chiqardi, chigitni ishlash 10769 tonnaga, chigitdan olinadigan moy esa 11 foizga yetdi[5]. 1942-yilning mart oyigacha bo‘lgan vaqt mobaynida Surxondaryo viloyatiga 719 oila yoki 1862 kishi evakuatsiya qilingan. Evakuatsiya qilingan aholining 480 nafari erkak, 1059 nafari ayol, 323 nafari bolalar, yoki ko‘chib keltirilgan aholining 1480 nafari ishga yaroqli edi. Viloyatga ko‘chirilgan ishga yaroqli aholi tezda ishlab chiqarishga jalb qilindi. Jumladan, ishga yarakli ana shu aholining 1209 nafari jamoa va davlat xo‘jaliklarida ishga joylashtirilgan bo‘lsa, 271 kishi esa turli tashkilot va muassasalarga ishga jalb etildi. 1942-yilda toshkentlik ayollar respublikaning barcha ayollariga murojaat qabul qildi. Unda “O‘zbekistonga evakuatsiya qilingan va boqimsiz qolgan bolalarga jamoat yordami ko‘rsatish umumxalq harakatini avj oldiraylik. Har bir ishchining, har bir kolxozchining, xizmatchining, ziyolining oilasi, har bir korxonalar, jamoa xo‘jaligi va davlat xo‘jaligi shu bolalarni joylashtirish va tarbiyalashda faol qatnashsin”[6], deyilgan edi. Toshkentlik ayollarning murojaatidan ruhlangan Surxon vohasi mehnatkashlari ham otaonasiz qolgan bolalarga astoydil g‘amxo‘rlik ko‘rsata boshladi. Viloyat mehnatkashlari otaonasiz qolgan bolalarga yordam sifatida 18800 so‘m pul to‘pladilar va otaonasiz qolgan bolalar fondiga topshirdilar. Mexridaryo surxondaryoliklar otaonasiz qolgan bolalarga g‘amxo‘rlik qilish bilan birga ularni o‘z xonadonlariga olib kelib tarbiyalab, voyaga yetkazish ishida ham faol ishtirok etdilar, norasidalariga otalik va onalik mehrini ko‘rsatib, yetimlik alami bilan jarohatlangan dillarga malham bo‘ldilar. Jumladan, ana shunday mehribon insonlardan Sherobod tumani g‘urjak qishlog‘ida yashovchi Egamberdi quvvatov 5 yoshli o‘g‘il bolani, viloyat xalq ta‘limi xodimi Lesenkin 5 yoshli qiz bolani va uy bekasi K.I.Kolesova 2 yoshli qiz bolani o‘z tarbiyasiga oldilar[7]. 1942-yilning ikkinchi yarmiga kelib viloyatga ko‘chib keltirilayotgan aholining soni ortib bordi, masalan, 1943-yilda viloyatga yana 966 kishi ko‘chirib keltirildi. Ko‘chib keltirilgan aholining 121 nafari erkaklar, 437 nafari xotin-qizlar, 208 nafari 1 yoshdan 8 yoshgacha bo‘lgan bolalar, 200 nafari esa 8 yoshdan 16 yoshgacha bo‘lgan O‘spirinlar edi. Jumladan, 1283 Polsha fuqarosi Sariosiyo tumanida o‘rnashgan bo‘lsa, 575 kishi esa Denov tumaniga qo‘chirib keltirildi, 548 kishi esa Sho‘rchi tumanidan boshpana topdi. Mehridaryo sho‘rchiliklar ko‘chirib keltirilgan ushbu jabrdiydalarga yordam tariqasida 2615 sum pul ajratdi, 59 kishiga esa moddiy yordam uyushtirgan edi. Shuningdek, 81 ta turli xil uy-ro‘zg‘or buyumlari, 23 ta ko‘rpa, 20 dona ko‘ylak, 18 dona shim, 2 etik, 1 juft tufli va boshqa turli mahsulotlar insonparvarlik yordami ko‘rsatdilar[8].

Xulosa qilib aytganda, ikkinchi jahon urushida barcha viloyatlar qatori Surxondaryo viloyati aholisining ham xizmatlari katta bo‘lgan. Agar askarlar ortida ularni ta‘minlab turgan xalq bo‘lmaganda hech qanday g‘alabani hatto tasavvur ham qilib bo‘lmasdi. Qanchalik qiyin bo‘lmasin xalqimiz bunday og‘ir kunlarni jasorat bilan yegib o‘tdi desak mubolag‘a bo‘lmaydi.

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Fertility Characteristics of Cows Belonging to Different Selections

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Annation. *This article provides information on the indicators of replenishment of the herd of Holstein cattle of various breeding works. The bodies of the German selection had a significant advantage over the cattle of the Polish and Belarusian selection in terms of the age of the first calving, live weight, duration of the service period and the fertilization index.*

Key words: *Cattle, cows, insemination age, insemination index, insemination, service period.*

Relevance of the topic. The demand of the population of our republic in livestock products requires further development of animal husbandry to meet growing needs. In this regard, an important task is to improve the breeds of each type of farm animals, zoned for breeding on the territory of our republic.

One of the important breeds zoned for breeding in our republic is the Holstein breed. This breed is widespread not only in our republic, but also on many continents of the world, and cows are distinguished by high milk and meat productivity, udder-fertility characteristics, the degree of feed coverage with milk and meat, rapid growth rates of young animals and the difference in a number of other important economically useful features.

The development of methods for creating a new herd of productive cows based on various breeding groups is of particular importance not only for improving the breed, but also for increasing their numbers and expanding their distribution area. Therefore, in recent years, scientific research aimed at improving the breed, productivity, fertility and other breeding traits of cattle in farms and large breeding enterprises of the breeding category has become relevant. Modern, innovative, intensive technologies occupy a special place in the further expansion of the scope of such research. Increasing the volume of milk production due to new innovative intensive technologies, which is of great practical importance and is considered relevant in filling the table of our people. On the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 8, 2022 No. DP-121 "On measures to further develop animal husbandry and strengthen the fodder base of animal husbandry", together with the State Committee for Veterinary Medicine and Livestock Development 2022-2023, the organization of the delivery of livestock and the processing and sale of agricultural products to farms of the population in a cooperative way by at least 1 enterprise for the production and processing of meat and dairy products in each district; in areas where there is a shortage of irrigated land for growing fodder, in order to fully satisfy consumer needs for meat and dairy products, the production and processing of meat and dairy products is being developed in a cooperative way¹.

Purpose of the study. It consists in studying the influence of environmental factors on the productivity and fertility of Holstein cows of various selections in the conditions of the Surkhan oasis and the analysis of other indicators.

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-121 "On measures for the further development of animal husbandry and strengthening the fodder base of animal husbandry." February 8, 2022

Object and method of research. The object of the study is the livestock farm of the Navruz-breeding complex, owned by "Uzbekistan Temir Yollari" JSC, located in the Termez district of the Surkhandarya region. The study used analytical methods based on zootechnical documents.

Discussion of the obtained results. The origin of the cows of the experimental groups and their belonging to different selections were studied according to the primary documents, that is, according to the breeding documents of each cow (Milk - 2 forms).

We studied the fertility characteristics of Holstein cows from different breeding works and presented them in Table 1 below.

According to the table, the study of the age of the first calving of Holstein cows of different breeding groups in the experimental groups showed that the age of the first calving of cows of the Holstein breed of German selection (group I) was higher than that of Polish cows (group II) by 5.0 (P >0.99) and 2.9 (P>0.95) days shorter than that of the Belarusian selection, and it was noted that the body weight at the first calving was 10.0 (P>0.99) and 15.5 (P>0.999) kg is higher in group I bodies than in their peers of groups II and III. The calving period in group I heifers was shorter by 16 days compared to group II, and in group III there was no significant difference. Also, the age of the first calving was 20.9 (P> 0.999) and 16.9 days (P> 0.99) less in cows of group II than in their peers of groups I and III, respectively, and it was noted that their live weight was 26.7 (P>0.99) and 35.1 (P>0.999) kg higher in cows of group I than in cows of groups II and III.

12-month-old Holstein females imported from Germany were divided into 3 groups according to the type of pairs-analogues. The first group (15 heads) was based on a diet composed of feed available on the farm, the females of the second group (n=15) were given 30 g of the "Imnamak" preparation per head per day with concentrated feed for 30 days. In the group that received "Imnamak", the duration of the service period and the level of fertility of cattle improved².

Table 1. Fertility indicators of cows belonging to different breeding breeds

Indicators	Groups					
	I		II		III	
	X ± Sx	Cv, %	X ± Sx	Cv, %	X ± Sx	Cv, %
Age at first conception, days	552,2 ± 5,8	5,78	557,2 ± 4,7	2,67	555,1 ± 7,2	4,07
Live weight at first conception, kg	372,5 ± 1,7	1,45	362,5 ± 3,3	2,85	357,0 ± 2,4	2,11
Duration of pregnancy, days	283,3 ± 8,5	9,53	299,3 ± 11,6	9,53	284,4 ± 8,2	9,15
Age at first birth, days	835,5 ± 11,4	4,31	856,4 ± 9,4	3,46	839,5 ± 3,7	1,40
Live weight at first birth, kg	465,0 ± 7,1	4,84	438,1 ± 6,5	4,69	429,9 ± 3,4	2,49
Service period duration, days	78,8 ± 1,3	5,28	81,1 ± 1,6	6,16	79,5 ± 1,5	5,85
Fertility rate from the 1st cycle, %	76	-	72	-	70	-
Fertilization index	1,38	-	1,53	-	1,41	-

It was noted that the duration of the service period of cows of group I was 2.3 (P> 0.99) and 0.7 days shorter than that of peers of groups II and III, respectively, these indicators are due to the fact that cows in all groups have good fertility characteristics.

There was no significant intergroup difference between the age of cows at the first calving, the duration of calving, the duration of the service period, the degree of calving from the first calving and the calving index of cows in all groups. This indicates that cows of all groups have similar performance in the same conditions of feeding and housing and are well adapted to the conditions of housing.

² Akhtamov M. T., Mamatov, H. A. and Chatparov Sh. T. (2022). indicators of feeding, live weight gain and milk production of Holstein cattle. Scientific Journal of Agrobiotechnology and Veterinary Medicine, 513-516.

Conclusion. Our studies have shown that the fertility rates of Holstein cows of various breeding works are at the level of the biological norm. This indicates the need for their effective use in the dairy herd.

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